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GLOBAL SOLUTIONS**

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LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR CONTROL (SUPERVISION) IN THE FIELD OF GROUNDWATER PROTECTION: CURRENT STATE AND RELEVANT ISSUES IN THE REPUBLIC OF BELARUS

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Abstract. *The article examines the legal framework for control (supervision) in the field of groundwater protection in the Republic of Belarus, analyzes the current state of regulatory and legal provisions, and identifies pertinent issues in this domain. The article formulates recommendations for the enhancement of legislation, including harmonizing the provisions of the Law ‘On Environmental Protection’ with the Sanitary and Epidemiological Requirements for the Protection of Groundwater Bodies Used in Drinking Water Supply from Contamination.*

Keywords: *groundwater, water resources protection, state control, supervision, Water Code of the Republic of Belarus, Subsoil Code, Law on Environmental Protection, sanitary and epidemiological requirements.*

To ensure compliance with legal norms in the field of groundwater protection, as well as the fulfillment of corresponding obligations by water users and subsoil users, it is necessary to implement effective control and supervision measures. These measures constitute an indispensable condition for maintaining discipline, ecological legal order, and safeguarding the right of every individual to a favorable environment in the course of water and subsoil use.

As noted by P. M. Umarova, control constitutes a set of measures implemented by supervisory authorities with respect to the entities under review to assess the conformity of their activities with legislative requirements [1]. In the context of environmental relations, it is appropriate to concur with L. V. Chkhutiashvili, who defines control as a legal form of environmental activity—‘a system of actions aimed at ensuring compliance with environmental legislation and the enforcement by the state of the prescribed coercive measures’ [2; 3, p. 103].

Pursuant to Part 2 of Article 94 of the Law ‘On Environmental Protection,’ control in the field of environmental protection and the rational use of natural resources (environmental control) constitutes a system of measures aimed at preventing,

detecting, and suppressing violations of the legislation on environmental protection and the rational use of natural resources [4]. The purpose of control is to ensure the implementation of legislation by all entities involved in environmental relations within the sphere of environmental protection, as well as to guarantee environmental safety. Control is also aimed at preventing, detecting, and suppressing violations of environmental protection legislation and the rational use of natural resources.

In accordance with the provisions of the Environmental Protection Law, control in the field of groundwater protection, as a component of the natural environment subject to a dual legal regime, entails ensuring compliance by all participants in environmental relations with the norms of water legislation and subsoil legislation. This encompasses compliance with groundwater protection requirements, as well as ensuring environmental safety during water use and subsoil exploitation. This control is focused on the prevention, detection, and cessation of violations of water legislation and subsoil legislation.

In our view, a crucial factor for achieving groundwater protection objectives is the rational use of this resource, alongside the prevention of its pollution, contamination, depletion, and other adverse effects on the environment, specific natural entities and their components, human life and health, as well as protected public interests arising from activities associated with groundwater use. Therefore, it is necessary to comply with the requirements for the remediation of the consequences of such harmful impacts, which corresponds to the fundamental essence of the legal protection of groundwater. In this regard, the primary focus of control is to ensure compliance with groundwater protection legislation by governmental authorities, organizations, and individuals.

These objectives and tasks related to control in the field of environmental protection and the rational use of natural resources must be codified in the Water Code and the Subsoil Code. According to A. S. Chuchmareva, economical and prudent use of groundwater should constitute a paramount strategic course for the state [5].

The general legal framework for the implementation of control in the Republic of Belarus is established by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Belarus dated 16 October 2009. “On the Improvement of Control (Supervision) Activities in the Republic of Belarus” [6]. Special provisions regarding environmental control are contained in the Law “On Environmental Protection” (Chapter 17) [4] and in other legislative acts adopted in furtherance thereof [7]. The fundamental principles of activity within the framework of control should be recognized as its independence, as well as the prohibition of combining the functions of state regulation, management, and control in the field of environmental protection with the functions of nature management (Article 4) [4].

The constitutional foundations of control in the field of environmental protection are enshrined in Article 46, Part 2 of the Constitution of the Republic of Belarus,

which establishes that the state exercises control over the rational use of natural resources to protect and improve living conditions, as well as to safeguard and restore the environment. This provision of the Constitution establishes control as one of the guarantees of the inalienable human right to a favorable environment [8].

Article 59 of the Water Code, Article 11 of the Subsoil Code, and Decree No. 510 designate the implementation of control over the use of groundwater as the responsibility of the Ministry of Natural Resources and Environmental Protection and its territorial authorities. The scope of state control (supervision) in the field of environmental protection is extensive, which accounts for the diverse specific forms and methods of its implementation as stipulated by the Environmental Protection Law (Article 95). In accordance with paragraph 1 of Decree No. 510, state control (supervision) is conducted through selective and unscheduled inspections. measures of a technical (technological, verification) nature; measures of a preventive and precautionary nature [4, 6, 9, 10].

One of the most important tasks of control activities in the field of groundwater use is to establish the negative impact factors on groundwater caused by violations of legislation by water users and subsoil users. The trend towards enhancing the efficiency of groundwater use remains pertinent for all economically developed countries. At the same time, control over the use and protection of groundwater as a function of state administration constitutes a fundamental means to enhance the effectiveness of legal protection of groundwater. The effectiveness of such control will be enhanced by the further refinement of legislation.

State control represents a critical legal measure to ensure the protection of groundwater from the harmful impacts of economic and other activities. The principal functions of control are informational, preventive, and punitive. Control exercised by water users and subsoil users pursuant to the obligations imposed on them by legislation ensures compliance by the water users and subsoil users with state-imposed requirements aimed at protecting groundwater. Accordingly, the functions of such control are considerably narrower compared to those exercised by the state, being primarily informational and, to some extent, preventive in nature.

The Environmental Protection Law imposes an obligation on legal entities and individual entrepreneurs to ensure the implementation of operational monitoring in the areas of environmental protection and rational (sustainable) use of natural resources, including the organization of sampling sites and the conduct of measurements, in accordance with the requirements established by regulatory legal acts, including mandatory technical regulatory legal acts in the field of environmental protection (Article 101) [4].

The sanitary norms and rules entitled 'Sanitary and Epidemiological Requirements for the Protection of Groundwater Bodies Used in Drinking Water Supply from Pollution' designate production control of the water quality

of underground sources of drinking water supply, conducted by the operating organization in accordance with the sanitary norms and rules establishing requirements for the organization and execution of production control to ensure compliance with sanitary regulations and the implementation of sanitary, anti-epidemic, and preventive measures (clause 5 of SanPiN). This control includes the implementation of measures stipulated in the production control program (hereinafter referred to as the program); the conduction of laboratory studies of objects subject to production control; timely notification, in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Belarus, of local executive and administrative bodies, bodies and institutions exercising state sanitary supervision, and the population about emergency situations, violations of technological processes, and/or other circumstances that pose a threat to the sanitary-epidemiological well-being of the population (clause 25 of SanPiN) [11].

Production control shall be conducted in accordance with a program that must be developed and implemented by the entities responsible for production control prior to the commencement of the respective activities. The program concerning the control of safety and harmlessness indicators of water from sources, in relation to human life and health, is developed based on a risk analysis and must include the following information: a list of controlled indicators and their regulated parameters in accordance with the current Sanitary Norms and Regulations that establish requirements for the quality of water in centralized drinking water supply systems, as well as technological documentation, methodologies for conducting laboratory investigations; a plan of water sampling points at water intake sites; the number of controlled water samples and the frequency of their collection for laboratory investigations; responsible executors (clauses 26, 28 of SanPiN) [11].

The safety of drinking water supplied to legal entities and individuals, including individual entrepreneurs, is ensured by the establishment and adherence to drinking water safety standards; maintaining sources of drinking water supply in a condition suitable for use; applying the best available methods, technologies, and facilities used for drinking water treatment; using technological and other equipment, as well as products intended for drinking water treatment, in compliance with mandatory technical regulatory legal acts and the requirements set forth in international legal instruments constituting the law of the Eurasian Economic Union; implementation of operational control to ensure the safety of drinking water; protection of sources of drinking water supply for centralized drinking water supply systems (Art. 21, Law “On Drinking Water Supply”) [12].

Protection of sources of drinking water supply for centralized drinking water supply systems from pollution and contamination is ensured through the establishment of sanitary protection zones for these sources and the regulation of economic and other activities within the boundaries of such zones; compliance

with the regimes governing economic and other activities established within the boundaries of such zones (Art. 24, Law ‘On Drinking Water Supply’) [12].

Sanitary protection zones of sources of drinking water supply for centralized drinking water supply systems comprise three belts: the first belt is designated to protect these sources from pollution and contamination; the second belt is designated to prevent pollution of sources of drinking water supply for centralized drinking water supply systems that causes adverse changes in the microbiological (biological) parameters of drinking water composition; The third zone is designated to prevent contamination of sources of drinking water supply for centralized drinking water supply systems, which results in adverse alterations to the chemical composition parameters of the water (Art. 24, Law ‘On Drinking Water Supply’) [12].

Laboratory analyses within the scope of production control are conducted by entities independently (provided they have an established laboratory) or on a contractual basis by an accredited laboratory in accordance with the procedure established by the legislation of the Republic of Belarus. Laboratory water testing within the framework of state sanitary supervision and industrial control shall be conducted using research methods approved in accordance with the procedures established by the legislation of the Republic of Belarus (clauses 27, 29) [11]. The frequency of laboratory testing and the number of water samples analyzed shall be determined individually for each centralized water supply system, based on a risk analysis that takes into account the degree of sanitary reliability of the water source, and must provide reliable information enabling the prevention of contamination risks. The quantity and frequency of water samples collected for laboratory analysis at water intake sites during the operational period shall comply with the following requirements: microbiological, parasitological, organoleptic, and overall indicators — no fewer than 4 samples annually (seasonally); the content of inorganic and organic substances, and radiological indicators — no fewer than 1 sample annually. Upon detection of pathogenic microflora in the water sources of active centralized drinking water supply systems, urgent measures shall be taken to identify and eliminate the contamination source. Concurrently, it is necessary to increase both the frequency and the number of water sampling points from both the source and the water supply system, and to intensify control over the operation of water supply facilities. Entities subject to industrial control must, upon the request of the authorities and institutions conducting state sanitary supervision, provide information regarding the results of industrial control carried out in accordance with the procedure established by these Sanitary Norms and Rules [11].

Thus, the inconsistency between the Environmental Protection Law and the Sanitary Norms and Rules gives rise to legal uncertainty. The fact is that industrial control is not included in the Law on Environmental Protection. At the same time, this Law distinguishes a category of industrial observations, which can be regarded

as analogous to industrial and departmental control, since it serves similar objectives and functions. In this regard, it is advisable to harmonize the Sanitary Norms and Regulations with the Law 'On Environmental Protection' by replacing the term 'industrial control' with 'industrial observations,' thereby eliminating the existing ambiguity. Furthermore, for the effective implementation of control measures in the field of groundwater protection, it is essential to include provisions concerning sampling and groundwater measurements in both the Water Code and the Subsoil Code.

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SCIENTIFIC DESIGN OF A SYSTEM OF COMPREHENSIVE EDUCATIONAL SUPPORT FOR STUDENTS WITH LEARNING DISABILITIES: FORMULATION OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

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Abstract. *This article is dedicated to defining methodological and scientific-methodological approaches to the scientific design of a system for comprehensive psycho-pedagogical support for the education of children with learning disabilities, who constitute the largest group of learners with special educational needs. The preliminary theoretical study yielded the following main results: for the first time, general and specific approaches to the scientific design of a system of comprehensive psycho-pedagogical support for learners with learning disabilities have been identified; The tasks proposed for resolution within the framework of the scientific research have been formulated; Scientific and practice-oriented results have been planned.*

Keywords: *learners with learning disabilities, psycho-pedagogical support system, collective subject of psycho-pedagogical support, prevention of professional burnout among educators, corrective and developmental methodologies.*

Formulation of the research problem. Improving the education system for the largest and most heterogeneous category of learners with special educational needs — children with learning difficulties — requires equal attention to all participants in the educational process. The increase in psychological stress, the growing complexity of demands on educational outcomes, and the uncertainty of life positions and attitudes in contemporary society equally affect learners, their parents, and educators. In this regard, the creation of a unified system of continuous psycho-pedagogical support is imperative, capable of addressing both the distinct needs of the participants within the educational environment and the complex issues arising in the course of their interaction. The resolution of this issue entails the development of psychological tools and pedagogical technologies to improve the quality of education, harmonize the educational environment,

and promote the activation of personal resources among all participants in the educational process.

The aim of the preliminary theoretical investigation was to determine the scientific and methodological approaches for designing an integrated system of continuous psycho-pedagogical support for learners with learning disabilities and to delineate the tasks proposed for subsequent scientific inquiry.

The methodological foundation of the study was based on the principles of L. S. Vygotsky's cultural-historical theory of development and the activity approach, whereby the child's psychological development is understood as the internalization of socio-cultural experience through activity, communication, and developmental interaction with adults and the peer group; the concept of functional diagnosis as applied to children with mild mental developmental disorders (I. A. Korobeynikov), and the methodology of psychological support within general (I. V. Dubrovin) and special (N. V. Babkina) education contexts. The scientific and methodological approaches developed at the Institute of Special Pedagogy (Russia, Moscow) were applied to identify the special educational needs of learners with disabilities [4; 7; 8]; to evaluate the educational outcomes of learners with disabilities, including their personal achievements [1; 3]; the regulation on a differentiated approach to defining the content of psycho-pedagogical support for learners with learning disabilities [2; 4].

Research methods: analysis of the results of theoretical and experimental studies in the fields of special pedagogy and special psychology addressing the issue of psycho-pedagogical support for learners with learning difficulties; conceptualization of the analysis results in accordance with the aims and objectives of the conducted study; design methodology; analysis of regulatory and program-methodological documentation concerning the education of learners with disabilities.

Results. To achieve the stated objective, scientific research and methodological developments on this issue were analyzed, and the practical experience of educational institutions was summarized and systematized.

It has been determined that the general prerequisites for the development of the designed system of psycho-pedagogical support for learners with learning difficulties, established in the interdisciplinary works of Russian psychologists, educators, and clinicians, were conceptually formulated and specified in the studies of N. V. Babkina [3; 5; 6]. The result of this work was the development of a psychological support system for younger schoolchildren with learning disabilities [5]. To date, there are also specific practice-oriented methodological recommendations addressed to educational psychologists in educational institutions working with adolescents facing learning difficulties [9]. However, a holistic, scientifically grounded, and empirically validated system of continuous psycho-pedagogical support for learners with learning disabilities, encompassing all levels of general education and all participants in the

educational process (the 'collective subject,' including the child, their family, teachers, specialists of the psycho-pedagogical service, and the administration of the educational institution), is currently lacking.

The body of results from existing scientific and methodological developments, both completed and requiring further theoretical and empirical validation, can be considered the foundational basis for formulating new research tasks that extend the conceptual context and methodological tools for enhancing the conditions and quality of education for learners with learning disabilities, as well as for learners with analogous special educational needs, including those with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. Among these are, in particular, the tasks of studying the prerequisites for the emergence and the possibilities of preventing desocialization in adolescents with learning difficulties, which often precedes the development of deviant behavior, including its addictive forms.

The conducted in-depth analysis of the literature reveals that, within special psychology, both theoretical and scientific-methodological aspects of this issue are presented fragmentarily and outside the integrated context of educational environment characteristics. There is a need for an in-depth study of the factors that reduce the adaptive resources of educators working with students with learning disabilities, particularly in the context of inclusive education. The results of planned and partially completed scientific research projects, possessing independent theoretical and practical value, can be most effectively implemented only as an integrated whole.

The conceptualization of the theoretical analysis results regarding the current state of psycho-pedagogical support for students with learning disabilities enabled the formulation of the primary objective of the planned scientific research: the development of a system of continuous psycho-pedagogical support for students with learning disabilities, applicable to all levels of education and all participants in the educational process; would ensure the possibility of productive interaction among all participants; would facilitate the effective utilization of scientific and methodological developments in addressing both specific and general tasks of psycho-pedagogical support for learners with learning disabilities. Moreover, in light of evolving social demands, an initial comparative study is planned between learners with learning disabilities and learners with analogous conditions that cause difficulties in their upbringing and education (in particular, those with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder and children undergoing prolonged treatment).

Conclusion. Addressing the tasks set requires fundamentally new approaches that consider not only the characteristics of the specific nosological category under study but also current trends in the education of students with disabilities overall, alongside the priorities outlined in the Strategy for the Development of Education in the Russian Federation.

The scientific outcomes of the planned research will provide the methodological basis for designing systems of continuous psycho-pedagogical support for children with disabilities from various nosological categories within the modern educational environment. The developed unified system of continuous psycho-pedagogical support for the collective educational subject of learners with learning disabilities is recommended for broad application in educational practice within modern and prospective models of psycho-medical-pedagogical assistance. These models provide for the expansion of networked interaction (including remote consultations with specialists and collaboration with resource centers) and the enhancement of the role and accountability of the psycho-pedagogical council within the educational organization.

The practical significance of the anticipated research results lies in the implementation, within broad educational practice, of a scientifically substantiated, comprehensive system of continuous psycho-pedagogical support for learners with learning disabilities, encompassing all levels of general education and all participants in the educational process (the learner, their family, educators, specialists of the psycho-pedagogical service, and the administration of the educational institution), oriented towards current requirements regarding the content, conditions, and outcomes of education, and supported by the necessary methodological resources. Specialists of psychological-medical-pedagogical commissions and psychological-pedagogical councils of educational institutions will have the opportunity to utilize ready-made domestic developments for conducting diagnostic and psycho-corrective work with students, preventing professional burnout, and supporting educators working with students with learning disabilities in various educational contexts.

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CONFLICTS AND THE SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CLIMATE IN THE WORKFORCE OF NURSES

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Abstract. *This article presents the results of a study on the socio-psychological climate (SPC) within the collective of nursing staff in a therapeutic department. Objective and subjective factors influencing the level of conflict within this collective, the primary causes of conflicts, and the behavioral strategies of nurses in conflict situations have been identified. Measures have been proposed to reduce conflict levels and improve the socio-psychological climate within this collective.*

Keywords: *socio-psychological climate, medical organization, conflict, factors influencing SPC*

Introduction

A substantial number of studies have been devoted to examining the SPC, the factors affecting it, and the influence of the socio-psychological climate on the quality of the collective's performance [2–4, 7, 10]. Different authors provide various definitions of socio-psychological climate. The socio-psychological climate is a comprehensive characteristic of relationships and employees' satisfaction with various factors of the collective's life activity [5]. The socio-psychological climate refers to the relationships among employees, as well as those between management and subordinates [6]. The socio-psychological climate encompasses the general mood within the collective, management style, and the characteristics of work and rest [9].

Thus, despite various formulations of SPC, its essence lies in being a quality of the internal environment of an organization, which influences each employee within that organization. A favorable internal environment within the collective is one of the most important conditions for the efficiency of the collective's activities.

In a medical organization, relationships among members of the collective, as well as between subordinates and management, hold particular significance, as

the quality of their work directly impacts patients' health and lives. Nursing work belongs to the most complex and responsible types of activity. It is characterized by significant intellectual demands and, in some cases, considerable physical effort. It requires attention, endurance, and a high level of work capacity, often under extreme conditions and with a severe lack of time [1]. The work of a nurse in an inpatient setting involves substantial psychological and physical stress. However, the issue is not solely related to the professional training of the nurse; the conditions in which she works, including the socio-psychological climate, are also of considerable importance [11]. The responsibility of the manager is to evaluate the existing socio-psychological climate within the collective, identify the causes and factors contributing to conflicts, and foster a favorable internal environment to ensure high-quality work.

Objective — to investigate the causes of conflicts and factors affecting the socio-psychological climate within the nursing workforce at the hospital stage.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted in the therapeutic department of the healthcare institution 'Road Clinical Hospital' at Chelyabinsk station.

The following methods were employed: extraction of data from accounting and reporting documentation, survey, and mathematical-statistical method. Self-assessment of approval motivation was conducted using the test by D. Marlowe and D. Crown. The socio-psychological climate within the collective was assessed using the methodology of V. M. Zavyalova. Behavioral strategies in conflict situations were assessed using the methodology of K. Thomas (Antsupov A. Ya., et al., 2006), adapted by N. V. Grishina (2006).

A complete enumeration method was employed in the study. The sample comprised 56 individuals.

Results and Discussion

A collective is a group of individuals united by common activity, work, or a specific goal. Within the collective, a particular type of relationship is formed, with no sharp distinctions between personal and collective interests. Only under these conditions will the tasks facing the collective be accomplished. A collective cannot be formed without specific efforts, determination, and trust [8]. In relation to the nursing collective, these groups are focused on delivering quality medical care, restoring health, and preserving patients' lives. Senior members of the collective play a significant role, as their industrial and professional experience, autonomy, conscientiousness, and loyalty to the collective increase over time. On the other hand, the predominance of employees in this age group may negatively affect the socio-psychological climate in the event of the introduction of any innovations

within the collective. According to the results of our study, more than half of the surveyed nurses were aged 40 years or older. Length of service influences the quality of work, and consequently, the number of defects in medical care provision, which in turn affects the level of conflict within the collective. In this collective, nurses with more than 11 years of experience predominated, which may indicate higher work quality and conflict prevention. Unequal qualifications and levels of professionalism among nurses may also influence the SPC within the collective, as individuals without certification generally exhibit more frequent work deficiencies, which may cause social tension and lead to conflicts. According to the results of our study, 42.0% of nurses lack a qualification category.

A high turnover rate among nurses has been observed, with only 23.5% leaving due to retirement. Workplace relationships within the collective, as well as the systems of management, control, and employee motivation, significantly affect staff turnover.

The staffing level of nurses is 79.5%, while that of junior medical personnel is 56.0%. At this stage of the study, it can already be assumed that a risk factor for an adverse socio-psychological climate is insufficient staffing of middle and junior medical personnel, as increased workload leads to accumulated fatigue and dissatisfaction with working conditions and schedules, which may result in both horizontal conflicts (unsatisfactory relationships among employees of the same level — nurses) and vertical conflicts (between management and subordinate staff). Conflicts among the department staff are reported by 73.5% of respondents, with the majority (32.6%) adopting an avoidance strategy and 22.2% accommodation; furthermore, 64.4% of respondents demonstrate high levels of approval motivation. This behavioral strategy results in the accumulation of negative emotions and the deterioration of the psychological climate within the collective.

Special attention should be given to the labor intensity of the nursing staff. Eighty-five percent of nurses work more than one full-time equivalent position, which is related on the one hand to insufficient staffing and on the other hand to low wages.

The study revealed that only 37.0% of respondents were fully satisfied with relationships within the collective. However, the socio-psychological climate cannot be defined solely by employee satisfaction [7]. For instance, management style affects the SPC within the collective [6]. The respondents identified three classic management styles. This fact, on the one hand, may indicate flexibility in management within this collective, and on the other, suggests that the nurses evaluated the management style based on the measures applied to each of them. Moreover, the respondents may not be well acquainted with the characteristics of specific management styles. Nevertheless, according to the majority of respondents, the authoritarian management style predominates within the collective. More than half of the nurses responded in this manner. The authoritarian management style

induces feelings of inferiority in subordinates, undermines their self-confidence, and hampers opportunities for further career advancement. Simultaneously, one in ten respondents believes that a liberal management style most frequently predominates within the collective. This group of surveyed nurses noted that staff are often left to their own devices, with notably weak supervision over task completion. The respondents explain this by noting that management hesitates to reprimand or sanction employees due to low staffing levels and high turnover. All of this leads to disorganization within the collective, a decrease in labor and executive discipline, deterioration of the psychological climate, and adversely affects work quality, which in turn again results in conflicts. One in three nurses believes that a democratic management style predominates in the department. Under this leadership style, the most positive relationships develop among members of the work collective, as this style enhances the leader's interest in the issues faced by collective members; informal relationships predominate, and members of the collective demonstrate a heightened willingness to work and communicate [4].

A significant factor for the SPC within the collective is employees' satisfaction with their work [2]. One in ten employees is dissatisfied with horizontal relationships, that is, with their colleagues, while 26.0% are dissatisfied with vertical relationships, that is, with supervisors at various levels. Working conditions are unsatisfactory for 15.0% of respondents. The largest proportion comprises those dissatisfied with their salary — 40.0%, while the remainder have lost interest in their work. In addition to the base (official) salary, nursing staff receive an incentive bonus for work quality. More than two-thirds (65.3%) of respondents consider the evaluation of their work by management to be unfair. According to the respondents, the primary criterion for evaluating work is the personal affinity of the supervisor. It is evident that such an incentive systems does not foster good relationships either among employees themselves or between subordinates and supervisors. The system of material incentives influences the psychological atmosphere within the labor collective, its socio-psychological climate, reduces workers' creative activity, and contributes to the development of a negative attitude towards work.

Respondents were asked how often they receive rewards by any methods (excluding incentive bonuses). The majority (42.9%) of respondents received a reward once in the past three years, while 12.0% have never received any rewards or other forms of encouragement. Analysis of responses to the question 'How did the rewards affect your subsequent work?' showed that 79.3% of respondents' attitudes toward work remained unchanged, indicating that incentive bonuses and various rewards do not motivate nurses to improve the quality of their work nor positively influence their attitude toward work. This is due to the infrequency of rewards, lack of clear criteria for evaluating work quality, and the insignificance of the incentive bonus relative to the salary, which fails to motivate better performance.

One of the components of collective management is the control of the quality of medical care. The principle of regularity in its implementation plays an important role. According to the responses, quality control is conducted daily (42.3%), weekly (11.6%), 'spontaneously' (41.4%), and 4.7% of respondents were unable to answer. It can be assumed that nurses, on the one hand, have a limited understanding of what quality control is and how it should be conducted, and on the other hand, that the control is in fact carried out irregularly. The second equally important principle of control is transparency. However, 10.8% of respondents stated that deficiencies identified during control of nurses' work are not discussed either with the employee personally or within the collective. The control procedure itself, its frequency, and the discussion of results generate a conflict situation. Only 36.8% of respondents have not received any disciplinary sanctions resulting from control during their employment; 53.6% have had sanctions 'one to two times,' 5.7% 'more than two times,' and 3.9% of nurses receive sanctions annually based on control outcomes.

The level of conflict is influenced by the organization of joint activities, that is, the formal structure of the group [2]. According to 53.1% of respondents, when scheduling shifts, the head nurse does not consider factors such as employees' experience and length of service, their psychological characteristics, interpersonal relations, and age.

Conclusions

Only 37.0% of respondents are fully satisfied with the relationships within the collective. Conflicts among the department staff are reported by 73.5% of respondents.

The primary causes of conflicts within the collective are an irrational system for calculating incentive bonuses to wages, violations of work quality control principles, high workload combined with inadequate wages, absence of a system for adapting young employees, and unsatisfactory working conditions. More than half of the surveyed nurses reported that they would seek help from a psychologist; however, such a specialist is not available within the medical organization.

Based on the results of the study, recommendations were developed and presented at the medical and nursing staff conference.

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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING AND SELF-ESTEEM IN FIRST-YEAR UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract. *Psychological well-being and self-esteem play a key role in the adaptation of first-year university students to new academic and social environments. This article examines the correlational relationship between these constructs based on empirical data. The study was conducted on a sample of 250 students (aged 17–19 years) using the “Personal Psychological Well-Being Scale” (Samokhvalov et al.) and the Dembo-Rubinstein method adapted by A. M. Prikhozhan. The results demonstrated a positive correlation ($r = 0.62$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that high self-esteem supports the stability of psychological well-being.*

Keywords: *psychological well-being, self-esteem, first-year students, adaptation, higher education.*

Introduction

The transition to university represents a critical period in the psychological development of students. First-year students encounter the loss of the familiar social support inherent in school, increased academic demands, and the necessity for autonomous planning. During this period, psychological well-being — defined as an integrated state of emotional stability, life satisfaction, and personal growth — is susceptible to disruption. Self-esteem, as a stable evaluation of one’s own worth, is a significant predictor of adaptation.

The objective of the study is to establish the degree of correlation between psychological well-being and self-esteem in first-year university students. Hypothesis: a positive correlation exists between levels of psychological well-being and self-esteem, with a stronger association observed in individuals with low self-esteem. The relevance of the topic is underscored by the rise in psycho-emotional problems among young people: according to data [8], up to 57% of university students exhibit symptoms of depression of varying severity.

Theoretical Foundations

Psychological Well-being according to the model of Samokhvalova A. G. et al. [5] encompasses components of emotional resilience, self-actualization, and social connections. A low level of psychological well-being correlates with anxiety and burnout [7]. Self-esteem, assessed using the Dembo-Rubinstein method in the adaptation by A. M. Prikhojan [2], measures the subjective significance of traits and the level of aspiration.

Analysis of domestic research indicates a moderate positive correlation between psychological well-being and self-esteem among students. Among first-year students, this relationship is intensified due to adaptation stress: low self-esteem exacerbates the perception of failures, thereby diminishing psychological well-being. Research by S. A. Rusina [4] demonstrated that 62% of students with low self-esteem exhibit deficits in psychological well-being.

Research Methodology

Sample: 250 first-year students from a pedagogical university (70 males (28%), 180 females (72%), mean age 18.2 ± 0.8 years). Instruments: Psychological Well-Being Scale [6]; Dembo-Rubinstein method in the A. M. Prikhozhan modification [2]; COPE Stress Coping Questionnaire (C. S. Carver, M. F. Scheier, J. K. Weintraub) [1, 3]. Procedure: group administration of questionnaires; statistical analysis conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics version 23, including Pearson correlation analysis, regression, and Student's t-test. Ethical standards were adhered to (informed consent obtained).

Results

Descriptive statistics indicated a normal distribution of scores (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, $p > 0.05$). The mean level of psychological well-being was 115.4 ± 14.2 points (normal range 100–140). Low psychological well-being (below 105) was observed in 32% of students, medium levels in 45%, and high levels (above 130) in 23%. Self-esteem: $M = 6.8 \pm 1.2$ points (normal range 5–8). Low self-esteem was found in 28% of students, medium in 52%, and high in 20%. Females demonstrated higher self-esteem ($M = 7.0$ versus 6.4 in males; $t = 2.89$, $p < 0.01$), whereas psychological well-being did not significantly differ by gender ($p = 0.12$).

Correlation analysis revealed a strong positive relationship between psychological well-being and self-esteem: $r = 0.62$ ($p < 0.001$). This association was strengthened when controlling for coping strategies. Specifically, among students with low self-esteem ($n = 70$), $r = 0.71$ ($p < 0.001$); with medium self-esteem ($n = 130$), $r = 0.59$; and with high self-esteem ($n = 50$), $r = 0.48$ (differences were significant, $z = 2.15$, $p < 0.05$). Preference for active coping strategies correlated with both psychological well-being ($r = 0.55$, $p < 0.01$) and high self-esteem ($r =$

0.48, $p < 0.01$). The affective component (self-acceptance, satisfaction) correlated with self-esteem, $r = 0.68$; the cognitive component (self-concept), $r = 0.59$; the conative component (self-actualization), $r = 0.55$; the reflective component (awareness), $r = 0.49$; the value-semantic component (goals), $r = 0.52$ ($p < 0.01$).

Table 1 presents the correlation matrix.

Table 1. Intercorrelation Matrix

Indicator	Psychological well-being	Self-esteem	Coping strategy
Psychological well-being	1	0,62**	0,55**
Self-esteem		1	0,48**
Coping strategy			1

Note: ** $p < 0.01$.

Students with high self-esteem demonstrated psychological well-being 25% higher ($M = 128.3 \pm 11.5$) than those with low self-esteem ($M = 102.7 \pm 10.8$; $F(2, 247) = 42.3$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2 = 0.26$). Post hoc (Tukey): all pairs differ significantly ($p < 0.01$). Regression analysis: self-esteem accounts for 38.4% of the variance in psychological well-being ($\beta = 0.55$, $t = 12.1$, $p < 0.001$; $R^2 = 0.384$, $F = 145.2$, $p < 0.001$). Table 2 presents the relationship between levels of psychological well-being and self-esteem.

Table 2. Comparison of psychological well-being across levels of self-esteem

Self-esteem level	n	M _{PW} \pm SD
Low (<6)	70	102,7 \pm 10,8
Medium (6–7.5)	130	116,2 \pm 12,1
High (>7.5)	50	128,3 \pm 11,5

Among the seven scales, the strongest correlations with psychological well-being were observed in the self-esteem scales ‘self-confidence’ ($r = 0.65$), ‘abilities’ ($r = 0.61$), and ‘appearance’ ($r = 0.58$); Below — ‘peer authority’ ($r = 0.45$). The discrepancy between aspirations and self-esteem correlated negatively with psychological well-being ($r = -0.42$).

Table 3 presents the results of students specializing in pedagogical fields and those enrolled in the psychology-pedagogical education program.

Students enrolled in teacher education programs exhibit higher levels of psychological well-being and self-esteem compared to students in psychological and pedagogical education programs; consequently, the latter require increased attention in the planning of psychological support programs. The data obtained confirm the predictive role of self-esteem in psychological well-being.

Table 3. Comparison of psychological well-being and self-esteem by field of study

Field of study	n	Psychological well-being	Self-esteem	Correlation between psychological well-being and self-esteem
Teacher Education	140	118,5 ±14,0	7,1 ±1,1	0,65**
Psychological and Pedagogical Education	110	111,9 ±14,3	6,4 ±1,2	0,58**

Note: **p < 0.01.

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RELATIONSHIP OF COPING STRATEGIES WITH STRESS AND PROPENSITY TO ADDICTIVE BEHAVIOR AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract. *This article presents the results of a study aimed at determining the correlation between coping mechanisms in stressful situations and the level of predisposition to addictive forms of behavior among young people. The research involved 40 respondents who completed two psychodiagnostic assessments: a questionnaire measuring coping strategies and a scale assessing propensity toward addictive behavior. The analytical methodology included descriptive statistics, normality testing, as well as correlational and regression analyses.*

The findings demonstrated a pronounced susceptibility toward specific types of addictive behavior, particularly drug and alcohol use. The study established that predisposition to addiction positively correlates with a wide range of coping strategies, including both adaptive and maladaptive ones. Notably, denial emerged as a critical risk factor, showing a statistically significant contribution to predicting drug-related addictive tendencies in the regression model. These results point to the ambiguous nature of coping behavior in youth, who may rely on ostensibly constructive strategies but employ them ineffectively under emotional strain.

The findings underscore the relevance of developing preventive programs aimed at fostering conscious and adaptive stress-coping skills while reducing avoidance and other maladaptive reactions. The study contributes to a deeper understanding of the psychological mechanisms underlying addictive behavior among youth and outlines promising directions for future research.

Keywords: youth; coping strategies; stress; addictive behavior; addiction proneness; denial; correlational analysis; addiction prevention

Introduction. The relevance of examining the relationship between coping strategies and addictive behavior among youth is driven by the accelerating pace of social and digital transformation. Increasing exposure to academic, social and economic stressors makes young people vulnerable to seeking rapid means of emotional relief and reward. Understanding both protective and risk-related coping patterns is crucial for the development of targeted prevention and intervention programs.

Theoretical foundations are based on the typology of coping strategies: problem-focused coping (active problem solving), emotion-focused coping (regulating affect), and avoidance-based patterns (distraction, denial). Empirical findings consistently demonstrate associations between avoidance-dominant or impulsive coping and heightened risk of behavioral and chemical addictions, while adaptive strategies correlate with improved self-regulation and stress resilience. Mechanisms underlying this relationship include reduced impulse control, heightened need for immediate reward and weakened cognitive-social resources for long-term planning.

The purpose of this article is to empirically examine the relationship between various coping strategies and predisposition to addictive behavior among youth, identify key predictors of addictive tendencies, and propose evidence-based recommendations for prevention. Research objectives include: assessing the prevalence of different coping strategies among youth; analyzing correlational and regression models to determine predictive roles of coping strategies in various types of addictive behavior; discussing potential interventions that support the development of adaptive coping skills.

The practical relevance of the study lies in its applicability to designing digital literacy programs, emotional regulation training, and school or university mental health initiatives. Identifying vulnerable coping profiles allows preventive resources to be directed toward those at risk, mitigating long-term negative effects of addiction on educational and social functioning.

Literature review. Modern youth navigate increasing stress loads driven by academic pressure, uncertainty regarding the future, interpersonal conflicts, and peer and family expectations. In the context of chronic stress, selecting effective coping strategies is vital for maintaining psychological well-being. Dysfunctional coping strategies can serve as predictors of addictive behavior, including both chemical addictions (substance misuse) and non-chemical forms (internet addiction, gambling, gaming, etc.).

According to the classical framework of Lazarus & Folkman (1984), two fundamental categories of coping were identified:

Problem-focused coping — strategies aimed at changing or eliminating the stressor itself.

Emotion-focused coping — strategies aimed at regulating negative emotions associated with the stressor, without altering the situation.[1]

Subsequent research, including Hobfoll (2007), expanded the model to incorporate maladaptive patterns such as avoidance, denial, substance use for relief and immersion in virtual environments.[2]

Studies by Kovaleva & Kuznetsova (2021) have shown that students with pronounced internet addiction rely on avoidance and emotional reactions, while lower-risk individuals exhibit more constructive coping and social support.[3]

Maltseva (2020) found that adolescents struggling to manage anxiety often resort to smoking and drinking as compensatory stress-relief mechanisms.[4]

Baranova & Kuznetsova (2022) emphasized that emotional self-regulation and strong social ties protect against reliance on addiction-prone coping patterns.[5]

Smirnova (2019) identified that students predisposed to both chemical and behavioral addictions tend to favor avoidance-based strategies combined with insufficient self-control.

Empirical findings consistently confirm positive associations between maladaptive coping and addiction risk. Avoidance, denial and substance use as coping strategies are significant risk factors because they fail to address underlying causes and instead reinforce dependence on external means of emotion regulation. Conversely, problem-focused coping is linked to greater resilience and reduced addiction susceptibility.

Underlying psychological mechanisms include:

- emotional dysregulation, contributing to compensatory addictive patterns;
- deficits in social and cognitive resources, increasing vulnerability;
- impulsivity and limited self-reflection, reinforcing short-term behaviors such as substance use.

Methods and materials. Forty respondents aged 18–25 studying at higher education institutions in Almaty took part in the study. Participants represented both humanities and technical specializations.

Instruments

Coping Assessment (COPE Inventory) The Russian-adapted version of the Coping Orientation to Problems Experienced (COPE), developed by Carver, Scheier and Weintraub (1989), was used. It consists of 15 subscales covering a wide range of responses including active problem solving, planning, seeking help, avoidance, diversion and the use of harmful habits (e. g., alcohol, intoxicants). Respondents rated frequency of use from 1 («never») to 4 («very often»).

Addictive Behavior Scale The questionnaire «Proneness to Addictive Behavior», developed by V. D. Mendelevich, assesses the propensity for various forms of addictive behavior among adolescents and young adults.

Results and discussion. Analysis of the average (Table 1) indicators of propensity to addictive behavior among young people revealed the dominance of drug addiction (average value 105.1) and a significant level of alcohol dependence (среднее mean 91.3). Less pronounced were the tendencies to fanaticism (average value 48.3) and gambling addiction (average value 44.9).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics — propensity to addictive behavior

Scale	N	M	Median	Mode	Σ	SD	Variance	Min	Max
Addiction to drugs	40	105.1	104.0	89.0	4203	14.0	197	76	128
Addiction to alcohol	40	91.3	96.0	63.0	3651	17.2	297	63	120
Sports and music fanaticism	40	48.3	51.0	28.0	1933	13.2	174	24	72
Addiction to computer games	40	44.9	48.0	20.0	1794	16.4	271	20	70

Analysis of coping strategies (Table 2) revealed a moderate distribution of their use. The most frequently used methods were: conversion to religion (average value M=11.22), positive reformulation (M=10.57), and planning (M=10.18) [Kniga4]. The results of testing the normality of the distribution showed that most of the studied variables deviate from the normal distribution ($p < .05$). This circumstance requires a careful approach to the interpretation of the results obtained using parametric statistical methods.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics-coping strategies

Strategy	M	Median	Σ	SD	Variance
Positive Reformulation and Personal Growth	10.57	11.50	423	3.95	15.64
Mental Withdrawal	8.35	9.00	334	3.20	10.23
Emotional Focus	8.60	8.00	344	3.61	13.07
Instrumental Social	Support 8.90	9.00	356	3.53	12.45
Active Coping	9.97	10.00	399	3.79	14.38
Denial	7.88	8.00	315	2.86	8.16
Turning to Religion	11.22	12.50	449	4.53	20.49
Humor	8.18	8.00	327	3.59	12.92
Behavioral withdrawal	8.13	8.00	325	3.24	10.52
Deterrence	9.35	10.00	374	3.66	13.41
Emotional Social support	8.82	9.00	353	3.76	14.15
Use of «Sedatives»	6.13	4.00	245	3.47	12.01
Acceptance	9.68	10.00	387	3.63	13.15

Strategy	M	Median	Σ	SD	Variance
Suppression of competing activities	8.88	9.00	355	3.31	10.93
Planning	10.18	10.50	407	3.93	15.48

Correlation analysis has shown that addiction is closely related to various coping strategies. It was found that the higher the propensity to addictions, the more actively a person uses a variety of copings.

In particular, for drug addiction, the most pronounced associations were with denial, seeking instrumental social support, actively overcoming problems and focusing on their emotions.

Similar trends were observed for alcohol dependence, where there were also strong positive correlations with active coping, denial, concentration on emotions, and use of social support.

A common pattern can be traced for both gaming and fanatical addictions: they also positively correlate with all the copings studied. This suggests that young people with an increased propensity for addiction resort to a wide range of behavioral responses, including those that may not be the most adaptive.

It is worth noting that the use of strategies aimed at «calming down» (for example, to relieve tension) showed significantly weaker and sometimes statistically insignificant associations with addictions (Table 3).

Table 3. Matrix of significant correlations (Pearson r)

Copingstrategy / Scale	Drug Addiction	Alcohol addiction.	Fanaticism	Computer games
Denial	0.684	0.731	0.722	0.706
Concentration on emotions	0.552	0.747	0.696	0.662
Active coping	0.544	0.738	0.676	0.597
Planning	0.557	0.695	0.634	0.587
Mental Withdrawal	0.506	0.670	0.577	0.573

Evaluation of the reliability of the results: Cronbach's highest reliability index α was 0.922. This indicates a high degree of internal consistency of the scale items and confirms the suitability of the tool used for assessment in this group of subjects.

Regression models allowed us to establish that the factors under study explain a significant part of the variability in the propensity to different types of addictions:

Drug addiction: Models explain 65.6% of the variability ($p < .001$).

Alcohol dependence: Models explain 76.5% of the variability ($p < .001$).

Fanaticism: Models explain 70.5% of the variability ($p < .001$).

Game addiction: Models explain 65.1% of the variability ($p < .001$).

Despite the high explanatory power of the models as a whole, only a small number of individual predictors (factors) showed a statistically significant effect:

Denial was a significant predictor of drug addiction ($p=.029$).

For fanaticism, active coping was a significant predictor ($p=.041$).

The remaining coping strategies (coping strategies) did not show a statistically significant contribution when all factors were taken into account at the same time. This may indicate that these strategies themselves are closely related to each other, and their impact on each other can be «leveled» within the framework of a comprehensive analysis (Table 4).

Table 4. Summary indicators of regression models

Dependent variable	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	COEX
Addiction	0.810	0.656	0.440	8.13
Addiction to alcohol	0.874	0.765	0.617	8.25
Sports and music fanaticism	0.840	0.705	0.521	7.07
Addiction to computer games	0.807	0.651	0.433	9.59

Research has shown that young people who are prone to addictions use a variety of but often ineffective ways to deal with stress. Interestingly, their addiction tendencies are linked not only to harmful strategies such as denial, problem avoidance, and emotional obsession, but also to seemingly beneficial ones such as planning, taking active actions, and seeking social support. This supports the theory that young people can use different tactics in stressful situations, but their success depends on self-control, maturity, and emotional state. It is important to note that denial turned out to be the only reliable indicator of addiction, which highlights the role of avoiding reality in the development of addiction. The weak association of «sedatives» as a coping method may indicate that this strategy is not widely adopted or understood in this group.

Key findings:

- The strongest addiction tendencies emerged in drug and alcohol domains ($M=105.1$ and $M=91.3$).
- Coping patterns were moderately used, with religion, reappraisal and planning most frequent.
- Most variables deviated from normal distribution.
- Correlations showed significant positive associations across nearly all coping strategies and addiction scales — suggesting that youth employ many coping tactics but often unproductively.
- Denial emerged as the only reliable predictor of drug addiction.
- Active coping predicted fan behavior.
- Overall models accounted for 65%–76% of variance across addiction types.

These results demonstrate that adaptability of coping style is not defined solely by form but by effectiveness and psychological maturity with which the strategy is employed.

Conclusion. The study confirmed significant correlations between stress-coping strategies and addictive behavior proneness among youth. Young people with elevated addictive tendencies tend to employ not only maladaptive coping strategies, such as denial and avoidance, but also a wide range of ostensibly adaptive strategies — although often ineffectively. Denial was identified as the most stable predictor of drug-related addiction proneness, supporting the central role of avoidance in the etiology of addiction.

The findings underscore the need for psychological interventions aimed at enhancing adaptive coping and reducing reliance on avoidance and emotionally driven strategies. Preventive efforts are particularly important in youth populations where stress often triggers the pursuit of immediate emotional relief through risky behaviors. Future research should expand sample size, examine cultural determinants and explore distinctions across types of addictions and personality profiles.

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DIAGNOSIS OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN PRESCHOOLERS AND ITS ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATION SKILLS

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Annotation. *This article is devoted to the issues of determining the level of emotional intelligence in preschoolers and its role in the development of communication skills. Emotional intelligence is a key factor in a child's mental development, affecting their ability to understand and express emotions, empathize, and build relationships with others. Since it is at preschool age that basic communication skills are formed, early diagnosis of emotional intelligence helps to identify individual characteristics and possible difficulties in social interaction. The article provides an overview of modern methods for assessing emotional intelligence in children, including their ability to recognize emotions, understand emotional signals, and show empathy.*

Special attention is paid to the relationship between the level of emotional intelligence and the success of communication in a children's team. The results of the study confirm the importance of comprehensive diagnosis and subsequent correctional and developmental work for the formation of emotional competence, which is the foundation of effective communication. The practical value of the work lies in the possibility of applying the data obtained to create psychological support programs for preschoolers that promote their harmonious emotional and communicative development.

Keywords: *emotional intelligence, preschooler, diagnosis, development, communication skills, emotion recognition, empathy, mutual understanding.*

Introduction.

In the context of modern education, the development of emotional intelligence in preschool children is recognized as one of the fundamental aspects that determine their successful socialization and further educational trajectory. Emotional intelligence acts as a powerful predictor of social competence, directly influencing a child's ability to recognize and understand emotions, effectively manage their behavior, and build constructive interactions with both adults and peers. In this regard, increasing attention to the emotional and personal development of preschoolers is becoming a priority for teachers and psychologists.

Diagnosis of emotional intelligence in preschoolers plays a key role, performing a number of interrelated functions. It allows you not only to identify the current level of development of such important skills as emotion recognition, empathy and establishing mutual understanding, but also to identify potential risk areas in interpersonal communication. In addition, the diagnostic results serve as the basis for the justification and planning of effective correctional and developmental programs. Russian psychological and pedagogical literature consistently emphasizes the need for a systematic approach to diagnosis, which involves the integration of various methods: from direct observation in natural conditions to the use of standardized techniques and qualitative interpretation of the data obtained.

The practical implementation of the diagnosis of emotional intelligence in preschoolers is based on a variety of tools. It includes structured observations in play and household activities, conversations and interviews with a child, analysis of the products of his creative activity, projective techniques, as well as specialized tests aimed at recognizing facial expressions and emotional states. The comprehensive use of this toolkit makes it possible to evaluate both the cognitive and affective components of emotional intelligence, as well as their manifestation in real-world communicative situations. Special importance is attached to the assessment of empathy and the ability to establish mutual understanding, since these skills are the cornerstone for the formation of stable interpersonal relationships in the preschool group.

The purpose of this article is to conduct a comprehensive psychodiagnostic examination of the level of emotional intelligence in preschool children and a subsequent analysis of its role in the development of communication skills. The study will be based on empirical data obtained using modern and proven assessment methods.

Literary review.

The ability of preschoolers to understand and manage their emotions, as well as recognize the feelings of others, known as emotional intelligence, is considered a cornerstone for successful adaptation to society and the development of communication skills. According to D. Goleman, this includes the child's

ability to recognize, express and control his emotions, as well as to understand the emotional state of others [1]. In Russian psychological science, the development of emotional intelligence is closely linked to the idea of scientist L. S. Vygotsky about the inextricable link between feelings and thinking [2].

In the research of Savenkova T. D. and other scientists, it is noted that a high level of emotional intelligence contributes to the development of empathy, reducing the number of conflicts and developing effective ways of interacting with others [3]. A. A. Gavrilova points out that children with developed emotional intelligence are easier to integrate into a team, are able to verbally express their feelings and understand the emotions of their peers, what is the basis for building a harmonious relationship [4].

The diagnosis of emotional intelligence in preschoolers performs a number of important functions:

- Determining the degree of awareness and the ability to self-regulate emotions.
- Identification of problems in the sphere of communication and interaction with others.
- Development of individual and group programs aimed at developing emotional intelligence.
- Monitoring the child's progress in an educational institution [3].

Thus, diagnostics becomes not only an assessment tool, but also an active tool for improving communication skills. Emotional intelligence plays a primary role in the formation of communication skills in preschoolers. Its timely diagnosis enables educators and psychologists to identify emerging difficulties and develop development programs aimed at improving children's social competence and preparing them for further education.

Materials and methods.

The study was conducted on the basis of kindergarden No. 153 in Almaty. 52 children from preparatory groups aged 5–6 years took part in it. The ratio of boys and girls in the group was natural for kindergarden groups. All the children regularly attended the institution. The children's participation in the study was coordinated with both the kindergarden administration and their parents.

To diagnose the emotional intelligence of preschool children, the «Emotional Faces» technique was used (developed by N. Y. Semago). This basic tool was designed to determine how well a child can recognize and describe basic emotions from facial images, as well as relate them to real-life situations.

A special form was used in the diagnostic examination procedure to record how children interact with each other during games and in group activities. The protocol included such items as: starting communication, maintaining conversation, resolving conflict situations and using speech strategies. Also, cards

with images of faces, forms for notes, a timer and a separate room equipped for individual work were used.

The diagnostic work was carried out in several stages: obtaining written consent from parents for the participation of their children; conducting instruction for educators; preparing a room for individual classes, creating a calm and playful atmosphere.

Each child was playfully shown cards with images of faces expressing basic emotions (joy, sadness, anger, fear, surprise). The child was required to name an emotion, describe a situation in which a person could experience it, and tell about his own reaction in such cases. 15–20 minutes were allocated for each child. All the answers were carefully recorded.

For two weeks after individual lessons, children were systematically monitored for how they communicate in their natural environment — during joint games, morning classes and free activities. The observations were carried out by two researchers according to a pre-approved schedule, recording behavioral manifestations according to the protocol.

The results of the study and their interpretation.

The study involved 52 children of senior preschool age (5–6 years old) of kindergarden No. 153 in Almaty. All children were examined using the «Emotional Faces» technique (N. Y. Semago), as well as additional monitoring of their communicative behavior in the group.

Diagnostic analysis using the «Emotional faces» technique (N. Ya. Semago) he identified the following levels of emotional intelligence development:

- High level of emotional intelligence — 18 children (34.6%).
- Average level of emotional intelligence — 24 children (46.2%).
- Low level of emotional intelligence — 10 children (19.2%).

Table 1. Table of distribution of children by levels of emotional intelligence

The level of emotional intelligence	Number of children	% of the sample	Average communication index
High	18	34,6%	~33
Medium	24	46,2%	~28
Low	10	19,2%	~20

The average recognition accuracy of basic emotions was 72% (SD = 14%). The children were most successful in identifying the emotion of joy, with the greatest difficulties in distinguishing between fear and surprise.

When verbalizing and explaining the causes of emotions, the children indicated the following parameters:

- About 60% of the children provided adequate and detailed explanations.
- Partially adequate explanations — 30%.
- Lack of explanations or inadequate answers — 10%.

Only a third of the children ($\approx 33\%$) were able to offer verbal regulation strategies («ask for help», «tell the caregiver», «calm down»). The rest more often resorted to behavioral reactions (crying, withdrawal from the situation, silence).

The results of the diagnosis of emotional intelligence and the connection with communicative competence (n=52)

Figure 1. The relationship between emotional intelligence and communication skills of preschool children

The average index of communicative competence (according to the observation and assessment of teachers) was 28 points out of 40 (SD = 6).

- Children with high levels of emotional intelligence were more likely to initiate contact, listen, and offer compromise solutions.
- Children with an average level demonstrated situational communication skills, but sometimes found it difficult to verbally resolve conflicts.
- Children with low levels of emotional intelligence were more likely to show aggressive or avoidant reactions.

Correlation analysis showed a positive and statistically significant relationship between the level of emotional intelligence and communicative competence ($r = 0.62$, $p < 0.001$). This confirms that the development of emotional intelligence is directly related to the quality of communication among preschoolers.

Discussion of the results.

The results of the study showed that the majority of older preschool children have an average level of emotional intelligence. At the same time, a significant part demonstrates a high level, and about one in five children has a low one. The

ability to recognize emotions and express them in words is generally formed, which indicates a basic understanding of one's feelings. However, children have difficulty applying self-control strategies and verbal conflict resolution. The found strong correlation (correlation coefficient of about 0.62) between emotional intelligence and the quality of communication confirms that emotional competence plays a key role in the communication of preschoolers.

The close relationship between emotional intelligence and communication skills indicates that the ability to identify and name emotions promotes more effective verbal interaction, reduces impulsivity, and increases the likelihood of constructive dispute resolution. Low self-regulation rates in some children explain their tendency to avoid conflict or aggressive behavior in such situations. This highlights the need for purposeful work on teaching children techniques for calming down and expressing their feelings. Differences in the recognition of individual emotions (for example, difficulties in distinguishing fear and surprise) reflect the peculiarities of the development of perception of facial expressions and affects in this age period.

The results obtained are consistent with theoretical and empirical studies that consider emotional intelligence as an important factor of social competence and successful adaptation to the school environment. The revealed importance of verbalization of emotions in conflict resolution confirms the conclusions about the importance of developing emotional vocabulary and communication strategies in preschool age. At the same time, the revealed limitations in self-regulation in part of the sample coincide with the risks described in the literature for further social adaptation with insufficient development of emotional skills.

Conclusion.

The results of the study substantiate the need for regular assessment of emotional intelligence in preschool institutions and the introduction of educational programs into daily practice. Priority areas of work include: exercises for recognizing and naming emotions, role-playing games for practicing verbal conflict resolution strategies, as well as training simple self-regulation techniques. Individual lessons are advisable for children with low levels of emotional intelligence, while group play trainings are effective for improving the overall level of emotional literacy in a group.

Longitudinal studies are needed to track the dynamics of the development of emotional intelligence and its impact on the further social and academic success of children. It is also advisable to expand the sample to include children from various educational institutions and cultural backgrounds in order to increase the representativeness of the data obtained. It is important to use more comprehensive methods for assessing emotional intelligence, which would take into account not only the recognition of basic emotions, but also an understanding of more complex

emotional states, as well as the ability to empathize and manage one's own emotions in various situations. The study of the impact of specific pedagogical interventions on the development of emotional intelligence and communication skills also seems to be a promising area.

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INCLUSIVE TEACHER COMPETENCIES AS A NECESSARY CONDITION FOR TEACHING STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL EDUCATIONAL NEEDS IN NATURAL SCIENCE SUBJECTS

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Abstract. *This article focuses on the competencies required by subject educators to teach students with special educational needs in natural science subjects. Inclusive competence has been identified as the primary professional competency. An analysis of the professional standard for educators was conducted from the perspective of identifying the necessary components of this competence — namely, inclusive professional competencies. Types of teacher activities aimed at the meaningful assimilation of the physics curriculum by students with disabilities, taking into account their special educational needs, are presented. It is concluded that a teacher's inclusive competencies must be specified based on the special educational needs of a particular nosological group, the subject taught, and the individual characteristics of the students. The research findings can be used in the training and professional development of staff to effectively implement inclusive education processes.*

Keywords: *students with disabilities, special educational needs, teacher inclusive competencies, inclusive education, adapted educational program, natural science subjects.*

Problem statement of the research. The modern education system, aimed at creating conditions for the education of all children regardless of their inclinations, abilities, developmental characteristics, or physical and mental health status, sets particular requirements for teachers' professional competencies. Traditionally, the following types are distinguished: special competence, social competence, personal competence, and individual competence [10, p. 25]. The development of

all components of professional competence is essential for every teacher, but it gains particular significance when working with students who have special educational needs, especially those with disabilities [1].

The relevance of this study is driven by the increasing proportion of children with disabilities within the overall school population. Currently, according to statistical data, approximately 984.7 thousand school-aged children hold the status of “Child with Disabilities,” and the majority of them (59.8%) receive education in an inclusive setting [8]. Such students are, in principle, capable of mastering the standard (basic) level of education, provided that a differentiated approach to their learning is implemented, which takes into account the peculiarities of their cognitive, emotional, and speech development. These characteristics define the special educational needs of such students [3; 9] and impose specific requirements on the professional qualities of the teacher and their personal competence. The particular significance of this component of professional competence is confirmed by the results of a study on teachers’ psychological well-being, which demonstrated that the risk of professional burnout and personal distress among educators teaching students with disabilities in inclusive environments is significantly higher than among educators working with such children in special remedial schools, as well as educators teaching children with typically developing conditions [12]. Thus, the development of the professional competence of the contemporary educator is, on the one hand, a guarantee of their psychological stability and, on the other hand, ensures the quality of teaching in the context of inclusive education.

The issue of teaching children with disabilities is especially acute for educators working in inclusive settings who teach natural science disciplines. They must deliver instruction at a contemporary level of scientific knowledge, taking into account the heterogeneity of the student body and the resulting diversity of special educational needs of learners, both typical of various nosological groups as a whole and exhibiting individual specificity [4].

Several studies addressing the challenges of university-level training of teaching staff for inclusive educational institutions [6; 7] conclude that teachers working in inclusive settings require not only traditional professional competencies but also specific competencies — referred to as inclusive competencies — which together form the educator’s inclusive competence; generalized competencies of this type are identified. In particular, the following integral inclusive competencies of the educator are highlighted: readiness to organize the inclusive educational process as a whole; readiness to organize an individually oriented educational trajectory for a student with health limitations; readiness to provide individual or collective support to students with health limitations; readiness to organize psychological and pedagogical support for students with health limitations. Substantive and instrumental knowledge necessary for working with students with disabilities» [6, p. 305].

At the same time, based on the conducted research, it is concluded that currently there is no comprehensive evaluative paradigm regarding educator competencies within the pedagogical community, which underscores the need for further development of the model of inclusive competence of the educator, its empirical verification, and subsequent implementation into professional educational programs in accordance with the current requirements of inclusive practice» [7, p. 107].

At the same time, the issue of inclusive competence pertains not only to the training of new educators but also to the professional development and enhancement of competencies of currently practicing teachers. Moreover, generalized inclusive competencies do not adequately reflect the special educational needs of students from different nosological categories, which, in turn, depend on the specific characteristics of particular academic disciplines. Therefore, it is necessary not only to refine the model of inclusive competence for educators working with schoolchildren with disabilities but also to specify its component competencies in accordance with their educational needs and the subjects studied.

The scientific novelty of this study consists in conducting a comprehensive analysis for the first time of the inclusive professional competencies required by a physics teacher — a core subject of the natural science cycle — for the effective instruction of students with health limitations in inclusive educational settings.

Research methods: analysis of scientific and methodological literature concerning the problem under study; analysis of regulatory and legal documents (the Federal Adapted Educational Program for Basic General Education for students with health limitations, the Professional Standard for educators, etc.); A synthesis of personal methodological experience in designing federal curricular programs for academic subjects for students with health limitations at the level of basic general education, alongside the practical experience of physics teachers educating schoolchildren with learning disabilities in inclusive environments.

Results. Let us examine the specific inclusive competencies of a teacher by the example of physics instruction, aligning the content of the professional educator standard sections with the content of the federal adapted educational program for students with health limitations and the special educational needs of students with learning disabilities.

The psychological and pedagogical characteristics and special educational needs of students with learning disabilities were systematically described by us previously [3]. In the context of this study, it is important to emphasize the following features of the psychosocial development of schoolchildren with learning disabilities, which contribute to difficulties in assimilating educational material in natural science subjects: low awareness in perceiving the material, lack of sustained cognitive interest, and an absence of motivation for independent information seeking. Delayed development of conceptual thinking; difficulties in defining concepts, identifying

essential features of concepts, and manipulating concepts; Deficiencies in spatial-temporal representations; Insufficient goal-directedness of activity; difficulties in retaining the algorithm of sequential learning actions; tendency to shift from problem-solving to formal actions; weakness in self-monitoring of one's own actions and outcomes; Difficulties in working with educational texts, including highlighting the main points and reproducing the core content; unstable academic motivation and low productivity, as well as general socio-emotional immaturity. Students within this nosological category are also characterized by an insufficient understanding of the surrounding world, a fragmented worldview, and difficulties in applying previously acquired knowledge in everyday life.

The professional standard for an educator encompasses competencies related to the performance of professional activities in accordance with the requirements of the Federal State Educational Standard for Basic General Education. The federal physics curriculum for students with learning disabilities differs from the program for students with neurotypical development in that the amount of theoretical material covered is reduced. Accordingly, adjustments have been made to the content of this academic subject and to the expected learning outcomes. In this regard, the teacher must take a differentiated approach to the selection of educational material, differentiating the theoretical concepts introduced in each section according to the required level of mastery: knowledge, comprehension, or familiarity. For the meaningful acquisition of physics content by students with learning disabilities, the teacher must also master specialized methods, techniques, and instructional resources that consider the specific features of mastering the system of knowledge, skills, and abilities [4]. Specifically, this refers to the 'step-by-step' presentation of educational material using appropriate algorithms, supporting diagrams, and other visualization tools. It is also crucial to thoroughly develop the educational material and reinforce the acquired knowledge and skills by relating them to specific real-life situations. Considering that the category of students with special educational needs is heterogeneous in terms of cognitive development levels, when preparing lessons in an inclusive classroom, the teacher must plan the individualization of learning activities and the necessary degree of specialized support. Individualization involves reducing the number of tasks, extending the time allotted for their completion, simplifying the phrasing of instructions, and dividing them into separate parts according to the task execution algorithm. Individual visual aids and reference materials containing physical formulas and notations may also be used.

The professional standard for educators identifies, as a distinct labor function, the organization, supervision, and evaluation of academic achievements, including ongoing and final results of mastering the core educational program. Special requirements for assessment procedures have been established for students with

health limitations [2; 11]. The ability to assess educational subject-specific, meta-subject, and personal outcomes achieved within the taught subject, considering the special educational needs and capabilities of students with learning disabilities, constitutes another essential competency of the teacher. Our online survey revealed insufficient competence among physics teachers working in inclusive education settings in this area. This deficiency stems from a lack of knowledge about the specific features of assessing the educational achievements of students with special educational needs, adapting control and measurement materials and assessment tools and procedures, as well as the special conditions required for conducting interim and final certification. It should be noted that, from a scientific perspective, the problem of assessing the educational outcomes of students with learning disabilities at the basic general education level remains insufficiently developed and requires further research and practical validation.

In accordance with the professional standard, the teacher must collaborate with other specialists within the framework of the psychological-pedagogical council of the educational institution, possess specialized methodologies that enable corrective and developmental work, and conduct psychological-pedagogical support of educational programs jointly with a psychologist and other specialists.

The professional standard establishes requirements for the personal qualities of the educator, inseparable from their professional competencies, such as psychological readiness to teach children regardless of the peculiarities of their development or limitations in physical and mental health. In this regard, the professional development of empathy and the cultivation of skills in educators working in inclusive settings becomes paramount. skills in emotional and volitional self-regulation. An important component of inclusive competence is the emotional and meaningful support of a student experiencing learning difficulties. It is manifested in the adult's empathy towards the child during the process of mediatory interaction. Working in inclusive settings requires the teacher to have special regulation of empathic understanding and emotional-volitional self-regulation. The study of conditions and patterns of development of these abilities in educators requires further research.

Special attention should be given to the development of all components of inclusive competence in the training of educators, including the core curriculum discipline 'Psychological and Pedagogical Features of Working with Children with Special Educational Needs' [5].

Conclusion. For the effective education of schoolchildren with learning disabilities in inclusive settings, teachers must possess specific inclusive professional competencies. The set of these competencies, defined as inclusive competence, applies to the process of teaching students with health limitations from all nosological categories. At the same time, these competencies must be specified

according to the special educational needs of a particular nosological group, the subject taught, and the individual characteristics of the students.

The results of this study hold both theoretical and practical significance. The theoretical significance lies in the research results serving as a foundation for the expansion and substantive concretization of the model of inclusive professional competence of subject teachers working with students with disabilities across various nosological categories. The practical value of the obtained results is determined by their contribution to the methodological support of the education system for students with special educational needs, as well as to the training and professional development of personnel for the effective implementation of inclusive education processes.

Addressing the issue of enhancing the inclusive professional competence of educators primarily requires the improvement of professional educational programs. Future research prospects lie in the conceptual development of core and supplementary training programs for inclusive education educators, aimed at the formation and expansion of the competencies discussed in this article.

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ANTHROPOCENTRISM OF ETHNOPEDAGOGICAL APHORISMS

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Abstract. *The system of perception, systematization and interpretation of the world surrounding a person is based on anthropocentrism — a worldview that defines a person as a measure of objects in the surrounding world. Therefore, by studying the ethnopedagogical means of personality formation, by analyzing the aphoristic maxims that accompanied his growing up and socialization, we obtain information about the nature of ethnic education, identifying in what the child was limited, how he was encouraged, consoled, punished, edified, inspired. And knowledge of these patterns helps to use more widely the anthropologism of ethnopedagogical aphorisms as a substantive basis for the ethnocultural component of modern educational programs: to consider a person in all his universal characteristics, in all spheres of an individual's activity from everyday life to diplomacy and education. It is also important to keep in mind that the presence of anthropocentrism in folk aphorisms can be expressed not only explicitly, but also implicitly: no matter what the aphoristic unit talks about (flora, fauna, natural phenomena, etc.), ultimately, through comparison, metaphor, synecdoche and other poetic and artistic means, it talks about man.*

Keywords: *ethnopedagogy, anthropocentrism, ethnocultural education, aphoristic genres of folklore.*

Each individual is a bearer of the language, traditions, spiritual values, as well as the worldview attitudes and priorities of their ethnocultural group, which they acquire through the process of maturation and socialization. These very elements shape their understanding of the world, in which the human is both subject and object. Prominent scholars E. Benveniste, W. von Humboldt, A. A. Potebnya, F. I. Buslaev, A. N. Afanasyev et al., each examining the problems of language and folklore through their respective materials, discussed the individual as a personality that reflects the worldview of an entire people, encapsulated within the structure of language, the particularities of folklore, and traditional culture. All this folk knowledge, orally transmitted across generations, was anthropocentric (from Ancient

Greek ἄνθρωπος — human and Latincentrum — center), designed to guide the individual through life: to provide exemplary ideals, protect from marginalization, and offer vivid, memorable prescriptions of preferred social and familial interaction models (1; 4; 5, pp. 151–155; 8, pp. 203–209; 2, pp. 37–52).

The anthropocentric orientation of folk aphoristics, predominantly expressed in proverbial and saying forms, is well-known. Such anthropocentric proverbs focus the listener's attention on the human being — as an imaginative, direct, collective, or generalized representation of their activity and character, life experience, and national mentality. Typically, these utterances contain two interrelated planes: the plane of content, encompassing conclusions and inferences of a universal, all-human character; and the plane of expression, which conveys these meanings through nationally and culturally specific images, concepts, narratives, and artistic devices characteristic of the particular ethnos. The universal human aspect of proverbs demonstrates that all humanity, regardless of ethnic, linguistic, historical, or cultural differences, possesses elements inherent to it as a species concept (spirit, soul, body, kin, labor, family, homeland, etc. (1, pp. 18–21; 5, pp. 151–155; 3, pp. 14–48.).

Anthropocentrism permeates the centuries-old experiential knowledge of numerous generations of North Caucasian highlanders concerning the patterns of child development and education. In folk tales, riddles, songs, fables, epic narratives, traditions, and legends containing plots and ideas of an educational nature, the regularities, factors, and recommendations conducive to the upbringing and formation of a harmoniously developed personality are captured in an artistic form. The quintessence of ethnopedagogical knowledge has been preserved within the folklore tradition through folk aphorisms — didactic injunctions (proverbs, sayings, paremiological units, maxims, winged words, and non-figurative expressions). The enumerated minor aphoristic genres of mountain folklore, which take the form of complete sentences, even when addressing natural phenomena, the beauty of plants, animal and bird behaviors, the movement of planets, and so forth, are ultimately anthropocentric, since the figurative and allegorical dimension of these expressions conveys information about and for humans, typifying the most diverse manifestations of human life.

In form, the aphoristic expressions of the North Caucasian peoples adhere to the principles of brevity, conciseness, stability, and expressiveness. Alongside their literal meaning, they embody figurative motivations of a general nature and, despite their specificity among different ethnic groups, exhibit significant similarities in meaning and sense; at times, they coincide with proverbs of other peoples, with numerous examples available. The analysis of the material under consideration reveals a functional characteristic: anthropocentrism, which entails a focus on moral instruction, admonition, teaching, caution, and aid to individuals in various life and everyday circumstances. This orientation characterizes the

aphorism not only as a poetic, aesthetic, and philosophical category but also as a pedagogical category.

Given the absence of universally accepted terminological definitions for this concept within ethnopedagogical research, it is justifiable to propose the following definition: an aphorism is a historically established folk-poetic instrument of traditional education, distinguished by its extreme conciseness, informational density, figurative expressiveness, anthropocentrism, the coexistence of literal and figurative meanings, and a functional didactic intent (6; 7).

Proverbial admonitions encapsulate life information that has undergone synthesis and analysis of facts, generalization, and artistic transformation. This sublimation is manifested either as a direct exposition of a continuum of views, conceptions, and attitudes that guide a particular ethnos (proverbs and sayings with a literal motivation of their general meaning) or through an artistic depiction of the subject (proverbs with a figurative motivation of their general meaning).

The analysis of the patterns underlying the contemporary functioning of didactic utterances among diverse peoples reveals that such proverbial sayings are perceived by the bearers of ethnoculture not as a distant past but as the living voice of the people. People are confident in their current relevance, as well as in their necessity for the future. Primarily, their demand is explained by the fact that a proverb is created by the entire community and embodies the collective, time-tested opinion of the people; they not only constitute an effective means of traditional education but also support the maintenance of regulatory norms within society, as they are employed to transmit experience and compel the listener to internalize this experience through the apprehension of becoming a social outcast should they fail to conform to the collective ethos (9).

As a rule, the specified means of traditional education, in their living practice, function as an educational form termed explanation. Proverbial sayings, appropriate to the occasion and interwoven into speech, substantiate certain arguments presented by the speaker. Since proverbs encompass a broad spectrum of phenomena and objects, every individual in any typical situation can employ an authoritative aphoristic explanation for educational purposes.

In addition to explanatory functions, proverbial aphorisms can take forms of verbal influence on the individual such as persuasion, instruction, admonition, moralizing, advice, precept, and vow (1, pp. 71–79). Forms of moral influence — either elevating the personality or suppressing it — include proverbs and proverbial omens that reflect customs, prohibitions, beliefs, contempt (as a manifestation of social opinion), reproach, as well as curses and blessings. The objectives of creating an emotionally supportive environment were fulfilled by such forms of traditional education as well-wishes, greetings, expressions of gratitude, oaths, and indirect threats.

The educational effectiveness of the aphoristic forms of folk education was ensured not only by the lexical content embedded within them but also by the specific tone of their enunciation, the speaker's expressive facial expressions, characteristic gestures accompanying the aphoristic utterance, and their relevance to the given context. At one time, the educational significance of aphoristic admonitions was intensified not only by reverence for the special, not fully understood power of the word, but also by the 'magical' aspect inherent in the sounded and purposeful word. Even in ancient civilizations, people recognized the special influence of words on the human psyche and health, as well as on the vitality of plants, animals, and objects in the surrounding environment.

Analysis of an extensive corpus of aphoristic forms confirms their anthropocentrism and their focus on transmitting life experience, preparing younger generations to accept and carefully cultivate the world, preventing mistakes, and averting individual and social misfortunes. Such content underpins their sententiousness, didactic nature, pedagogical orientation, and enduring relevance. As an expression of the pedagogical wisdom of the people and a folk-pedagogical instrument of education, aphorisms teach not only how to live and nurture, and influence the consciousness of individuals, but also reveal that the world inhabited by the ancestors of the contemporary Caucasian ethnoeses was neither primitive nor simple, and that a dignified life therein required from each member of society specific internal efforts, including the exercise of willpower, intellect, and spirit.

The anthropocentric paradigm of aphoristics is encyclopedically comprehensive: there are no topics or issues of human life to which it does not respond. Therefore, it resonates within the soul of every individual at various stages of their life, across diverse everyday circumstances. Accordingly, statistics indicate that aphoristic literary works are among the most sought after by people.

It is particularly important to note that the anthropocentrism of aphoristics represents a traditional field of investigation for a range of related disciplines: these folkloric units are examined from the perspectives of folklore studies, ethnopedagogy, ethnology, language theory, and comparative linguistics, as well as from the standpoints of language didactics and methodologies for teaching both native and non-native languages, including their use within educational curricula across institutions of various tiers and in extracurricular pedagogical engagements interaction (2, pp. 37–52; 5, pp. 151–155; 4, pp. 14–48; 8, pp. 203–209;). Recently, due to the strengthening of principles of multicultural and multilingual education, increased attention has been directed towards anthropocentric proverbs, proverbial sayings, and aphorisms of non-native languages, which are studied in pedagogical methodology through comparative and contrastive analysis with analogous reflections in the students' native language. Aphoristic texts constitute one of the most valuable resources for teaching ethnocultural and ethnolinguistic vocabulary

and for fostering the development of translation proficiency. This work is reflected in published anthologies, dictionaries, teacher's manuals, and methodological guidelines, which present selected educational linguistic and folkloric material accompanied by a system of exercises constructed in accordance with the principles of the theory of ethno-culturally determined translation.

Thus, mastering the aphoristic material contributes not only to acquiring relevant philological and ethno-cultural knowledge, fostering more conscious and accurate interlingual and intercultural communication, and enhancing learners' bilingual communicative competence, but also to deeply influencing the formation of personal aspirations, ideals, and behavioral patterns through folk wisdom. What is achieved, according to the majority of practicing educators, is that the inculcation of value-based ethnocultural attitudes occurs implicitly and does not provoke rejection among learners, which frequently arises in adolescents when these attitudes and prescriptions are imposed directly and directive.

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DYNAMICS OF CHANGES IN THE INDICATORS OF THE PSYCHOEMOTIONAL STATE OF YOUNG BANDY PLAYERS OF THE TEAM “EROFEY 2007”

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Abstract. *The study examined the dynamics of changes in the psycho-emotional state indicators of young bandy players of the Erofeiy 2007 team during their performance at the final stage of the All-Russian Bandy Competition in Ulyanovsk from March 23 to 30, 2024. During the performance of young bandy players at the competition, it was found that such indicators as the level of balance, aggression, charisma, self-regulation corresponded to an average high level for most athletes throughout the entire survey period, and the level of danger, stress, inhibition and neuroticism also corresponded to an average level for most athletes during their performance at the competition. Only the level of anxiety fluctuated throughout the study for most young bandy players, either increasing to a high level or decreasing to an average level.*

Keywords: *young bandy players, All-Russian competitions, final stage, vibrated hardware and software system, psycho-emotional state, central nervous system*

Introduction

The dynamics of psycho-emotional state changes were studied among young bandy players from the Erofeiy 2007 team during their performance at the final stage of the All-Russian Bandy Competition in Ulyanovsk from March 23 to 30, 2024. Ten psycho-emotional state measurements were taken, beginning on March 22, 2024, before the start of the competition, each day of the competition, and on

March 31, 2024, the day after the end of the competition. All psycho-emotional state measurements were conducted in the morning hours using the Vibramed hardware and software system.

The VibraMed system allows for the measurement and study of human psychoemotional and psychophysiological parameters (stress, energy, charisma, aggression, inhibition, anxiety, balance, etc.) as objectively as physical quantities unrelated to a person or biometrics are measured. This is because it directly measures the physical parameters of a person's head movement, which are functionally linked to their psychophysiological state [5].

Vibraimaging technology enables contactless recording of human head vibration parameters and the identification of emotions based on accumulated statistics from comparative tests with EEG, GSR, psychological testing, and theoretical assumptions [2,3].

1. Results

Having analyzed the indicators of the psycho-emotional state of young bandy players during their performance at competitions, we found that indicators such as the level of balance, aggression, charisma, and self-regulation corresponded to an average high level for the majority of athletes throughout the entire period of the survey, while the level of danger, stress, inhibition, and neuroticism also corresponded to an average level for the majority of athletes during their performance at the competition, and only the level of anxiety fluctuated throughout the study for the majority of young bandy players, either increasing to a high level or decreasing to an average level (Table).

Comparing the indicators of the psycho-emotional state recorded before the start of the competition (March 22, 2024) with the indicators after the completion of the competition (March 31, 2024), it can be noted that a significant decrease occurred in such indicators as the level of aggression from 57% to 50% (by 12,3%), the level of energy from 28% to 23% (by 17,9%), the level of danger from 45% to 42% (by 6,7%), and a significant increase occurred in such indicators as the level of balance from 67% to 72% (by 7,5%), the level of anxiety from 35,5% to 39% (by 9,9%) in young bandy players ($p < 0,05$).

The dynamics of changes in the level of balance in young bandy players during the study showed that for most young men the indicator fluctuated either towards a slight deterioration or a slight improvement, but no reliable differences were recorded, except for a comparison of the initial indicator before the competition (67%) with the final indicator after the competition (72%), an improvement of 7,5%, which indicates stability in the balance of nervous processes in players and the ability to quickly and efficiently carry out game activities.

Table
Dynamics of changes in the psycho-emotional state indicators of young bandy players of the Erofey 2007 team at the final stage of the competition

Indicators of psycho-emotional state (%)	22.03.24 X±m	23.03.24 X±m	24.03.24 X±m	25.03.24 X±m	26.03.24 X±m	27.03.24 X±m	28.03.24 X±m	29.03.24 X±m	30.03.24 X±m	31.03.24 X±m
Equilibrium	67±2,7	65,5±1,7	63±1,3	67±2,1	69±1,8	70±1,9	68±1,5	69±1,4	70±1,8	72±1,6
Anxiety	35,5±0,5	35±1,1	36±0,7	39±0,5	37±1,5	38±1,3	41±1,3	44±0,8	42±1,3	39±0,9
Aggression	57±1,9	47±1,8	54±1,6	55±1,6	48±1,6	47±1,2	49±1,3	51±1,8	48±1,3	50±1,8
Danger	45±0,7	39±1,0	43±0,8	40±0,9	42±1,4	43±1,2	41±1,1	40±1,3	42±0,8	42±1,2
Stress	36±1	35±0,7	35±0,7	36±1	35±0,5	35±0,4	35±0,7	34±0,6	37±0,8	35±0,4
Charisma	61±1,6	52±2,7	63±1,9	62±1,5	58±1,8	54±1,3	56±1,4	57±1,2	60±1,4	59±1,6
Self-regulation	64±2,1	59±1,7	64±1,9	66±1,8	60±1,5	60±1,3	62±1,1	61±1,4	63±1,4	65±1,3
Energy	28±1,8	22±1,3	25±1,7	28±1,8	25±1,8	26±1,3	24±1,6	25±1,4	25±1,4	23±1,6
Braking	15±0,6	14±0,2	15,5±0,6	13±0,7	14±0,2	13±0,5	15±0,3	16±0,5	12 ±0,3	16±0,4
Neuroticism	17±0,6	17±1,1	16,5±0,6	15±0,2	17±1,2	16±0,7	17±1,6	15±0,8	16±1,2	16±0,9

The anxiety level indicator of the majority of young bandy players changed during the study, either increasing to a high level on March 28–29, 2024 (41–44%) compared to the baseline indicator (35,5%) by 15,5% and 23,9%, respectively, or decreasing to 39% — the average level after the completion of the competition compared to the indicator on March 29 and 30, 2024 by 11,4% and 7,2%, respectively ($p < 0,05$). Nevertheless, the final anxiety level indicator (39% — average level) worsened compared to the baseline indicator (35,5% — average level) by 9,9%.

The increase in anxiety levels among young hockey players is primarily due to coaching guidelines and increased responsibility on the days of the final games, which influence placement, and a consistent decline in this indicator after a positive performance in the final games. The level of aggression among bandy players fluctuated during the study, either decreasing or increasing compared to the baseline. Before the decisive game on March 31, 2024, the level among young men decreased by 15,8% to an average of 48% (the average level) compared to the baseline (57% — the high level).

After the competition, there was some change in this indicator, averaging 50%, but overall, this parameter significantly decreased from 57% before the competition to 50% after the competition by 12,3% ($p < 0,05$). Fluctuations in aggression levels among young athletes, sometimes rising and sometimes falling, reflect the players' focus on a specific opponent and their readiness to engage in a fierce, uncompromising fight. However, before decisive games, they demonstrate the ability to manage their emotions and control their actions.

The level of danger among most young bandy players fluctuated between decreasing and increasing during the study's intermediate indicators. However, compared to the baseline (45% average), it significantly improved on almost all recorded intermediate days of the study. By the final games on March 28–29, 2024, it had significantly decreased to 41–40% average (an increase of 8,9% and 11,2%, respectively).

The average stress level of young bandy players throughout the study did not undergo significant fluctuations towards deterioration compared to the initial indicator (36% — average level), but we note a slight increase to 37% on March 30, 2024, before the decisive game for a prize place compared to the indicator on March 29, 2024 (34% — average level) by 8,8%, which is apparently associated with the nervous and emotional tension in young men and their high share of responsibility for the result in the upcoming game.

Having followed the dynamics of changes in the level of charisma throughout the study of young bandy players, one can note periods of a sharp decrease in this indicator to 52%-high level (March 23, 2024), to 54% — high level (March 27, 2024) compared to the initial indicator on March 22, 2024 (61%-high indicator),

which may be associated before the start of the competition on March 23, 2024 with some pre-start fever and a decrease in self-confidence, and on March 27, 2024 with a difficult victory over an opponent on March 26, 2024. Moreover, on March 24, 2024, there was an increase in this indicator to 63% — a high level compared to the indicator on March 23, 2024 (52% — a high level) by 21,1%, which may be associated with the first labor victory and the acquisition of greater self-confidence.

As the team continued to perform, this indicator decreased to 54–56% — a high indicator (March 27–28, 2024) compared to the indicator on March 24, 2024 (63% — a high indicator) by 14,3% and 11,2%, respectively, which may be due to some accumulated fatigue of the team, but by the decisive game on March 30, 2024, this indicator increased to 60% — a high indicator by 11,1% compared to the indicator on March 27, 2024 (54% — a high indicator), which may be due to the focus on the opponent and an increasing share of confidence in their ability to take a prize place ($p < 0,05$). The level of self-regulation throughout the study in the majority of young bandy players did not show a sharp tendency to deteriorate, but there was a slight decrease in this indicator to 59% — a high level (March 23, 2024) to 60% (March 26–27, 2024) compared to the initial indicator of 64% — a high level (March 22, 2024), which may be associated with an increase in the level of anxiety on these days, but before the decisive game on March 30, 2024, it increased almost to the initial indicator and amounted to 63% — a high level, which indicates the ability to regulate their state and control the manifestation of emotions before the decisive game. The energy level throughout almost the entire study in the majority of young bandy players showed a significant downward trend. A sharp decrease in this indicator occurred on March 23, 2024, to 22% — the average level, compared to the initial indicator (28% — the average indicator) by 17,9%, which may be due to insufficient mobilization of their energy resources, and subsequently, by the final games (March 29–30, 2024), this indicator significantly decreased to 25% — the average level, by 10,7%, compared to the initial indicator (28% — the average level), which is apparently due to the gradual depletion of energy resources and a further decrease in this indicator to 23% after the final difficult game by 17,9%, compared to the initial indicator.

The level of inhibition in young bandy players showed no significant upward trend throughout the study. Before the crucial game, this indicator (average 12%) significantly decreased by 20% compared to the baseline (average 15%). After the competition, it significantly increased to 16%, a 33,3% increase compared to the March 30, 2024, level ($p < 0,05$).

The low level of inhibition throughout the study is associated with the high level of composure in young bandy players, while its increase after the decisive game is associated with the expenditure of physical strength and energy resources.

Finally, the level of neuroticism in the majority of young bandy players did not show any significant decline throughout the study. Instead, it showed a slight, significant decrease in the midterm studies, dropping to 15% (average) on March 25 and 29, 2024, compared to the baseline (17% (average) recorded on March 22, 2024) by 11,8% ($p < 0,05$).

The low level of neuroticism throughout the study indicates the ability of young bandy players to control their emotional stability and anxiety levels.

2. Conclusions

Thus, an analysis of the dynamics of changes in psychoemotional state indicators in young players from the Erofey experimental group, born in 2007, during competition performance revealed that out of ten indicators, four corresponded to a high level of psychoemotional state, while indicators such as anxiety, danger, stress, energy, inhibition, and neuroticism corresponded to an average level. Moreover, the anxiety indicator in the young men increased to a high level, but decreased to an average level by the end of the study.

All of the above indicates fairly good indicators of the psychoemotional state of the athletes' central nervous system, along with indicators of psychomotor performance and the athletes' readiness to win the highest awards in competition. By the final, crucial match for the prize, most of the young bandy players' psychoemotional state indicators were fairly good and not significantly different from their baseline values, allowing the team to perform well at the final stage of the All-Russian Bandy Competition in Ulyanovsk and win silver medals [1].

However, indicators such as anxiety levels, which were somewhat high for most athletes, and energy levels, which decreased for most players before the crucial match compared to their baseline values, negatively impacted the team's ability to achieve first place.

All of this points to the need for systematic assessment of the dynamics of psycho-emotional state changes and appropriate adjustments to the training process for young bandy players.

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PROBLEMS OF DIGITALIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. USING THE EXAMPLE OF P.F. LESGAFT NATIONAL UNIVERSITY, ST. PETERSBURG

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Abstract. *The object of this study comprises the processes and outcomes of digitalization and digital transformation of the educational process. The relevance of this study lies in the fact that the tasks associated with the digitalization and digital transformation of the educational process, when implemented under specific conditions, face a considerable number of challenges that require specialized analysis and investigation. The objective of this study is to analyze the primary challenges of digitalization and digital transformation within the educational process.*

Keywords: *digitalization, digital transformation, LMS platforms, educational process, distance learning technologies.*

Introduction

The educational process, like all sectors of the Russian economy, is currently engaged in addressing the objectives outlined in the ‘Strategy for the Development of the Information Society in the Russian Federation for 2017–2030,’ approved by the order of the Government of the Russian Federation No. 1632-r dated July 28, 2017 [1]. Although this process was initiated in 2017, many issues related to the digitalization and digital transformation of the educational process remain unresolved and are systemic in nature [2, 5–6].

With considerable experience in the digitalization of the educational process dating back to 2009, when at P. F. Lesgaft National University, Saint Petersburg [3], the Department of Biomechanics began implementing student work on websites, followed by the transition to distance learning platforms (LMS Moodle)

[4, 36–37], we propose to identify the main areas that may present challenges during their implementation.

1. The use of a unified platform for hosting educational materials (content), assignments, tests, and a system for monitoring and record-keeping.
2. Requirements for the digitalization of content.
3. Content visualization.
4. Assessment system.
5. System for monitoring and recording the activities of both students and educators.
6. Ensuring security and user identification.

Currently, the distance learning portal of P. F. Lesgaft National University, Saint Petersburg, includes 3,292 distance courses and 10,787 users, including those enrolled in continuing professional education. We conducted a selective analysis of the most typical variants of distance courses for each of the six aforementioned aspects.

Research results

1. Regarding the first point: the use of a unified platform for hosting educational materials (content), control and test assignments, as well as monitoring and accounting systems. At present, several working modalities for the faculty staff are identified, as shown in

Table 1. Primary options and challenges in using the educational space.

№	Types of utilized space	Percentage of usage	Key challenges in usage
1	Use of Internet websites, both personal and corporate	5–8	Technical complexity of user interaction with the website. The need for regular updates. If it is a personal website, then the associated maintenance costs.
2	Use of social networks such as WhatsApp, Telegram, VK, and others.	50–60	Large, unstructured volumes of information exchange with no evaluation, control, or accounting systems. Predominantly personal interaction.
3	Use of video services such as Zoom, Jass, KonturTalk, and others.	15–20	Primarily used for teaching theoretical sections; it leaves no record of students' work and lacks evaluation, control, and accounting systems.
4	The use of LMS platforms such as Moodle, Eduardo, E-Levels, and others.	70–75	Weak digitalization, visualization, and organization of educational content, as well as insufficient qualifications of the teaching staff to work with assessment, control, and record-keeping systems. Cloud hosting of LMS may lead to information leakage regarding course content.

The primary challenges related to the requirements for content digitalization include: incomplete digitization of course materials, absence of digitized methodological materials, and lack of materials for practical and seminar sessions. The digitized material is not classified according to the topics and sections of the course. Hypertext documents are almost entirely absent.

3. Content visualization is at a very low level. More than half of the courses lack even presentations for the topics, let alone video materials or multimedia presentations. The use of links to pre-existing video content available on the internet is widespread; however, this raises concerns regarding copyright for such content. Moreover, often, besides the links, no additional information is provided within the course, which immediately calls into question the necessity and role of the course instructor.

4. Assessment system. Pose significant challenges for mastery and implementation in a digital format. [5, 108–109] The main types of assessment are presented in Table 2.

5.

Table 2. Main Types and Challenges of Assessment

No	Assessment types	Percentage of usage	Key challenges in assessment
	Testing	60–70	Insufficient number of questions in question banks; only multiple-choice questions are used; inability to configure the test properly
	Essays	15–20	No plagiarism check is conducted. Difficulties arise in the verification process when groups are large.
	Presentations	20–25	No plagiarism check is conducted. Difficulties arise in the verification process when groups are large. Students often focus excessively on formatting and effects, to the detriment of the substantive content.
	Assignments	80–85	Most instructors are unable to establish control over the personalization of task completion and their administration in online mode, resulting in a high level of falsification. Difficulties arise in the verification process when groups are large.
	Essay-type testing	15–20	Manual evaluation of essay-type responses is required, which prevents their use in tests combined with other question types assessed automatically. Difficulties arise in the verification process when groups are large.
	Online report and presentation	80	The necessity of conducting videoconferences to resolve these issues, along with frequent technical problems related to internet connectivity and network performance. Difficulties arise in the verification process when groups are large.

A system for monitoring and recording the activities of both students and educators. Monitoring, accounting, and reporting of student work in spreadsheet programs can be effectively performed by sufficiently advanced instructors. When using LMS, such tracking is conducted automatically, covering not only the activities of students but also those of teachers; however, many teachers lack the qualifications to view and present these materials in the formats they require.

7. Ensuring the security and identification of user activities. Issues related to securing course content can only be resolved by restricting access exclusively to authorized course users. A wide range of mechanisms can be applied for user identification; however, they require a relatively high level of teacher qualification and are frequently disregarded to enhance the intensity of the educational process.

Conclusions

Thus, despite the active development of digitalization and digital transformation processes in education, a considerable number of problems arise during their practical implementation, which are widespread and systemic in nature and require consistent and systematic resolution.

One of the primary approaches to addressing these problems in education, in our view, is the use of LMS platforms along with targeted and active professional development of faculty members in utilizing these platforms across all the directions mentioned above.

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PRACTICAL WORK ON STUDYING THE PROPERTIES OF THE ENZYME UREASE AS A FORM OF ORGANIZING STUDENT RESEARCH

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Abstract. *A methodological framework for an integrated lesson in the tenth grade is presented. The lesson is conducted in the context of studying the properties of proteins as biological catalysts (enzymes). At this stage, it is important to highlight the significance of chemical skills and competencies for the acquisition of chemical and biological knowledge.*

Keywords: *interdisciplinary connections, integrated lesson, practical lesson, urease, enzyme.*

The updated Federal State Educational Standard for general secondary education sets requirements for subject-specific learning outcomes, including ‘skills acquired by students through studying the academic subject that are specific to the subject area; activities related to obtaining new knowledge within the subject framework, its transformation, and application; development of scientific thinking; mastery of scientific terminology, key concepts, methods, and techniques.’ The fulfillment of these requirements becomes feasible through the active use of interdisciplinary connections within the process of subject teaching.

We utilize interdisciplinary connections in the teaching of chemistry as a crucial means of organizing students’ research activities. Our premise is that, from a methodological standpoint, interdisciplinary connections consist of the application of knowledge and procedures acquired in lessons from various subjects. The integration of interdisciplinary knowledge, such as chemistry and biology, constitutes a distinctive form of proof, argumentation, generalization, heuristic reasoning, interpretation, and modeling. Students learn to transfer knowledge acquired in other subjects to chemistry and biology lessons to gain a better

understanding of the studied content [2; 4]. The systematic updating of the content in natural science subjects, associated with interdisciplinary issues, requires developing a new teaching approach that entails a comprehensive analysis of the substantive components of the educational process and an optimal combination of educational technologies, methods, techniques, tools, and organizational forms. One such form may be interdisciplinary lessons. For example, a lesson on the topic: ‘Studying the properties of the enzyme urease.’

Nitrates are salts of nitric acid, for example, NaNO_3 , KNO_3 , and NH_4NO_3 . They are normal products of nitrogenous metabolism in any living organism — both plant and animal; therefore, ‘nitrate-free’ products do not exist in nature. Even within the human body, 100 mg or more of nitrates are produced and utilized daily in metabolic processes. Of the nitrates ingested daily by an adult human, 70% are derived from vegetables, 20% from water, and 6% from meat and canned products.

But why is there concern regarding the dangers of nitrates? When consumed in excessive amounts, nitrates are partially reduced to nitrites (more toxic compounds) in the digestive tract. When nitrites enter the body, they begin to interact with hemoglobin. As a result of this interaction, methemoglobin is formed, which is incapable of transporting oxygen. This results in impaired cellular respiration and the development of tissue hypoxia. Additionally, N-nitrosamines possessing carcinogenic activity (which promote the formation of cancerous tumors) may form from nitrites in the presence of amines [3].

Following ingestion of high doses of nitrates via drinking water or food, symptoms such as nausea, shortness of breath, cyanosis of the skin and mucous membranes, and diarrhea appear within 4–6 hours. This is accompanied by general weakness, dizziness, pain in the occipital region, and palpitations. First aid includes copious gastric lavage, administration of activated charcoal, saline laxatives, and fresh air [1].

What are the primary sources of dietary nitrates? They are almost exclusively plant-based products. In animal products (meat, milk), nitrate content is very low.

By which method can the safety of the consumed vegetable be rapidly determined? The simplest and most appropriate method is bioindication.

The use of biochemical reactions at the molecular level in bioindication is due to the high sensitivity of these reactions to external contaminants. A biochemical indicator sensitive to the presence of heavy metal ions, nitrates, and other toxins is urease.

Urease is a proteinaceous enzyme widely distributed in the plant kingdom. Urease is particularly active in the seeds of certain vegetables (legume seeds, watermelons, and zucchinis) and is also present in bacteria, yeasts, and some invertebrates. Enzymes accelerate biochemical reactions by a factor of a thousand, and in some cases, by a factor of a million. This implies that in the absence of the enzymatic apparatus, all intracellular processes would virtually cease, leading

to cell death. Therefore, the role of enzymes as biologically active substances is substantial [6].

In the modern world, the use of a rapid method for determining nitrates in plant raw materials is relevant; this method is based on the ability of the enzyme urease to catalyze the hydrolysis of urea (carbamide), resulting in the formation of ammonia and carbon dioxide:

Ammonia solution colors an indicator, such as phenolphthalein, crimson. If urease does not catalyze the conversion of urea, ammonia is not formed, and the solution's color remains unchanged. The demonstrativeness of this experiment is ensured by the rapid appearance of an intense coloration of the indicator. The activity of ureases can be inhibited by nitrates found in vegetables and fruits.

This property of ureases can be employed in an integrated, interdisciplinary lesson combining chemistry and biology for tenth-grade students, both at the advanced and basic levels. According to the Federal State Educational Standard for Secondary General Education (Order of the Ministry of Education of Russia No. 413 dated 17 May 2012), the topic 'Proteins: properties, types, and functions' is covered in the biology curriculum during the first academic quarter within the section 'Chemical Organization of the Cell,' and in the chemistry curriculum during the fourth quarter as the topic 'Proteins: their characteristics and properties' within the section 'Nitrogen-containing Organic Compounds' [5]. The objective of this practical lesson is to use urease to determine the nitrate content in vegetable crops. During the lesson, students complete the following tasks: to study the properties of the enzyme urease; to determine the nitrate content in vegetable crops using this enzyme; to apply the acquired knowledge to solve tasks in the state final certification (GIA) format.

The following equipment and materials are required for the lesson: a test tube rack, 3–5 test tubes, methyl orange indicator in a dropper, Pasteur pipettes, spatulas, a flask with a pre-prepared suspension of the enzymatic preparation (urease + urea), and samples of crushed cucumber, crushed green onion, and other vegetables. The suspension is prepared from one gram of crushed, peeled watermelon seeds (which contain urease), 10 grams of commercial urea, and 100 ml of water.

Procedure: add 4 ml of the enzymatic suspension (urease + urea) to several test tubes. The first test tube is left as a control. To the second and subsequent test tubes, add crushed cucumber, crushed green onions, and other crushed vegetables, and leave to stand for 5 minutes to activate the enzyme. After 5 minutes, add 2–3 drops of the indicator — methyl orange. Record the color of the indicator.

The intensity of the indicator's color development can be used to assess enzyme inhibition. If the color of the solution in the test tube changes (becoming yellow — alkaline environment), this indicates that urease retains its activity, as ammonia is released which colors the indicator. If the indicator color changes to red (acidic

environment), this indicates that nitrates contained in the plant material inhibit the urease enzyme.

Students record the obtained results in a table, formulate conclusions based on the completed work, study the theoretical material provided by the teacher, and answer questions.

Test tube number	Sample	Indicator coloration	Medium (pH)	Nitrate content	Enzyme activity
1	Control				
2	Green onion				
3	Cucumber				
4	...				

This practical work on studying the properties of the enzyme urease enables 10th-grade students in biology lessons to determine the nitrate content in vegetable crops using a simple bioindicator and to apply the acquired knowledge to solve problems in the format of the state final certification, both in chemistry and biology.

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PROFESSIONALLY ORIENTED EDUCATION OF FOREIGN CITIZENS AT THE STAGE OF PRE-UNIVERSITY TRAINING: A TEXTBOOK ON THE HISTORY OF RUSSIA (A SYSTEM OF ASSIGNMENTS AND OBJECTIVE CONTROL)

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Abstract. *The article presents the theoretical foundations and practical experience of professionally oriented education for foreign citizens at the pre-university training stage, illustrated by a history of Russia textbook designed to develop subject-specific competencies among foreign students in the academic sphere and to facilitate their successful socio-cultural adaptation.*

Keywords: *pre-university training, foreign students, textbook; history of Russia, subject-specific competence; sociocultural adaptation.*

The History of Russia textbook, developed by the faculty of the Department of Russian as a Foreign Language at Vladimir State University, is a compilation of educational texts and assignments designed to develop subject-specific competencies in the academic domain for foreign students enrolled in the pre-university training program.

The content of the textbook complies with the requirements for mastering additional general education programs designed to prepare foreign citizens and stateless persons for professional educational programs conducted in Russian, as approved by the Order of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation dated October 18, 2023, No. 998.

In accordance with the Requirements, the history of Russia is one of the principal (mandatory) general education subjects for students within the humanities profile and is included in the list of additional general education subjects for students of the natural sciences, engineering and technical, economic, and medical-biological profiles.

Through engagement with the Textbook materials, learners acquire a comprehensive set of knowledge, skills, and competencies that prepare them

for the final history exam of the pre-university training course, the entrance examination for admission to a Russian university, and the comprehension of lecture content during the first year of bachelor's and master's degree programs, as history holds a central position within the socio-humanitarian component of the academic curriculum at universities.

The textbook introduces students to fundamental key concepts that form the theoretical basis for understanding the issues and core content of the studied course. It promotes comprehension of the principal trends in the development of Russian statehood, political and socio-economic life, the ethnic distinctiveness of the peoples of the Russian Federation, and their spirituality.

The textbook offers an opportunity to familiarize oneself with the periodization of Russian history, the principal processes, phenomena, and events across different historical periods, notable Russian and Soviet personalities, as well as the locations of settlements and territories where significant historical events occurred.

The objectives of the textbook include the development of the following skills and competencies:

- to use the terminology of the academic discipline;
- to correlate historical events with the corresponding periods of Russian history;
- to characterize the primary events in the history of Russia;
- to identify cause-and-effect relationships among facts, events, and processes;
- to analyze historical phenomena.

The main structural unit of each topic is the educational text.

Considerable attention is given to both receptive and productive engagement with graphic objects (schemes, diagrams, tables), which constitute an effective means of organizing information and are intended to assist students in systematizing the knowledge acquired.

One of the primary objectives is the acquisition of terminological vocabulary. The terminological glossary included in the structure of the Textbook plays an important role in forming the basic categorical framework of the academic discipline.

Let us provide an example of assignments on the topic 'The Reunification of Crimea with Russia.' The Special Military Operation. This topic is significant and relevant for foreign students to understand the events of recent decades and the contemporary geopolitical situation.

The work begins with the presentation of terminological vocabulary: neo-Nazism, nationalism, rebellion, junta, to overthrow the president, legitimacy of power, coup d'état, regime, military oath, militia, diplomatic mission.

Before reading the text, students familiarize themselves with a commentary that provides information about realities and personalities encountered in the text. For example:

Yanukovych Viktor Fedorovich — president of Ukraine until 22 February 2014. On 21 November 2013, V. Yanukovych, by refusing to sign the Association Agreement with the European Union (EU), provoked mass protests — the ‘Euromaidan.’ On February 22, 2014, during an acute political crisis, V. Yanukovych was removed from power by the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine.

Post-text assignments are designed to assess comprehension of the text and mastery of terminological vocabulary and concepts.

Find the definitions of the terms. If necessary, consult the explanatory dictionary (Table 1).

Table 1.

I

Rebellion	A political faction that has come to power by unconstitutional means and exercises dictatorial rule through methods of terror.
Junta	An armed uprising resulting from a conspiracy against state authority.
Coup d'état	A violent seizure of power within a state, carried out in violation of prevailing constitutional and legal norms, usually involving the use of force.

II

Neo-Nazism	A movement that, following World War II, unites far-right extremist and ultra-nationalist organizations ideologically aligned with historic German Nazism.
Nationalism	An ideology and political direction whose fundamental principle is the thesis that the nation, as the highest form of social unity, holds primacy in the state-forming process.

The ability to correlate historical events with the corresponding periods of Russian history and to identify cause-and-effect relationships among facts, events, and processes enables the following types of assignments:

Complete the table titled ‘The Return of Crimea and the Special Military Operation.’ Use information from the text and additional sources (Table 2).

Table 2.

Date	Event	Significance
22 February 2014	Armed rebellion supported by Western countries	President V. Yanukovych was overthrown; a junta assumed power.
?	?	?

Match the items (Table 3).

Table 3.

February 2014	In Odesa, Nazis set fire to the Trade Union House, burning dozens of citizens protesting against the coup d'état who were trapped inside.
2 May 2014	military coup in Ukraine
16 March 2014	Referendum in Sevastopol. Reunification of Crimea with Russia.
May 12, 2014.	Proclamation of sovereignty of the DPR and LPR.
September 2014.	Minsk Agreements — 2.
February 2015.	Minsk Agreements — 1.
February 21, 2022.	Commencement of the SVO.
February 21, 2022.	Signing of treaties on friendship, cooperation, and mutual assistance, including military, between the Russian Federation, LPR, and DPR.
February 24, 2022.	Recognition by the Russian Federation of the independence of the LPR and DPR.

Effective types of assignments include responses to questions and monologic statements on the topic.

Intermediate and final assessments hold significant importance for an objective evaluation of knowledge.

Ongoing assessment at the end of each section and the final assessment are conducted in the form of test tasks that closely emulate the format of the entrance examination for Russian universities.

Let us provide an example of test tasks on the topic.

1. Before 2014, people in Ukraine for whom the Russian language and Russian culture were native constituted

- a) 20%
- b) 80%
- c) 50%

2. In February 2014, an event occurred in Ukraine.

- a) an armed uprising and the removal of the president from power
- b) a revolution
- c) a referendum

3. The referendum in Crimea and Sevastopol took place

- a) on March 16, 2014
- b) on March 16, 2016
- c) on December 15, 2014

4. 97% of residents of the Crimean Peninsula voted in the 2014 referendum

- a) to remain part of Ukraine
- b) for reunification with Belarus

c) for reunification with Russia

5. The LPR and DPR were proclaimed

a) in 2014

b) in 2020

c) in 2016

6. The Ukrainian side to the Minsk Agreements

a) complied with

b) did not comply with

c) observed

7. The President of Russia announced the commencement of the Special Military Operation

a) in 2022

b) in 2020

c) in 2018

8. The goal of the SVO is

a) intervention

b) expansion

c) protection of the LPR and DPR, and ensuring the security of Russia

The final assessment includes tasks on knowledge of abbreviations:

Provide the full forms of the abbreviations: NEP, RSFSR, CMEA, NATO, CSCE, UN, OVDR, SVO, LPR, DPR.

The textbook materials correspond to the requirements of the first level (B1) of Russian language proficiency, which form the basis of the pre-university training program.

The textbook is intended for foreign students enrolled in the pre-university training program, as well as bachelor's and master's degree students studying the history of Russia.

The materials of the Textbook have been piloted in practical history classes with groups of students enrolled in the pre-university training program.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the subject-specific competencies acquired by foreign students through studying the course on the history of Russia using the presented Textbook ensure their preparation for passing examinations in Russian history, for comprehending lecture materials in the first year of Bachelor's and Master's programs, and also facilitate understanding the main trends in the development of Russian statehood, as well as the political and socio-economic life of the Russian Federation, which constitutes an essential condition for socio-cultural adaptation.

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TO THE PROBLEM OF APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN PRESCHOOL AND PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The authors analyze the problem of applying innovative technologies in preschool and primary education, examining various types of innovations and their impact on the educational process and the professional competence of educators. The methods and approaches for implementing these technologies are discussed to improve instructional effectiveness, foster children's creative potential, and accommodate their individual characteristics.*

Keywords: *technology, innovative technologies, problem, preschool education, primary education.*

At present, in practical school settings, the number of children encountering learning difficulties and requiring focused attention from educators is increasing. All of this adversely affects the subsequent intellectual and personal development of the child. They are unable to keep pace with the instruction and fail to assimilate the curriculum material within the designated time. Furthermore, both teachers and parents at times regrettably note: 'does not want to learn,' 'could perform excellently but lacks motivation.' In these cases, it is evident that the student has not developed a need for knowledge and lacks interest in learning. The resolution of this issue is substantially facilitated by the implementation of innovative pedagogical technologies within the educational process.

The advancement of the education system requires the integration of new methods for teaching and child development. This is related to a shift in the teacher's priorities: not to impart knowledge, but to create conditions that foster the learner's independent creative exploration. At the present stage, it is increasingly apparent that the traditional school, focused on the transmission of knowledge, skills, and abilities, fails to keep pace with their rapid expansion. The professionalization of the educator and their transition to an innovative mode of work are impossible without creative self-determination, in which innovative pedagogical technologies play a leading role. Innovative pedagogical technologies are understood not only as an orientation towards perceiving, generating, and applying new knowledge, but primarily as openness.

Innovative pedagogical technologies represent one of the dominant trends in human development; they are specific and highly complex, requiring specialized knowledge, skills, and abilities. The implementation of innovations is impossible without an educator-researcher who possesses systemic thinking, a well-developed capacity for creativity, and a conscious, well-established readiness for innovations.

At present, when preparing for a session in a preschool educational institution, a lesson at school, or a class within the system of supplementary education, each educator must ensure that it is not only informative but also interactive, integrative, and relevant to the learners. This is associated with the adoption of the federal preschool education program and the new generation federal state educational standard (hereinafter FSES), which are designed to enable learners to independently acquire knowledge and apply it in any life situation.

The field of education is evolving rapidly, and to avoid lagging behind, it is essential to implement more advanced strategies.

Innovation (from Latin *in* — into, *novus* — new) denotes a novelty, an innovation. The primary indicator of innovation is a progressive initiative in the development of a higher education institution in comparison with established traditions and widespread practice. Existing definitions of innovations in domestic pedagogical science mainly reflect three of the most widely recognized approaches [4].

According to the first of these, innovations in education are changes based on novelties (N. V. Bordovskaya, A. A. Rean, I. P. Podlasiy, et al.). The criterion of innovativeness is novelty. According to researchers, innovation can be defined as any novelty, and its effectiveness may be evaluated on a scale ranging from 'leading to positive changes in education' to 'negatively impacting the educational process.'

The second approach (Yu. K. Babansky, V. A. Slastenin, L. S. Podymova, et al.) views innovations in education as the introduction of new elements into the objectives, content, forms, and methods of teaching and upbringing, as well as into the organization of collaborative activities between teachers and students. Within this framework, innovation in education can be defined exclusively as novelties that lead to positive changes within the educational system in which they are applied.

The essence of the third approach lies in the view that not every novelty aimed at optimizing the educational system qualifies as an innovation. Thus, T. I. Shamova, P. I. Tretyakov, and N. P. Kapustin deem it necessary to differentiate the concepts of 'innovation,' 'novelty,' and 'innovation.' According to their perspective, innovation involves the introduction of novelty into both content and organization; novelty pertains solely to the introduction of new elements in the organization of the process; while innovation encompasses the core of a new method, technique, or technology.

I. A. Antropova and S. V. Sidorov, synthesizing the most widely recognized scientific and pedagogical interpretations of the term "innovation," define innovation in education as the introduction of new elements into the goals, content, and organization of a managed process with the purpose of developing education and optimizing the educational system [1, p. 22].

Activity aimed at implementing innovative processes is termed innovative activity. Activities aimed at the creation, adoption, and utilization of pedagogical innovations are referred to as innovative-pedagogical.

The logic of the innovation process is governed by the concept of modernizing and optimizing the educational system and reflects the pathway of educational system renewal, encompassing idea formulation, project development, innovation evaluation, implementation and adjustment, dissemination, and routinization of new experiences.

Innovation in education is defined as the process of enhancing pedagogical technologies, encompassing the set of methods, techniques, and instructional tools. Currently, innovative pedagogical activity represents a fundamental component of the educational practice within any academic institution. Innovative activity not only establishes the foundation for creating the competitiveness of a given institution in the educational services market but also defines the directions for the professional development of the educator, his creative inquiry, and genuinely contributes to the personal growth of the pupils.

Innovative activity is inextricably linked to the scientific and methodological work of educators and the educational and research activities of pupils. In some cases, the use of an already known method with slight modification or adaptation is considered innovative. Innovation constitutes a particular domain of human activity that transcends traditional conditions, methods, and approaches, seeking not only novelty in content but fundamentally new outcomes.

An analysis of recent scholarly literature, alongside an examination of lesson plans for organized educational activities and primary school lessons (124 plans analyzed over two years), reveals that they are predominantly developed within a traditional paradigm. Nonetheless, educators report utilizing innovative technologies such as problem-based learning, project-based activities, experimentation, research activities, and the TRIZ methodology (TRIZ UMKA). However, can technologies that are over

50 years old still be regarded as innovative? All of them emerged in the twentieth century. On the one hand, they can be considered innovative, since educators employ them fragmentarily rather than systematically. Nevertheless, the question arises as to why technologies intended to effectively develop children's intellectual and creative abilities have not become the foundation of the currently approved preschool and primary general education curricula. Indeed, both the 'From Birth to School' program and the 'School of Russia' program incorporate elements of these technologies, but not across all educational domains, and not in a systematic, but rather episodic manner. Although these technologies do not require substantial technical or material resources. Only a high level of pedagogical competence is necessary. An analysis of the list of educational trends for 2030 reveals none of the aforementioned technologies, despite the fact that the efficacy of this group of technologies has been well established. So, which innovative technologies can and should be regarded as genuinely innovative today?

The Higher School of Economics and the Skolkovo School propose the following: multimodal pedagogy, gamification, socio-play technology models, mapping technology, teambuilding, budding, hypertext technologies, bricolage, challenge-based learning, screencasting, technologies of augmented (AR) and virtual (VR) reality, fidigital technologies, urban studies, and many others. All these technologies are based on the use of artificial intelligence (AI). The fundamental idea for developing an innovative education system was expressed by the head of Sberbank, G. Gref, who is overseeing the 'Education 2030' project, stated: 'The entire education model — from kindergartens to universities — must be transformed.' An 'AI revolution' awaits us by 2030.

The 'Education 2030' concept indicates that the entire new architecture of the education system is reduced to one principle: the learning process and the individuals themselves will be governed by artificial intelligence. Life is portrayed as a game. To this end, digitalization is extensively implemented, and education is essentially reduced to games. Concepts such as «Play is the norm,» «Play encompasses the entire childhood,» and «The playing person as a societal norm» are being introduced. It is asserted that life and work in virtual and augmented realities are also normative. Consequently, considerable attention is devoted to gamification and other game-based technologies.

If a school aims to develop a successful student, it must adapt to the challenges of the twenty-first century. This has given rise to one of the trends — the necessity for strong digital competencies from an early age. Knowledge of programming languages is becoming equivalent to knowledge of foreign languages. The advancement of digitalization results in both increased forecasts and amplified concerns. Some are already considering the replacement of teachers with artificial intelligence. Intelligent textbooks and chatbots, as supplements to traditional textbooks, are already being actively implemented. This implies that very soon

there will be a demand for educators who not only can utilize neural networks or VR but also structure the entire learning process around these technologies [3].

The Department of Preschool, Primary, and Supplementary Education Pedagogy at the Taganrog Institute named after A. P. Chekhov operates two research laboratories, one of whose objectives is to facilitate so-called dual education. This allows students to actively engage in practical activities from their first year, thereby mastering their future profession. An analysis of lesson plans developed by students and educators from partner educational institutions, along with a study of the operational experience of various experimental educational platforms, indicates that educational institutions partially implement innovative educational technologies such as the flipped classroom, cross-sense technology, hexagonal learning, urban studies, case technology, quests, coworking spaces, and others. These technologies require the application of artificial intelligence; however, the role of «live» communication and the teacher remains substantial. Simultaneously, educators utilizing these technologies frequently pose challenging questions and employ brainstorming, analogies, synectics, research methods, and others. Therefore, the integration of “traditional” and innovative technologies proves to be effective.

The foundations of knowledge, skills, and social interactions are established in preschool and primary education. Artificial intelligence can significantly enhance the educational process by providing educators with innovative tools for engaging with children. Artificial intelligence can adapt to the individual needs of each child by creating unique educational games and tasks that promote error identification and progress analysis.

However, the implementation of artificial intelligence within the educational process also introduces several challenges and risks. It is important to recognize that children at this developmental stage may not fully comprehend what artificial intelligence is or how it operates. Therefore, the implementation of technologies must be undertaken carefully and deliberately, taking into account the characteristics of children’s perception and development. Educators must be prepared to explain to children how to use artificial intelligence and how it can support their learning, while also considering the ethical aspects associated with the use of technologies in the educational process.

Despite its clear advantages, the integration of artificial intelligence into the educational process also entails certain ethical obligations. According to the Beijing Consensus on artificial intelligence and education, the development and implementation of technologies must guarantee high standards of educational quality for all. This entails that educational technologies should be accessible to every child, irrespective of social status or level of preparedness, and the utilization of artificial intelligence must not result in segregation or inequality in learning.

It is essential to recognize that the implementation of artificial intelligence within the educational process extends beyond merely developing software or platforms. This is a complex task that involves the professional development of educators, adaptation of curricula, and teaching methodologies. The implementation of artificial intelligence within the educational process should be conceived as a synergy between technology and humanity. The application of these technologies should complement, rather than replace, the personalized approach to teaching.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF ACTIVE GAMES FOR YOUNGER SCHOOLCHILDREN IN DEVELOPING INTEREST IN LEARNING AND DISCIPLINE

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Abstract: *Active games with younger schoolchildren enhance students' health, develop physical skills such as agility, endurance, and reaction speed, and facilitate the acquisition of movement coordination. Furthermore, this is one of the most favored and beneficial activities for children. The article provides a variety of descriptions of active games for younger schoolchildren, performed both outdoors and indoors.*

Keywords: *active games, coordination, motor skills, physical activity, interest in learning, teamwork skills.*

Contemporary children spend a significant amount of time after lessons engaged with computer games and various gadgets, which also adversely affects students' health. Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop physical culture among younger schoolchildren and to strengthen their health. Physical education lessons at school enable the development of strength, agility, speed, flexibility, and attention, improve overall health, and cultivate healthy lifestyle habits. However, physical education lessons alone are insufficient for schoolchildren, as the majority of students do not participate in physical exercises or activities during their free time. Active games are a crucial means of developing physical activity in younger schoolchildren and one of the most favored and beneficial activities for children of this age. Active games are based on physical exercises and movements during which participants overcome a series of obstacles and strive to achieve a specific, predetermined goal. Due to the wide variety of game content, they comprehensively affect both the body and personality, facilitating the achievement of essential specialized objectives in physical education. They strengthen health, develop physical qualities (agility, strength, endurance, speed), improve coordination and motor skills, and cultivate social and moral skills

such as teamwork skills, respect for opponents, determination, discipline, and responsibility, while also enhancing interest in learning.

Active games help to earn students' trust, foster a positive disposition toward the teacher, organize and discipline them, and stimulate interest in tasks — all of which can be effectively achieved through games. Play is an essential need of the developing child. Through play, a child trains their muscles, learns bodily control, becomes accustomed to discipline, and develops attention and memory. In play, the child expresses creativity and channels their boundless energy. Most importantly, in play, the child experiences joy and shares it with peers. Therefore, every physical education teacher in school must thoroughly study the games of younger schoolchildren and acquire the skills to conduct them effectively.

Children of younger school age exhibit heightened motor activity. They consistently desire to run, jump, and participate in sports games. It is precisely during this period, from ages 7 to 11, that physical culture, knowledge of a healthy lifestyle, and involvement in sports clubs should be developed.

Games with narrative content (Chelyuskinty), as well as those incorporating elements of dramatization (such as 'The Fox in the Chicken Coop'), particularly attract children's attention.

Often, such dramatized games are created by the schoolchildren themselves, with the material for their content drawn from everyday life or television programs.

Teachers must pay close attention to these games, as they reflect students' understanding of real-life phenomena. These games provide insight into how accurately children perceive specific events.

However, it is not only creative games that engage students. Younger schoolchildren also have a strong preference for active games. The developing muscles of schoolchildren require physical activity. Running and jumping are among their favorite activities.

However, teachers should keep in mind that younger schoolchildren, due to their limited control over movements, often experience overfatigue. When supervising active games, teachers need to timely substitute vigorous games with less physically demanding ones and avoid activities that may lead to student exhaustion.

This article presents descriptions of active and less active games that fulfill this need for movement.

Active games also include word games, which satisfy students' desire for rhythm in movement combined with speech. We are all familiar with the game 'Baba seyal gorokh, pryg-skok, pryg-skok' ('Grandma sowed peas, hop-skip, hop-skip'), which is devoid of meaningful content but rich in rhythm and variety of movements.

Such word and rhythm-based movement games are especially valuable when musical instruments are unavailable. Words aid in developing a sense of rhythm.

The game 'Chelyuskinty' is included in the section on less active games. Before the game begins, the teacher informs the children about the objectives of the Soviet expedition of 1933–1934 on the steamship Chelyuskin, led by O. Yu. Schmidt, which aimed to navigate the Northern Sea Route. As a result of an accident, 104 people were stranded on a drifting ice floe, where they lived for two months awaiting rescue. The air rescue operation of the Chelyuskin crew carried out by pilots, which was the largest air rescue mission of its time, and the pilot-rescuers who became the first Heroes of the Soviet Union. For two months, polar aviators (A. Lyapidevsky, M. Vodopyanov, V. Molokov, N. Kamanin, S. Levanevsky, M. Slepnev, I. Doronin) transported people to the mainland.

For the game, all participants are divided into three groups: Chelyuskinty, ice floes, and aviators. Furthermore, there should be two Chelyuskinty for every aviator.

The participants portraying the ice floes must number at least six.

The Chelyuskinty select Schmidt and Krenkel (the radio operator). The game begins. The Chelyuskinty advance in a line, arms extended, swaying, while reciting:

Many hardships lie ahead on our journey

We must endure them.

Success is assured for us

Through discipline, vigor, and laughter.

Left rudder, right rudder,

The waves cut the ship's bow.

Hey, helmsman, look ahead!

One, two, three!

At the same time, the ice begins to advance toward the Chelyuskinty. With crackling and hissing, it surrounds the Chelyuskinty as they hold hands...

Schmidt gives the command: 'Calmly! We are unloading onto the ice!' The ship is breaking apart. The Chelyuskinty stand in no particular order, surrounded by ice. The pilots are standing five steps from the ice.

Krenkel (the radio operator) reports over the radio: 'Hello! Hello! We are trapped in the ice.' 'Help us!' The men on the ice begin to raise their hands. At the count: 'one, two, three, four, five,' hands are raised; at the signal 'trum,' hands quickly go down, then go up again, down again, and so forth. The pilots hurry to rescue the Chelyuskinty. They perform this as follows. When the 'ice' raise their hands (indicating no movement), the pilots quickly enter the circle one by one, capture two 'Chelyuskint' players, and run back. If the 'trum' sound has already been heard and the ice have lowered their hands before the pilot has managed to exit, the pilot waits for the next raising of the ice players' hands and then runs out. All the Chelyuskint players were rescued. The best pilots are those who managed to enter and exit with the Chelyuskint players within a single command: 'one, two,

three, four, five.’ Then the children switch roles: those who were ice blocks become pilots, the pilots become Chelyuskintsy, and the Chelyuskintsy become ice blocks; this continues until everyone has assumed the role of pilot.

The section on active games examines the game ‘Traffic Light.’

The number of players is unlimited. The game is held in a hall or on a playground.

Equipment consists of red, green, and yellow flags. A police officer’s cap may be made.

Game description. The children are divided into three groups — trams, automobiles, and pedestrians. One child is chosen to play the role of the policeman.

The policeman raises the green flag, and everyone begins moving in one direction, keeping to the right side. “Ding-ding” — the trams depart (four children lined up in a row, one behind another, hands on each other’s shoulders) with pedestrians moving on the right. The automobiles proceed (in pairs, hands on shoulders).

Suddenly, the policeman raises the red flag indicating “danger.” Everyone stops immediately; anyone who takes a step is penalized. After the game, they receive a task to perform something (sing, dance, etc.).

The yellow flag—‘prepare’—march in place; the tram and automobiles start their engines (‘r-r-r’). Green again — go again.

The game is played several times; afterward, all participants who committed infractions complete assigned tasks.

It is advisable to conduct the game after a brief discussion on traffic rules. Best conducted with musical accompaniment.

Qualities developed through the game: familiarity with traffic regulations.

It is currently essential to accurately assess the level of physical education development among younger schoolchildren. To this end, it is necessary to utilize the diagnostic tool developed by L. V. Golovesko [4]. The diagnostic was supplemented with the requisite questions. The test is divided into four sections: hygiene, daily routine, traffic regulations, and civic life.

Following the study, it was determined that not all students are familiar with traffic regulations.

Challenges arose with questions concerning which personal items should not be shared with close friends and under what circumstances hand hygiene is obligatory. A series of questions regarding sports revealed that some students (31 %) do not participate in any sports activities. Only two percent of students perform morning exercises. The majority of students sleep less than eight hours and do not take outdoor walks during the day. Furthermore, a large number of students attend physical education classes, actively participate in relay races, and perform warm-up exercises.

More than half of the students are unfamiliar with traffic rules. Third-grade students prefer to spend their free time reading books, practicing music, doing beadwork, watching television, socializing with friends and acquaintances on social networks, and playing computer games.

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FOSTERING CIVIC ENGAGEMENT AMONG JUNIOR STUDENTS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES (USING ENGLISH AS AN EXAMPLE)

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Abstract. *This article explores the vital role of civic engagement in fostering active and responsible citizens within a democratic society, particularly among students who historically drive social change. It highlights the connection between foreign language learning and civic engagement, emphasizing how language studies are influenced by social and political contexts. Key mechanisms for enhancing civic engagement through language education include developing intercultural dialogue, strengthening values, and promoting analytical thinking. By integrating civic themes into foreign language curricula and employing diverse pedagogical approaches, educators can nurture students' understanding of their rights and responsibilities, ultimately contributing to informed citizenship and positive societal impact.*

Key words: *civic engagement, junior students, foreign language learning, motivation, intercultural dialogue.*

Civic engagement plays a vital role in a democratic society, contributing to the upbringing of active, responsible and conscious citizens capable of influencing the development of their own state and society. It also strengthens social cohesion and the development of civil society.

The cultivation of civic engagement among young people, particularly students, has always been a priority task for our state at all stages of its history. It is the students, young intellectuals who care most about the fate of their homeland and who have historically served not only as indicators of existing social demands but also as triggers for the implementation of social projects and the initiation of processes which bring fundamental changes in the country's life. [1]

In Europe at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century, student unrest and strikes often became the core of opposition movements and political radicalization. For instance, in Russia from 1899 to 1907, students played a significant role in coordinating public demonstrations and political mobilization during the revolutionary events of 1905.

During the 1960s and 1970s, student movements in Western Europe and the United States advocated for civil rights, anti-war policies, and social reforms, frequently serving as a springboard for mass societal changes.

Foreign language learning and civic engagement have always been closely linked, as social and political phenomena have always influenced the choice of languages and motivation for their study. Motivation, being one of the most crucial components of the educational process and determining students' success, fosters interest, improves academic performance, develops critical thinking, and forms stable learning habits. Maintaining and developing motivation among students should definitely be a priority for educators and educational institutions. There is a certain connection between motivation to learn and civic engagement, as teachers often refer to various political trends and social phenomena when fostering students' motivation.

In Russia, for example, in the 18th and 19th centuries, the study of French was prioritized, as it practically had the status of an official language for the upper classes of Russian society at that time. In the 20th century, during the Soviet period, education lost its elitist status to become mandatory for all segments of society. On August 25, 1932, a decree was issued by the Soviet government stating that every student in secondary and high school had to be proficient in at least one foreign language. Proficiency in a language was understood as the ability to read literary works and maintain a conversation in a certain foreign language. In higher education institutions, curricula included a four-year foreign language course with 2–3 hours weekly. In contrast, in the Russian Empire, where foreign languages were mandatory in gymnasiums, a classical boys' gymnasium in 1890 offered up to 113 such lessons per week during an 8-year course of study, including 40–42 lessons of Latin, up to 33 lessons of Greek, and 19 lessons each of German and French. Therefore, most representatives of the imperial intellectuals knew at least two foreign languages, while only 29 hours were allocated for the study of the Russian language. [5]

In the 19th century, Russian society demonstrated a lot of interest in learning primarily the German language, which was closely linked to the political realities of the time — Marx and Engels wrote in German. However, in the post-war world, interest in learning German declined as many refused to learn the «language of the fascists.» Due to the political and economic dominance of the USA, globalization, the growth of international trade and business, the need for scientific and technical cooperation, and the spread of American culture through new technologies and

media, the English language became the key to communication and development. Thus, it gained popularity in Russia.[3]

The peak interest in learning the English language in our country occurred in the 1990s, which, unfortunately, was driven by rather unpatriotic motivations. Young people sought to leave their homeland in search of a better life, primarily in the USA, which was actively recruiting successful graduates from Russian universities. It is true to say that even today, many teachers while motivating students to learn a particular language, refer to arguments far from patriotism as a civic engagement component, which we believe is unacceptable in higher educational institutions.

In the current geopolitical conditions, there is a notable rise in interest in learning the Chinese language, China being a key partner for the Russian federation. However, interest in the English language remains stable despite the change in geopolitical vectors affecting societal sentiments. English, along with Chinese and Spanish, is a language of international cooperation, for example, in organizations like BRICS. English is also one of the official languages of our neighbor and long-time ally — India, with which Russia continues to develop intensive economic, cultural, and educational ties. Currently, in RANEP, as well as in many other universities, there are student mobility and exchange programs with China and India. Students have the opportunity to study not only the language and culture but also to exchange experiences and knowledge with students representing friendly nations. This opportunity not only motivates students to learn foreign languages but also contributes to civic engagement cultivation.

It is important to note that shifting the focus to the realities of friendly nations in foreign language learning can foster students' civic engagement through several key mechanisms:

1. Development of intercultural dialogue and tolerance.

Studying the cultures of friendly nations in the context of foreign languages brings the ability to perceive and respect diversity, promoting tolerance and empathy. Understanding the diversity of the world helps students comprehend their country's place in a global context and the value of peaceful cooperation and partnership with other countries.

2. Strengthening value orientations.

Comparing the realities of friendly nations with one's native culture allows students to reflect more deeply on their own values, traditions, and history. For example, analyzing common achievements in science, art, or sports can strengthen pride in one's country and its contribution to the global community, which, in turn, forms the foundation for strengthening civic identity and patriotism.

3. Development of analytical thinking.

Working with materials about friendly nations typically involves comparative analysis, discussions, and project activities. Such methods develop critical

thinking, the ability to argue one's position, and evaluate information from various perspectives. The importance of these skills for cultivating a citizen capable of analyzing social and political processes can hardly be overstated.

4. Development of social responsibility.

Projects related to friendly nations can include elements of social activity: for example, cooperation with foreign partners and participation in international initiatives. This fosters a sense of responsibility among students not only for their country but also for the common future, which is an integral part of civic engagement.

5. Overcoming stereotypes and forming an objective view of the world.

Becoming acquainted with the realities of friendly nations helps combat simplified stereotypes and prejudices. Students learn to see the complexity and multifaceted nature of other cultures, thus developing an objective view of the world. This is significant for fostering civic engagement, as it helps avoid xenophobia and promotes a constructive attitude towards intercultural interaction. [2]

Foreign language learning broadens students' horizons, allowing them to better understand the cultural and historical contexts of these languages' existence. By studying a specific foreign language, students immerse themselves in the world of foreign culture, which includes not only literature and art but also pressing social and political issues. This knowledge helps them form their own opinions about the world, develop their civic position, and consciously approach participation in public life.

Another point to bring about is that motivation for language learning can be both intrinsic and extrinsic. Intrinsic motivation arises when students understand that learning a language will help them in the future, whether for career advancement, travel, or communication with people from other countries. Extrinsic motivation may be reflected in requirements from educational institutions or employers. However, intrinsic motivation typically leads to deeper and more conscious language learning. This is why teachers should actively utilize various methods and approaches to foster and maintain student motivation: employing modern technologies, implementing project activities that allow students to work on real tasks and projects related to the target language. Participation in international competitions or exchanges can also serve as an effective incentive for language learning, providing students with opportunities to apply their acquired knowledge in practice. An important element in this process is creating an atmosphere of trust and support within group activities. Students should feel that their opinions matter and their efforts are valued — this not only helps in language learning but also in forming an active civic position. When students see that their knowledge can influence the world around them, they become more interested and engaged in the learning process.

One of the contemporary approaches to fostering civic engagement is project-based learning. Creating projects in foreign languages on topics related to being

a good citizen helps students gain a deeper understanding of relevant social issues. In foreign language classes, students from various fields have an opportunity to study social phenomena and institutions in different regions of the world. For example, law students prepare projects investigating judicial systems in different countries; sports journalism students examine the prospects for the development of the most popular sports in various countries. Students studying public and municipal administration conduct comparative analyses of the governmental structures and political climates of different regions of the world, becoming acquainted with the biographies of notable political figures and their roles in the historical development of various countries. [4]

Discussions and debates refer to the most effective forms of speech activity. Organizing discussions on current topics develops argumentation skills and critical thinking and fosters the formation of students' civic positions. In foreign language classes, it is recommended to discuss the most relevant socio-political events and phenomena. This, in turn, enriches the educational process and creates conditions for bringing up a more open and informed generation ready to interact with the world.

Role-play activities, also being an effective form of activity in foreign language learning, help simulate situations related to the rights and responsibilities of citizens in society, allowing students to better understand these concepts in practice.

The use of media resources has long been an integral part of the educational process in foreign language teaching. Watching films, reading articles and listening to podcasts in a foreign language about government structures, civil rights, traditions, and cultures of different countries have proved effective and are highly recommended not only in classroom settings but also as independent study material.

There are also a lot of podcasts that could be useful for foreign language teachers. However, it is worth noting that modern technologies allow both teachers and students to take on the role of podcast creators themselves, choosing specific themes and utilizing internet technologies such as artificial intelligence.

Thus, fostering civic engagement among junior students in foreign language classes is an important and relevant task that requires a comprehensive approach. By using diverse methods and techniques, educators can create conditions for developing students' active civic positions, respect for cultural diversity, and social responsibility. All of this contributes not only to the successful foreign language learning but also to the upbringing of active, responsible citizens capable of contributing to the development of society.

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IMAGES OF THE EARTH'S SURFACE AS A RESOURCE FOR DEVELOPING SCHOOL STUDENTS' GEOGRAPHICAL LITERACY

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Abstract. *This article examines contemporary approaches to the use of images of the Earth's surface (maps, satellite images, digital cartographic services, and landscape photographs) in the school geography curriculum as a resource for developing students' geographical literacy. It is demonstrated that the shift from illustrative use of images to the organization of learning activities based on them facilitates the development of informational-graphic, spatial, analytical-interpretative, and practice-oriented components of geographical literacy in school students. A structure for a universal analytical worksheet on images of the Earth's surface is proposed, comprising five sections: 'What do we see?', 'Characteristics of phenomena or territorial features', 'Causes and conditions', 'Practical significance, hazards, problems', and 'Final conclusion'. Drawing on master classes and the 'Digital School' course, the experience of preparing future geography teachers to work with images of the Earth's surface is described, along with examples of case assignments focused on specific objects and natural processes. The potential of these forms of work is recognized for integrating lessons, extracurricular activities, and field research, as well as for developing practice-oriented training for future geography teachers.*

Keywords: *geographical literacy, images of the Earth's surface, satellite images, digital maps, case assignments, practice-oriented learning, training of geography teachers.*

Introduction

Contemporary schools increasingly focus not only on the transmission of subject knowledge but also on the development of functional literacy, including geographical literacy, among students. In geography, this signifies a transition from simply memorizing the names of features to acquiring the ability to navigate spatially, interpret various sources of geographical information, explain the interconnections between natural environments and economic activities, and make responsible decisions in real-life contexts.

One of the most critical resources facilitating these tasks is images of the Earth's surface: maps, aerial photographs, satellite images, digital maps, panoramas of the terrain, and ground-level photographs. In practice, however, such images are often used primarily as illustrations accompanying the teacher's narration, rather than as a comprehensive data source or as a foundation for inquiry, projects, or case studies [3; 7; 11; 15].

Amid the digitalization of education and the growing accessibility of geoinformation resources, there is an increasing need to understand the didactic potential of images of the Earth's surface and to identify contemporary methods of engaging with them that can foster the development of students' geographical literacy.

The aim of the article is to substantiate the potential of using various images of the Earth's surface as a resource for developing geographical literacy and to describe contemporary methods of working with them in the school geography curriculum.

To achieve this aim, the following objectives are established:

1. To briefly characterize the structure of students' geographical literacy in the context of working with images of the Earth's surface.

2. To present a typology of images of the Earth's surface accessible to geography teachers and to elucidate their didactic functions.

3. To describe contemporary methods of working with images (case assignments, educational quests, project-based research activities) aimed at fostering geographical literacy.

1. Geographical Literacy and the Role of Visual Sources

Geographical literacy among school students, in a broad sense, may be understood as the ability to:

- locate, comprehend, and interpret geographical information from various sources, including visual ones;
- apply geographical knowledge and skills to solve practical tasks related to the surrounding environment;
- analyze natural and socio-economic processes within specific territories;
- To assess the consequences of human activities on the environment and propose potential solutions [1; 8; 9; 13].

When interpreted through work with images of the Earth's surface, several key components can be identified:

1. Informational and graphic literacy — the ability to interpret a map, satellite image, aerial photograph, photograph, and terrain profiles; To identify objects, relationships, and processes depicted therein.

2. Spatial thinking — the ability to mentally transition from a two-dimensional image to the actual terrain, visualizing the location of objects, the characteristics of the relief, scale, and distances.

3. Analytical-interpretative skills denote the ability to draw conclusions from images regarding the causes and consequences of phenomena (such as changes in water levels, the occurrence of fires, landslides, mudflows, etc.).

4. Practice-oriented skills involve the ability to utilize images of the Earth's surface for route planning, natural hazard assessment, environmental problem discussions, and the design of human interventions within a territory.

Therefore, images of the Earth's surface serve not merely as illustrations but as a crucial tool for developing nearly all components of geographical literacy [2; 4; 10; 11].

2. Images of the Earth's Surface in School Geography: Typology and Didactic Functions

In contemporary schools, teachers can utilize a wide spectrum of images of the Earth's surface, both traditional and digital. These can be conventionally divided into several groups.

2.1. Maps (paper and digital)

This represents the classical type of image of the Earth's surface in geography. For the purpose of developing geographical literacy, the following are particularly important:

- atlas maps and wall maps (physical, political, thematic);
- digital maps of school electronic atlases and online services;
- specialized maps and diagrams: climatic, natural zones, natural resources, hazardous processes.

Didactic functions of maps:

- provide a systematic overview of the territory (location, boundaries, structure);
- allow measurement of distances, elevations, and indicators (according to the legend);
- enable the establishment of spatial relationships (for example, between relief, climate, and economic activity);
- serve as the basis for routes, projects, and model tasks.

2.2. Satellite Images and Aerial Photographs

Satellite images and aerial photography enable students to observe the Earth 'as seen from a satellite or aircraft.' Particularly effective for school geography are:

- images of large natural features (Antarctica, Baikal, the Caspian Sea);
- depictions of hazardous natural phenomena (hurricanes, cyclones, forest fires, mudflows);
- Images of large cities and industrial areas (urbanization, transportation, pollution).

Didactic functions of satellite images:

- They serve as authentic data, enabling the derivation of conclusions (such as water color, smoke plumes, ice cover, deforestation);

- They allow for the observation of dynamics (temporal changes when paired images are available);
- They enhance motivation through the effect of a ‘live view from above’;
- They serve as a starting point for case-based tasks and investigative questions (‘What happened and why?’).

2.3. Digital Maps, Navigation Services, and Panoramas

This category includes:

- online maps (Yandex.Maps, Google Maps, Google Earth, etc.);
- street panoramas and ‘street view’ perspectives;
- GPS navigation tracks, marked points, and routes.

Didactic functions:

- enable students to locate and correlate objects on the map and in the field;
- are used for planning routes (excursions, hikes, research outings);
- provide opportunities to work with local territories (school district, microdistrict, nearest park, river);
- serve as a bridge between the textbook and the child’s real life, thereby ‘grounding’ geography in their immediate surroundings and city.

2.4. Ground-Level Photographs, Profiles, and Diagrams

Photographs taken on site, terrain profiles, and cross-section diagrams complement the ‘bird’s-eye view,’ enabling:

- comparison of the landscape’s appearance from above and at human eye level;
- identification of details not visible in aerial images;
- refinement of perceptions regarding elevations, slope steepness, built environment, and vegetation condition.

The use of multiple types of images of the same territory (satellite image, map, photograph, profile) creates a multidimensional representation, assisting students in progressing from fragmented impressions to a comprehensive understanding of the geosystem [3; 5; 6; 8; 12].

3. Contemporary Methods of Working with Images of the Earth’s Surface

The transition to geographical literacy requires not merely ‘showing a picture’ but organizing purposeful activities around it. Let us examine several approaches that enable the realization of the potential of images of the Earth’s surface.

3.1. Working with a Universal Worksheet

One productive approach is the use of a universal worksheet for analyzing various images (maps, satellite images, photographs). The worksheet’s structure can remain consistent across different themes and grade levels, for example:

1. “What do we see?” — enumerating objects and their attributes (color, shape, labels).

2. “Characteristics of the phenomenon and territorial features” — identifying distinctive characteristics of a fire, cyclone, mudflow, unique lake, etc.
3. ‘Why does it look and occur this way?’ — an investigation of causes related to climate, relief, water bodies, and human activity.
4. ‘Practical significance, hazards, and challenges’ — a discussion of why this phenomenon is important or dangerous to people.
5. ‘Conclusion’ — a concise coherent text reflecting an understanding of the situation.

This structure can be applied to various phenomena: from forest fires in Yakutia or a mudflow-dammed lake in the Genaldon Gorge to hurricanes, the Caspian Sea, Baikal, volcanic islands, or Antarctica. Gradual application of this framework across various topics develops robust analytical skills: the student first learns to observe, then to identify features, followed by explaining causes, and only thereafter moves on to drawing conclusions.

3.2. Case assignments based on satellite images

The case approach enables the transformation of a static image into a problem situation that closely resembles real-world challenges. Examples include:

- ‘The Baltic Sea and the Curonian Lagoon’: using a satellite image, students compare the water color in the sea and lagoon, identify causes of the differences (rivers, depth, water ‘blooming,’ economic activities), and discuss environmental issues and their impacts on the coastline [6].
- ‘Forest Fires in Yakutia’: the image is used to identify fire hotspots, the direction of smoke spread, and the location of the territory on the map of Russia; the consequences for nature and people are analyzed, and the role of satellite images in fire monitoring is examined.

• ‘Mudflow in a Mountain Gorge’: students analyze the image to identify a mudflow dam and the resulting reservoir lake, predict possible dam breach and breakthrough flooding, and discuss measures for population protection [6].

The structure of the case includes a scenario (a brief text, often presented in the style of a news report or a traveler’s account), images, a set of questions and tasks of varying complexity, and an output product (a mini-essay, memo, diagram, or route).

Such cases cultivate the ability to interpret visual data within the context of real-world issues, rather than solely to ‘recognize’ objects.

3.3. Educational quests and geocaching with subsequent image analysis

Quests and geocaching, which employ a combination of elements, occupy a special place:

image → *terrain* → *image again*.

For example, in an urban environment (the Perlovka microdistrict of Mytishchi city, a park, the microdistrict surrounding the school):

- At the first stage, students orient themselves using a map and/or image, locating specified points (a bridge, a river bend, a terrain feature, a monument).

- In the field, they complete tasks (observe, photograph, sketch a profile, assess the environmental condition).

- Then, in the classroom, they return to satellite images and digital maps, correlating their observations with the “view from above.”

This cycle provides:

- the integration of the school map, satellite images, and the student’s personal experience;

- the development of practice-oriented skills (route planning, hazard assessment, problem-solving);

- the cultivation of motivation: the area surrounding the school transforms into a ‘field site’ for geographical research.

3.4. Project and research activities

Images of the Earth’s surface serve as a convenient foundation for educational projects. Possible directions include:

- Dynamics of natural features: glacier retreat, shoreline changes, growth or deforestation of forest stands, and alterations in the area of water bodies (when images from multiple years are available);

- Urban geography: expansion of built-up areas, modifications in the transportation network, and the emergence of new infrastructure facilities;

- Local environmental studies: the condition of rivers, green spaces, ravines, and agricultural lands in the vicinity of the school.

Project work with images entails:

1. Formulation of a research question (for example: ‘How has the shoreline of our pond changed over the last 10–15 years?’).

2. Selection of images from different years, maps, and supplementary sources.

3. Comparison, analysis, and drawing of conclusions.

4. Presentation of results in the form of a map, poster, presentation, or short report.

Such projects develop not only geographical literacy among school students but also their research, communication, and presentation skills.

4. Experience in preparing future geography teachers: from mastering images to lesson design.

The preparation of future geography teachers to utilize images of the Earth’s surface in lessons cannot be accomplished solely through demonstrating the capabilities of digital resources. It is important that students not only are aware of the existence of satellite images, online maps, and navigation services but also master the methods of their didactic application, learn to design assignments,

and understand the relationship between this work and students' educational outcomes [3; 14].

Within the framework of courses on geography teaching methodology and the discipline 'Digital School,' a system of practice-oriented classes is implemented, including original master classes.

4.1. The Place and Objectives of the Module in Student Training

The use of images of the Earth's surface is incorporated into undergraduate training as an overarching theme that runs through several thematic blocks:

- general methodology of teaching geography (developing geographical literacy, working with maps and remote sensing data);
- the 'Digital School' course (proficiency with digital maps, satellite imagery, online services, and GPS navigators);
- methodology for studying the 'Geography of Russia' course (nature, population, economy, and regions of Russia).

The objectives of this module for student teachers can be formulated as follows:

1. To teach students to read and interpret various images of the Earth's surface (maps, satellite images, photographs, digital maps) in relation to school topics.
2. To develop experience in designing educational assignments and case studies based on images, with consideration of the age characteristics and geographical literacy levels of students.
3. To cultivate the ability to connect visual materials with practice-oriented tasks for schoolchildren (routes, local studies, environmental issues, safety).

Thus, an important component of a geography teacher's professional competence is developed: the ability to utilize modern visual and digital resources as tools for achieving planned learning outcomes.

4.2. Master class: 'The Case as an Adventure: Geography in Stories and Problems' (local route)

The first step involves a master class focused on working with a navigator and the local territory. Third- and fourth-year students, initially acting as learners and then as teachers, follow a route in the Perlovka district (city of Mytishchi), using GPS navigators and pre-selected points.

The master class structure includes:

- a brief introduction to the principles of GPS operation and the potential uses of the navigator in lessons and extracurricular activities;
- students conducting field search tasks in small groups (using coordinates and descriptions of objects such as a station, monument, park, riverbank, etc.);
- collection of visual materials: photographs of route points, concise descriptions, and documentation of problems and noteworthy features of the territory;

- returning to the classroom to transform the completed route into an educational case study or excursion route for school students (including tasks, questions, and problem scenarios).

It is important that, in this master class, the local territory familiar to the students is linked with the map and digital images, while the geographical content is embedded in the history of a specific place (such as the history of the settlement, commemorative sites, natural features of the river valley, etc.). Students gain the experience of ‘living the case’ and observe how a route or quest can serve as a form of acquiring geographical knowledge and skills.

4.3. Master Class on Satellite Images: A Universal Worksheet and Nine Thematic Cases

The second essential element is a master class focused on the use of satellite images and maps in the geography curriculum. A series of Earth’s surface images depicting diverse natural features and processes is selected for the exercise [6]:

- the Baltic Sea and the Curonian Lagoon;
- the Solovetsky Islands (satellite image and map fragment);
- tropical hurricanes over various regions of the world;
- forest fires in Yakutia;
- a mudflow dam and an impounded lake in the Genaldon Gorge;
- Antarctica;
- cyclone over the East European Plain;
- Caspian Sea lake;
- Lake Baikal;
- volcanic island off the coast of Japan.

Students work in small groups (2–3 people). Each group receives its own image (or a set comprising an image, map, and photograph) and a universal worksheet containing five sections:

1. ‘What do we see in the image?’ — recognition of objects, working with color, shape, and labels.
2. ‘Indicators of the phenomenon or characteristics of the territory’.
3. ‘Causes and conditions’ — based on the atlas, location, climate, relief, and human activity.
4. ‘Practical significance, hazards, and problems’.
5. ‘Final conclusion’ derived from the image.

At the first stage, students complete the worksheet as ‘learners,’ that is, they carry out the proposed tasks related to their own topic. At the second stage, they assume the role of teachers and:

- revise the task formulations taking into account the age of the students (grades 5–6 or 7–9);

- They add their own questions and tasks, including practice-oriented ones (route planning, discussion of an environmental issue, research project).

- They consider which topics of the school curriculum this case study could be integrated into and how it aligns with the planned learning outcomes.

The final product of the master class is a set of mini case studies and worksheets that can potentially be used by students in their future teaching practice and geography lessons at school.

4.4. Professional Competencies Developed in Future Geography Teachers

The reviewed master classes facilitate the targeted development in students of a range of professionally significant competencies related to the use of images of the Earth's surface:

- Information-analytical competence: the ability to select and interpret visual geographical materials (maps, satellite images, photographs) to solve educational tasks.

- Methodological competence: the ability to design assignments, worksheets, and cases based on images, differentiate them according to complexity level and student age, and structure the logic of questions progressing from observation to explanation and conclusion.

- Design competence: the ability to transform a local area (the Perlovka district, a park, a river section) or major features (Antarctica, Baikal, the Caspian Sea) into the foundation of a cohesive educational narrative that includes elements of inquiry-based and practical activities.

- Teacher digital competence: proficiency in the fundamental functionalities of digital atlases, online maps, and navigation services, coupled with an understanding of their instructional potential.

- Reflective competence: the ability to analyze one's own experience in participating in a master class and to evaluate which techniques for working with images are most effective in fostering students' geographical literacy.

Thus, the integration of images of the Earth's surface within the training system for future geography teachers is viewed not as a mere 'supplement' to the traditional curriculum, but as a central component of professional development, directly linked to the quality of future teaching.

4.5. Observed Effects and Prospects for Development

The outcomes of discussions regarding master classes with students and instructors highlight several positive effects:

- students' motivation to acquire methods for working with images of the Earth's surface increases; they begin to regard satellite images and maps as instruments of professional practice rather than solely as supplementary visual materials;

- There is an increasing recognition of the connection between the quality of assignments and the actual educational outcomes of school students: students

understand that the depth of comprehension of a phenomenon during the lesson depends on how the question regarding the image is formulated.

- The range of ideas for school projects and extracurricular activities is broadening, including geocaching, local environmental studies, and the investigation of natural objects' dynamics through images from different years.

- A foundation is established for the development of methodological materials, such as collections of case studies, worksheets, and practical guides for working with images of the Earth's surface, based on student-generated work.

Prospects for the development of this work include:

- the inclusion of such master classes in the system of student practices and internships, whereby the cases they develop are effectively piloted in schools;

- the expanded use of GIS platforms and remote sensing services within educational modules;

- the creation of an electronic repository of tasks and cases designed both for school students and for the training of future teachers.

Conclusion

The analysis conducted demonstrates that images of the Earth's surface hold significant potential for fostering students' geographical literacy when employed not merely as illustrative material but as a foundation for systematic educational activities. The developed model of a universal worksheet facilitates working with various types of images according to a unified logic: from initial observation and identifying features, through establishing causes and practical significance, to formulating independent conclusions.

Experience with using satellite images, digital maps, and local routes in the training of future geography teachers shows that these forms of work foster the development of students' informational-analytical, methodological, design, and digital competencies. Case assignments focusing on specific objects and processes facilitate the integration of visual materials into lessons on the geography of Russia and the world, as well as into extracurricular and project-research activities. Future work prospects involve expanding the repository of tasks based on images of the Earth's surface, incorporating GIS technologies, and systematically piloting the developed materials in school practice and teacher education programs.

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ON THE PHYSICAL FITNESS REQUIREMENTS OF FUTURE SUBLUNAR SPACE EXPLORERS

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“We are born to make a fairy tale come true...”

Keywords: *Moon, subsurface, space marine, tunneling, rock fragmentation, sport, physical education.*

At the beginning of 2010, in Moscow, at the 34th Academic Readings on Cosmonautics in memory of S. P. Korolev, General Director of the Russian Space Corporation Energia and Academician of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Vitaliy Lopota, in a report on the current development of Russian cosmonautics in figures and dates, presented the program for creating a Russian orbital base for constructing interplanetary spacecraft by 2030. By 2040, RSC “Energia” has planned to complete the preparation for the Mars expedition.

Let us consider the role assigned to the only specialists worldwide who are already prepared today to commence the development and creation of equipment and technologies for constructing habitable facilities located both within the Earth’s subsurface and that of celestial bodies.

The primary asset that Near Space can offer Earth is the validation of scientific ideas and the advancement of new scientific disciplines. There is also a direct and evident benefit in the development of Solar System celestial bodies in the form of mineral resources, known on Earth as rare-earth elements. For example, humanity invests significant effort in energy production through controlled thermonuclear fusion. Thus, colleagues, for sustainable controlled fusion, not deuterium and tritium (hydrogen isotopes) are appropriate, but a raw material such as the helium isotope known as “helium — 3”. While this isotope is extremely rare on Earth, the reserves of helium-3 on the Moon are so vast that planet Earth could be supplied with energy for millennia.

Our considerations will be limited to the exploration of the Solar System. Moreover, during this century, humanity will succeed in visiting the Moon, Mars, and such Jovian satellites as Callisto — a repository of metals — and Europa, the richest reservoir of water in the Solar System. Human space exploration will proceed ‘step by step,’ as the immense distances and even more unimaginable financial and intellectual costs will inevitably compel scientists to pursue a path of risk minimization. Accordingly, the development and testing of all technologies will inevitably commence on the Moon — the celestial body that Providence has placed closest to Earth. Thus, engineers of the future, capable of extended stays in space, are essential for the execution of forthcoming expeditions. This requires specialized physical training.

Cosmonauts’ physical training comprises a comprehensive set of exercises targeting strength, endurance, coordination, and vestibular system conditioning, including running, swimming, gymnastics, strength training, and parachuting, as well as specialized testing in centrifuges, barochambers, and hydrolaboratories to prepare for extreme flight conditions and adaptation to weightlessness. On Earth, the physical standards are rigorous (running, swimming, pull-ups), whereas in space, daily training sessions (2 hours) are essential to counteract muscle and bone atrophy, utilizing stationary bikes and treadmills.

Massive muscles do not play a significant role in the physical condition of a cosmonaut. He must be strong, agile, and resilient to function comfortably in weightlessness. Therefore, the majority of training encompasses various sports to enhance these capabilities. These include athletics, swimming, parachuting, diving, artistic gymnastics, and skiing.

Cosmonauts spend two hours in the gym three times a week, emphasizing multifunctional training. Weight training exercises are mainly performed with light weights to maintain muscle tone. To achieve the highest score in physical fitness, a cosmonaut candidate under 35 years of age must meet the following standards:

- 3 km run — no more than 12 minutes and 20 seconds
- 800 m freestyle swim — no more than 19 minutes
- 5 km cross-country ski race — no more than 24 minutes
- pull-ups — 14 repetitions
- 100-meter sprint — no more than 13.2 seconds
- Long jump — at least 2.5 meters.
- Underwater diving — at least 25 meters.

The standards appear entirely achievable. Perhaps some of you may even wish to test your abilities and pass the initial stage of selection. However, these training exercises constitute only a small part of the extensive preparation cosmonauts must undergo prior to flight.

For the purpose of training, the construction of a long-term space base on the Moon is envisaged. Simultaneously, factors such as intense cosmic radiation, frequent meteorite showers, vacuum, and abrupt temperature fluctuations on one side, and the high cost combined with delivery times of equipment and consumables from Earth, alongside the need to ensure their preservation on the lunar surface on the other side, tip the balance in favor of establishing the Base within the lunar regolith.

What is the conclusion, colleagues? Russia urgently needs mining engineers — space marines!

And what are the requirements for space marines, apart from excellent physical fitness?

A space marine is a highly qualified specialist in mining, endowed with great courage and profound professional responsibility.

Fully aware of the risks and complexities inherent in conducting mining operations practically in open Space, a space marine must apply all their knowledge and experience to accomplish the mission, or, if that is not possible, to advance mining operations to the greatest extent their strength permits.

It is now necessary to examine the list of technological tasks involved in the development of sublunar space.

1. The space marine is required to personally participate in the creation, assembly, and field testing of each equipment component. This is not only crucial from the perspective of professional training but often directly influences the specialist's survivability under extreme conditions. Space marines will repeatedly conduct field tests fully equipped with space suits, as during mining operations within the confined volume of lunar regolith, stringent requirements apply to preserving the integrity of the suit. Despite the significant achievements of Russian specialists in the field of industrial textiles — who have developed ultra-strong reinforced fabrics, including those intended for space applications — the testing of the space marine's operational parameters in confined environments relative to the surfaces of mining excavations and the corresponding equipment remains vital.

2. The construction of the lunar Base will require not merely tons but tens of tons of various cargoes, which presents considerable challenges to contemplate. It should be noted that delivering all cargo from the planet's surface to near-Earth orbit using rocket engines is a necessary, and unfortunately sufficient, condition. Is the delivery of a cargo container to the lunar surface using rocket engines truly necessary? After all, the total volume of rocket fuel ultimately affects the overall cost of the entire Project!

Since we are discussing space athletes, let us attempt to apply the practices of the Russian Airborne Troops. Let us devise a lunar cargo parachute!

Fig. 1 Diagram of the space parachute:

1. cargo container, 2. explosive charge, 3. parachute canopy

It is necessary to develop a cargo container and a parachute that self-deploys in lunar orbit, analogous to the deployment of solar panels and “mirrors” of space radio telescopes in orbit.

Given the container’s deployment to low Earth orbit, it possesses specific, limited linear and volumetric dimensions, considerably smaller in cross-sectional area than the parachute dome. It would be an unacceptable engineering oversight not to leverage this fact in practice. Thus, charges of explosives are sequentially fired from the container, generating upon detonation the required gas volumes to decelerate the payload as it approaches the lunar surface. Gas in the vacuum of space forms a dispersal sphere, and thus, when interacting with the cross-sectional area of the container shape S_1 and the parachute area S_2 , it produces a braking effect

with a deceleration force proportional to the ratio of these areas.
$$F_{\text{top}} = f \left(\frac{S_2}{S_1} \right)$$

. One kilogram of explosives produces approximately one thousand liters of gas. The details will be finalized by specialists in ballistics and developers of parachute technology. But what advantages! We free the containers from rocket engines and a considerable volume of rocket fuel. Meanwhile, the cargo spacecraft can tow several similar autonomous equipment containers to the Moon from low Earth orbit, functioning like a tug.

2. Here, the miners — Space Marines — are on the lunar surface equipped with all necessary cargo, which must still be transformed through the required technological processes. The universe is somewhat gracious to us, and on the sunlit surface of the Moon, we have two unlimited and renewable sources of energy.

The first is solar radiation, which we readily convert into electrical energy through solar panels.

The second is solar radiant energy itself, which we transform into thermal energy within the focal heat generator using concentrated mirrors.

Once the location for the vertical shaft excavation has been determined and the solar panels and heliothermal generator have been positioned as close to it as possible, one may proceed directly to the construction process.

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**CHOKAN VALIKHANOV:
A SYMBOL OF SCIENTIFIC ACHIEVEMENT**

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the scientific activities of Chokan Valikhanov. It is noted that in 1985 UNESCO commemorated the 150th anniversary of Valikhanov's birth, which confirms the global recognition of his contribution. Attention is drawn to the fact that his expeditions, in particular the one to Kashgar in 1858–1859, served as an example of combining scientific achievement with an exploratory mission involving considerable risks. The scholar demonstrated personal courage, a readiness to face extreme trials, the ability to maintain composure in dangerous situations, and determination to continue his work despite threats to his life.*

In 2025. Academic circles and the public of the Russian Federation and the Republic of Kazakhstan commemorated the 190th anniversary of Ch. Ch. Valikhanov. The necessity of involving a broad range of young researchers is emphasized in order to seek answers to existing contentious issues in the biography of Ch. Ch. Valikhanov.

Keywords: *Valikhanov, scholar, Central Asia, Kashgar, journey.*

Chokan Chingisovich Valikhanov (1835–1865) was a Kazakh scholar, traveler, ethnographer, diplomat, and educator who served as a bridge between the peoples of Eurasia. His life and legacy exemplify the synthesis of Eastern and European cultures. His five-volume scholarly legacy remains pertinent to historians, ethnographers, and cultural scholars to this day. The uniqueness of Chokan Valikhanov's scientific research lies in his interdisciplinary approach, innovative methods of source analysis, as well as the extensive and profound study of little-known regions. His works laid the foundations for the development of Oriental studies, ethnography, geography, folklore, and the history of Central Asia. Ch. Ch. Valikhanov's works attracted the interest of Western European scholars, particularly

English, German, and French orientalists, geographers, and contemporary historians. Valikhanov's research was published in the proceedings of the Russian Geographical Society, as well as in Berlin (1862) and London (1865), and was included in volumes 6 and 7 (1878–1879) of Élisée Reclus's 19-volume *Universal Geography* in French. Valikhanov was the first to introduce into scholarly use the Kashgar manuscripts 'Tazkira-i Bogra Khan' and 'Tazkira-i Khodjagan,' as well as to conduct research on Muhammad Haidar Dulati's work 'Tarikh-i Rashidi.'

Chokan Valikhanov was born in November 1835 in the aul of Kusmurun, Amangarai District, now the village of Kuntymes, Sarykol District, Kostanay Region. At birth, the infant was named Muhammad-Khanafiya, and subsequently, the affectionate name Chokan given by his mother Zeynep became his official name. His ancestors are descendants of the Chingisids; the great-grandfather Ablai (1711–1781) was Khan of the Middle Zhuz. The eldest son of Khan Ablai, Wali (1781–1819) — the last Khan of the Middle Zhuz — was Chokan's paternal grandfather, from whom he inherited his surname. Chokan's father, Chingis, was born to Khan Wali's younger wife, Aiganym, who became head of the khan's family following her husband's death. An intelligent, farsighted, and for that era well-educated woman provided her son with an excellent education: Chingis graduated from the Siberian Line Cossack Host School in Omsk, which offered a comprehensive secondary education. Chingis was among the first Kazakhs to master not only Eastern literacy but also the Russian language¹.

According to biographers, during his childhood, Chokan studied for about three years in Kusmurun at a madrasa, where he acquired Muslim literacy, mastered the basics of Arabic script, studied Eastern languages, and familiarized himself with medieval literature. One of Chokan's childhood interests was drawing, particularly sketching from nature. He acquired this skill from Russian cartographic artists and surveyors who resided for extended periods at the Kusmurun fortress, within the Valikhanov family. Subsequently, he formed the habit of illustrating in his diaries the things he observed around him; in numerous albums, he drew ethnographic objects and genre scenes, as well as drafted plans, diagrams, and routes².

In Chokan's spiritual development, his grandmother Aiganim played a significant role; from early childhood, he listened to her recount ancient Kazakh legends, tales, parables, and wise sayings. Already in his childhood, he recorded several versions of the steppe poems 'Қозы Көрпеш — Баян-сұлу' and 'Ер Көкше.' Even as a child, Chokan was recognized as a connoisseur of steppe traditions and

¹ Valikhanov Ch. Ch. Collected Works in Five Volumes. Vol. I — Alma-Ata: Great Soviet Encyclopedia, 1984.— p. 11.

² Valikhanov Ch. Ch. Collected Works in Five Volumes. Vol. I — Alma-Ata: Great Soviet Encyclopedia, 1984.— p. 19.

customs. The period of Chokan's most intensive spiritual formation is associated with the Omsk Cadet Corps, which at that time was considered one of the foremost educational institutions in Western Siberia, where he enrolled at the age of twelve. From his first year, the young cadet was distinguished by diligence and discipline. During his studies, he befriended G. N. Potanin, who later became a prominent scholar and public figure. Chokan studied military and general educational subjects with great interest, significantly deepening his knowledge of Eastern languages. He excelled academically beyond many of his peers. His friend and classmate G. Potanin wrote of this: «...Chokan developed rapidly and advanced far ahead of his companions.» Chokan avidly read the works of prominent Russian and foreign poets and writers such as A. S. Pushkin, M. Yu. Lermontov, N. V. Gogol, and Charles Dickens, among others. During this time, he formed a circle of acquaintances that included his mentors and classmates, notably the orientalist N. F. Kostyletskiy, historian P. V. Gonsevsky, publicist N. M. Yadrintsev, and others¹.

By the age of eighteen, in 1853, Valikhanov, a graduate of the Cadet Corps and cornet in the army cavalry, was assigned to the Sixth Cavalry Regiment of the Siberian Cossack Host. A year later, he was appointed adjutant to General Gustav Gasfort, who was then governing Western Siberia and the northeastern regions of Kazakhstan. In 1855, Chokan participated in General G. Gasfort's journey and undertook an extensive expedition across Central Kazakhstan, Semirechye, and Tarbagatai. In the same year, he took part in a major military-scientific expedition organized under the command of Colonel M. Khomentovsky. Chokan spent two months among the Kyrgyz in the Issyk-Kul basin. He addressed issues concerning the reconciliation of the Kyrgyz clans Bugu and Sarybagysh; simultaneously, he gathered various information, primarily studying the oral traditions and language of the Kyrgyz. He took part in the surveying of Lake Issyk-Kul, resulting in modifications to the shape and contours of its shores on the new map. He collected ornithological and entomological specimens, compiled a herbarium, and studied the flora and fauna of Semirechye and Issyk-Kul. Based on the results of this assignment, the cornet was awarded a commendation, and in 1856... He was awarded the rank of lieutenant.

At the beginning of August 1856, Ch. Valikhanov proceeded to Kuldja. En route, he visited a number of border posts in Western China. Chokan was provided with instructions from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs stating: '...To act in full consultation with the consul in Kuldja...'. 'Our main objective is to achieve a friendly resolution of the matter with China and to promptly restore the interrupted trade relations... In the event of Chinese demands, to enter into negotiations

¹ Valikhanov Ch. Ch. Collected Works in Five Volumes. Vol. I — Alma-Ata: Great Soviet Encyclopedia, 1984. — p. 91.

concerning our borders with China.’ Thus, Valikhanov was entrusted with a complex diplomatic mission involving the resolution of disputed border issues and the establishment of normal trade relations with China. He fulfilled this important assignment with distinction. Following a series of consultations with Chinese officials in Kuldja, trade relations were established and friendly ties between the two states restored. According to A. K. Haynes, Valikhanov’s journey to Kuldja laid the foundation for the ‘Tarbagatay Treaty and the opening of consulates in Kuldja and Chuguchak.’ Ch. Valikhanov stayed in the Kulja region for about three months; then, with the onset of late autumn, he returned to Omsk¹.

In 1857. In 1857, Ch. Valikhanov once again traveled to the Alatau Kyrgyz, this time to observe the situation in the areas of Western China adjacent to the southern border of the Russian territories, in connection with the unrest in Kashgar. During the mission, the young researcher was the first to draw attention to the famous Kyrgyz epic ‘Manas,’ referring to it as ‘the Steppe Iliad.’ The results of Chokan’s three journeys were the skillfully written travel essays “Diary of a Trip to Issyk-Kul,” “The Western Province of the Chinese Empire and the City of Kuldja,” and “Notes on the Kyrgyz.”

Winter of 1856. Chokan spent the winter of 1856 exclusively in the regional archive of Western Siberia, where he thoroughly studied all eastern sources pertaining to the Kyrgyz. On February 27, 1857. Ch. Valikhanov, upon the recommendation of P. Semenov-Tyan-Shansky was elected as a full member of the Russian Geographical Society, which signified recognition of the young scholar’s achievements.

In 1858–1859. He undertook his renowned journey to Kashgaria, which established his reputation as a courageous traveler. After Marco Polo and the Jesuit Goës, he was the first to enter Kashgaria. Having studied the geography, history, political system, and the characteristics of culture and everyday life in this then little-known country to Europe, Ch. Valikhanov made a significant contribution to the scientific study of Eastern Turkestan. This trip was extremely dangerous due to the ongoing war; for several years, there had been no stable authority in the region, and the country was engulfed in disorder, compounded by the local authorities’ suspicious attitude towards all foreign matters. The journey to Kashgar possessed not only immense scientific significance. Chokan was also entrusted with gathering valuable information for Russia about the contemporary condition of Eastern Turkestan and clarifying the causes of the disturbances occurring in the region at that time.

Subsequently, based on the materials obtained by the expedition, it was intended to develop a comprehensive political strategy concerning the region. From a geopolitical standpoint, the possibility of curbing the influence of Great Britain, which held dominions in India and was consolidating its presence in the region,

¹ Ch. Ch. Valikhanov. —URL: <https://infosphere.top/wiki/Ch.Valikhanov/> .

was under consideration. Accordingly, the expedition was organized by two principal imperial authorities — the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, through its Asian Department, and the General Staff of the Russian Armed Forces, which justifies the assertion that the primary objective of the expeditionary caravan they dispatched was the gathering of intelligence materials.

Chokan spent approximately half a year in Kashgar (from October 1, 1858, to mid-March 1859). During this period, he became closely acquainted with the city and conducted a thorough study of the country of the Six Cities (Altyshar, which comprised the cities of Kashgar, Aksu, Uch-Turfan, Yansar, Yarkand, and Hotan). Besides Kashgar, Chokan managed to visit Yarkand, but was unable to proceed to Hotan owing to the deteriorating political situation. Valikhanov was the first to determine the circumstances surrounding the death of the German geographer and employee of the British East India Company, Adolf Schlagintweit, a student of Alexander von Humboldt, who had entered Kashgaria a year earlier and was beheaded by the local authorities.

The situation prevailing in Kashgar during Ch. Valikhanov's stay is detailed in the 'Report on the Journey to Kashgar by Lieutenant Valikhanov,' which states: '...Lieutenant Valikhanov lived in Kashgar for five months, visited the surrounding towns, and managed to study and observe much.' In all six cities of Eastern Turkestan, there are only 15,000 Chinese troops. The natives do not perform military service. The soldiers are armed with bows and arrows, and only a small portion with firearms; There is almost no artillery at all...»¹.

During his journey to Kashgar, Chokan acquired a number of unique Eastern manuscripts, compiled a numismatic collection, a herbarium, a collection of rock specimens, and gathered various relics: ancient charters, examples of applied and folk decorative arts, artistic ceramics, and so forth. On March 11, 1859. He set out on the return journey and on April 12 of the same year arrived at the Verne fortification (now the city of Almaty). The journey to Kashgar lasted a total of ten months and fourteen days. Having stayed in Verne for approximately one and a half months, he returned to Omsk, where he commenced processing the collected materials.

At the end of 1859. Chokan arrived in Saint Petersburg, where he was retained for scholarly pursuits. He was assigned to the Asian Department of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. He was transferred from the military department to the foreign affairs system, while retaining his position in the army cavalry. This is stated in the order signed by Emperor Alexander II. By the highest command, the merits of the scholar-explorer were likewise acknowledged through his promotion to the

¹ Excerpt from the report on the journey to Kashgar by Lieutenant Ch. Valikhanov.— Collected Works in 5 Volumes.— Vol. 3. Alma-Ata: Great Soviet Encyclopedia, 1985, pp. 219–222.

rank of staff rotmistr, the awarding of an order, and a monetary prize. The Saint Petersburg period represents a vivid chapter in Valikhanov's biography. According to Semenov-Tian-Shansky, under his influence, he attended university lectures and became proficient in French and German¹.

During these years, Chokan was able to vividly demonstrate his exceptional talent and knowledge: he worked at several institutions — the Military Scientific Committee of the General Staff, the Asian Department, the Geographical Society — while simultaneously attending university lectures. He worked at the higher school for scientific studies within the Asian Department, where he taught Turkic languages to individuals traveling to Central Asia. By order of the Military Scientific Committee, he compiled maps of Central Asia and Eastern Turkestan. Under his editorship, the following were prepared: 'Map of the area between Lake Balkhash and the Alatau Range,' 'Reconnaissance of the western part of the Zailiysky region,' 'Plan of the city of Kuldja,' 'Map of the Western Region of the Chinese Empire,' and others. They meticulously studied ancient maps in various languages.

The damp climate of the capital adversely affected Chokan Valikhanov's health, already weakened by his travels, and on the advice of doctors, he was compelled to return to his homeland. The renowned Russian writer M. N. Ivlev describes Chokan Chingisovich's sudden departure from Saint Petersburg to his homeland as follows: 'At the end of May 1861, a carriage was departing from Saint Petersburg, the imperial capital of Russia, bound for Central Asia.' He was a seriously ill young man of Asian appearance dressed in the uniform of a Russian officer. He was the son of the senior sultan of the Kushmurun district and a distant descendant of the 'shaker of the universe'—the formidable Genghis Khan — Staff Captain of the Russian Army, Chokan Valikhanov. By the age of twenty-five, he was already one of the most renowned scholars and travelers in Russia, the first to undertake a perilous and eventful journey that revealed the then-unknown Kashgaria to the world and returned safely. In the capital, he left behind a significant cartographic project on the composition of Asian maps at the General Staff, as well as friends and acquaintances, including writers, poets, and scholars — F. M. Dostoevsky, A. N. Maykov, A. N. Pleshcheev, P. P. Semyonov-Tyan-Shansky, A. N. Beketov, E. P. Kovalevsky, and others².

On behalf of the Russian Geographical Society and Russian scholars, the distinguished orientalist I. I. assessed Chokan Valikhanov's contributions. Veselovsky wrote about him: "Like a brilliant meteor, a descendant of Kyrgyz khans and

¹ Valikhanov Ch. Ch. Collected Works in Five Volumes. — Vol. 5. — Alma-Ata: Great Soviet Encyclopedia, 1985, pp. 241–242.

² Ivlev M. N. Travels of the Steppe Prince // Centrasia. —URL: <https://centrasia.org/newsA.php?s=t=1292241120>.

simultaneously an officer of the Russian army, Chokan Chingisovich Valikhanov flashed across the field of Oriental studies.” Russian Orientalists unanimously recognized him as a phenomenal figure and expected great and important revelations from him concerning the fate of Turkic peoples, but the premature death of Chokan deprived us of these hopes. In less than thirty years, he accomplished what others could not achieve in a lifetime.”¹

His friend, the eminent Russian writer and thinker F. Dostoevsky spoke of him thus: «His name will not fade from the history of the Kirgiz-Kaisaks and Kara-Kirgiz; it will be remembered by both peoples». The Russian publicist, writer, and social activist, as well as a scholar of Siberia and Central Asia, N. M. Yadrintsev, who was a friend of Chokan, also remarked upon the death of Ch. Ch. Valikhanov: «Last autumn, in the Zaili region, the Kirgiz sultan Chokan Chingizovich Valikhanov, renowned for his daring expedition to Kashgar, a city in western China, passed away... We can find no more fitting way to honor the memory of Chokan Valikhanov than to wish that the Kirgiz people will not have to wait as long for a second Valikhanov as the Buryats awaited a second Dorzhi Banzarov.» Certainly, no better guides to European civilization and humanity among indigenous peoples exist than the indigenous peoples themselves. Therefore, we are always inclined to sympathize with the emergence of educated indigenous peoples, and we regard their deaths as a gross injustice of fate»².

The contributions of Ch. Valikhanov to the study of the history of the Senior Zhuz are particularly significant. As is well known, until the mid-nineteenth century, an erroneous opinion prevailed in scholarship, expressed already by eighteenth-century travelers, that the Senior Zhuz and the Kyrgyz constituted a distinct people, separate from the Kazakhs. In the years 1855–1859, Through meticulous field research and the collection of extensive materials, Chokan demonstrated the fallacy of this opinion. In ‘Sketches of Dzungaria,’ he made the following particularly important scientific conclusion: ‘Concluding my ethnographic notes on the Buruts and Uysuns [Kyrgyzes and Kazakhs of the Senior Zhuz], I consider it necessary to emphasize that these two entirely distinct peoples should not be confused... Even Humboldt and Richter... believed that the Buruts specifically constituted the Great Kaysak Horde and that this horde should be differentiated from the Small and Middle ones.’ However, this was a grave error on the part of the esteemed authorities of science. The Great, Middle, and Small Kirghiz-Kaisak hordes constitute a single people — the ‘Kazakh’—distinct from the Kirghiz, who are referred

¹ Valikhanov Ch. Ch. Collected Works in Five Volumes.— Vol. I.— Alma-Ata: Great Soviet Encyclopedia, 1984, p. 79.

² Valikhanov Ch. Ch. Collected Works in Five Volumes.— Vol. 5.— Alma-Ata, 1985.— pp. 276–279.

to by the Chinese as Buruts, and by the Russians as Dikokamennye or Black. These two peoples differ in language, origin, and customs...»¹.

Chokan Valikhanov died in 1865. At the initiative of his relatives, a vaulted tomb constructed of fired brick was erected over his grave in Altyn-Emel. Later, in 1881, at this mazar, by order of the Governor-General of the Turkestan region, K. Kaufman, and according to a design by architect P. Zenkov, a marble plaque was installed bearing the inscription: 'Here lie the remains of Staff Captain Chokan Chingisovich Valikhanov, who passed away in 1865. At the request of Turkestan Governor-General Kaufman I, in recognition of Valikhanov's scholarly merits, this monument was erected by Lieutenant General Kolpakovsky in 1881.'. In 1989, the marble slab was replaced with its replica, while the original is preserved in the Museum-Memorial Complex 'Altyn-Emel.'

Over time, the mazar fell into ruin; it was rediscovered in 1945. In 1958, a five-meter obelisk made of orange granite was erected above the grave. In his memoirs, Dinmukhamed Akhmedovich Konayev writes: 'From Panfilov (the name of the city of Zharkent from 1942 to 1991) we set out for Shokan Valikhanov's cemetery.' After reviewing it, we decided to erect a monument at Chokan Valikhanov's grave in the Altyn-Emel Gorge. The project was completed shortly thereafter. A sum of 240 rubles was allocated for the monument's construction. The monument was erected in 1958». The obelisk is crowned with a hemisphere of a globe — a symbol of travel. On the front side is a bronze bas-relief of Chokan Valikhanov. At the base is a marble plaque bearing a commemorative epitaph. The obelisk is a popular site visited by numerous tourists².

Chokan Valikhanov's legacy contains a number of 'white spots'—uncertain or contested aspects that have yet to receive definitive explanation. The active engagement of young researchers may provide answers to several complex questions concerning the scholar's fate.

Thus, Chokan Chingisovich Valikhanov accomplished a scientific achievement that combined not only profound scholarly analysis with a keen interest in the traditions and customs of the studied peoples, but also personal courage, the ability to swiftly navigate changing situations, and maintain secrecy.

¹ Masanov E. Outstanding Scientist of the Kazakh People Ch. Valikhanov // Issues of General Ethnography and Anthropology. — 1965. — p. 64.

² Azarov A. Memorial to Shokan Valikhanov. 23.04.2016. — URL: www.azattyq.org/a/memorial-chokana-valikhanova/27691206.html; accessed Konaev's Memoir-Essay 'Such Was the Era' / Aud. ed. Serik Abdirayimuly. — Almaty: Daur, Yntymaq, 1992. — 445 pp.

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THEORETICAL ISSUES OF STUDYING THE KARAKALPAK EPIC

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***Annotation.** The musical culture of the Karakalpak people is an original phenomenon with a centuries-old history, which in its origins is closely related to the work of related peoples inhabiting the territory of Central Asia. Karakalpak folklore has a variety of genres and forms, which embody history, way of life, customs and traditions. Oral folk art is the basic foundation of the richest spiritual heritage of the Karakalpaks, in which dastans occupy a particularly important place. The topic of this article is determined by the need to revive national traditions and aims to highlight some of the problems in the field of studying the epic heritage of the Karakalpaks.*

***Keywords:** Karakalpak epic heritage, dastan, bakhsi, zhyrau, dastan melodies, performance.*

Over the centuries, the Karakalpak people have created truly amazing, unique and original treasures that form the foundation of their spiritual culture, embodied primarily in epic tales — dastans¹, in the art of singer-storytellers zhyrau² and

¹ Dastan is a word borrowed from the Persian language, applied to epic works of both written, classical and oral, folk literature. In Central Asia, as well as in the Caucasus, and in many other neighboring countries of the Middle and Near East, epic, epic narrative is represented by the genre of dastan.

² Zhyrau — “storyteller” comes from the word “zhyr” (“epic”, “epic poem”), and the word “zhyrlau” means “to perform an epic poem to the accompaniment of kobyz”, experts and performers of Karakalpak heroic dastans.

bakhsy¹ (baksy), various genres of song and dance creativity, as well as in instrumental melodies and plays [2,30].

The most difficult of these sources are dastans, which, being passed down from generation to generation, had a great impact on the improvement of personality throughout the socio-historical development of society. According to I. T. Sagitov, “The Karakalpak epic is a great wealth of the spiritual culture of the Karakalpak people, its contribution to the treasury of world culture” [4,102].

Karakalpak epic works, called dastans, are divided into heroic tales, lyrical poems, dastans of a fabulous nature, and historical dastans (borrowed from other peoples).

Heroic dastans such as “Alpamys”, “Koblan”, “Kyrk-kyz”, “Er-Shora”, “Bozuglan”, “Er-Ziuar”, “Kurbanbek”, “Zhazkelen”, “Er-Kosai” and others are widely known.

Works of oral folk art are created and preserved in a living folk tradition thanks to the art of folk storytellers — its creators and performers, combining an actor, a storyteller, a singer and a poet. Unlike other peoples of the Central Asian region, the Karakalpak epic heritage has historically developed two performing traditions of dastan creativity — bakhsy and zhyrau, which are preserved at the present time. It should be emphasized that bakhsy and zhyrau are the leading areas of Karakalpak creative activity, embodying the specifics of the musical language of the karakalpak epic. Bakhsi mostly perform dastans of lyrical content, and zhyrau — heroic. The musical instrument of the bakhsa is the *duitar*, and that of the zhyrau is the *kobyz*.

Issues related to the study and promotion of the national musical heritage are always relevant, in demand and in the focus of promising fundamental research by scientists around the world. Studying the rich and diverse layer of musical creativity of each nation gives us the opportunity and broad prospects for theoretical and historical substantiation of the originality and uniqueness of musical art, at the same time, awareness of the true historical value and inner spiritual potential of each nation.

The centuries-old cultural heritage of the Karakalpak people, based on oral folk art, is a vivid confirmation of this. Karakalpak traditional music and its musical and theoretical features represent one of the little-studied areas requiring special scientific research in the field of theoretical musicology.

¹ Bakhsy is the creator, bearer, and keeper of the lyrical and musical tradition. According to historical data, the creativity of the Karakalpak Bakhsi was inherited from other Turkic peoples, in particular Uzbek and Turkmen at the turn of the XVIII–XIX centuries. Uzbeks, Turkmens, and Uighurs call bakhs “bagshi”, Kazakhs and Kirghizs “baksy”, Azerbaijani “ozan”, “ashug”, Georgians “masagan”, and Armenians “gusan”.

The first information about the work of folk performers was presented in the works of folklore philologists. In particular, the general issues of historical-theoretical, aesthetic-philosophical, etymological, comparative-typological aspects of the study of the epic genre, as well as the specifics of its artistic, pictorial and poetic foundations are touched upon in the works of folklore scholars, orientalists and literary critics A.Lord, V.Zhirmunsky, H.Zarifov, M.Khamraev, H.Khamraev, K.Rayhl and others.

Karakalpak epic musical creativity, its ethnogenesis, genre, stylistic and performance features represent a little-studied area in Russian musicology. The study of the musical language of the epic of the peoples of Central Asia, including Karakalpak traditional music, and issues of performing art are reflected in the studies of V.Vinogradov, F.Karomatli, T.Adambayeva, L.Kopbaeva, S.Khisamova, A.Azimova, R.Abdullaev, B.Matyakubov, P.Paluaniyazov, G.Khodzhametova, K.Kurbanov, and S.Berdikhanova [2,27].

In the study of A.Azimova [3.7], the patterns of the syntax of Eastern monody were studied, and in the comparative-typological aspect, the main and specific features of the musical language of the Uzbek, Karakalpak and Uighur peoples were revealed.

It is necessary to note the appearance of such a work as “Metrorhythmic foundations of karakalpak dastans” by Shakhida Berdikhanova, which became an important step in the study of the national culture of the karakalpaks and the peoples of the Central Asian region. The difficulty of studying this issue for many years has been due to the lack of musicological research, as well as fixed musical notation (due to the oral transmission of dastans in performing practice) and the specifics of its existence, the lack of full-fledged musical recordings and transcriptions.

Studying the karakalpak epic heritage, it was determined that there are only a small number of audio and musical recordings of dastans. Which undoubtedly caused some difficulties in learning the musical language of the Dastans. In addition, a significant part of the recordings of dastans and, in general, samples of karakalpak oral folk art were mainly conducted in the period of the 30–80s of the twentieth century.

It should be noted that there are fairly complete records of the texts of the dastans and considerable work has been done by philologists and folklorists to study the artistic and poetic content of the epic, but at the same time the musical component remained out of the field of view of researchers.

The reason for this, in our opinion, is the underestimation of the musical creativity of the folk performers bakhshy and zhyrau, as well as the lack of musicologists.

This situation had a negative impact on the fate of the epic, many of the melodies in their entirety did not reach us or were transformed, and the magnetic recordings became unusable, and a significant part of them was lost. Therefore, the

above indicates how important it is to preserve and record samples of traditional musical heritage in a timely manner.

In connection with which a number of problems have arisen that require investigation, namely:

1. The studies of karakalpak scientists lack a complete picture of the genre composition of the karakalpak epic, which requires further study;

2. The lack of information on the periodization, specifics and content of dastans, which indicates the need to create and substantiate a source base in this area;

3. Identification of the peculiarities of the performing traditions of the schools of Karakalpak Zhyrau and Bakhsy;

4. Lack of educational literature covering historical and theoretical issues of traditional karakalpak music.

In our opinion, solving the above problems is important for further understanding of all forms of musical language, the foundation of which is oral traditional music, the richest cultural heritage of the karakalpak people. After all, thanks to the epic, it is possible to know the history, way of life, ethnic roots and, in general, the spiritual world of the karakalpaks.

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ZOOMORPHIC ORNITHOLOGICAL METAPHORS AND SIMILES PLAYING ON STUPIDITY

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Abstract: *The article examines zoomorphic metaphors and similes that play on stupidity and low intellectual level in English linguistic culture, using phraseological units and illustrative contexts from literary works by English-language authors. Emphasis is placed on zoomorphic metaphors and similes based on the image of a bird.*

The purpose of the article is to identify typical metaphors and similes based on the image of a bird in English linguistic culture, to determine the role metaphors and similes play in creating a multifaceted image, and to highlight the characteristic features of birds projected onto humans, and vice versa.

The research methods are determined by the purpose and objectives of the study. The primary method is descriptive, implemented through the techniques of systematization, generalization, and interpretation of linguistic material. Linguistic methods include contextual analysis and semantic interpretation.

The article's key provisions, conclusions, and materials can be used to address intercultural communication issues and in teaching foreign (English) languages, as zoomorphic metaphors offer valuable cultural information and rich didactic potential. Knowledge of the metaphorical zoomorphic expressions of the target language allows for a better understanding of the native speaker's mentality, culture, and national worldview.

Keywords: *zoonym, simile, zoomorphic metaphor = zoometaphor, conceptual metaphor, ornithological metaphor, linguaculture, phraseological unit, anthroposphere; ambivalence of zoomorphic metaphor*

Introduction. The article focuses on the «Human — Bird» metaphorical model. It describes ornithological metaphors and similes. The authors adopt a broad interpretation of zoomorphic metaphor, which allows to encompass instances where the name and image of an animal are transferred to a human being, to whom zoomorphic characteristics (habits, lifestyle, physical characteristics, disposition, appearance, etc.) are attributed.

Zoomorphic metaphors represent one of the most regular models of metaphorical nomination, attributing certain characteristics and properties of animals to humans and implying evaluative connotations [20]. They regularly come to the attention of researchers based on materials from structurally different languages and are considered in a comparative sense [3], [9], [18], [21], [23], as an integral part of proverbs and saying and phraseological units [10], [13], [14], [22], from the point of view of ethnocultural specificity [1], cultural aspects [12], the linguistic picture of the world [17], in a methodological sense [6], etc. Characterizing a person and their activities, they belong to the anthroposphere.

Of interest to us are the negative qualities of stupidity, dullness, and low intellectual level, as expressed in the article's title, reflected and embodied in the corresponding zoological metaphors of English linguistic culture.

The article continues the line of research established in [5], [3], [4], [6], [7], [8] and others.

Results and discussion. The concept of «stupidity,» explored in this article based on ornithological metaphors and similes, signifies a complete or partial lack of intelligence (often referred to as «foolishness» and «stupidity») and a lack of logical thought. Typically, when a person's intelligence is denied — that is, when they speak of a limited, narrow-minded mind, hint at a low intellectual level, point out oddities and behavioral deviations — they resort to metaphors based on zoonyms such as «**ass,**» «**cow,**» «**donkey,**» and «**sheep,**» which refer to domestic animals, and to poultry such as «**bird,**» «**chicken,**» «**hen,**» «**goose,**» and «**turkey.**» The zoological metaphor «**cow,**» for example, is widely used to describe an unpleasant woman, someone disliked or considered stupid (silly cow), as well as an obese or plump woman (fat cow). Fiction abounds with illustrative examples:

She gathered up her bag and they parted with mutual expressions of affection and goodwill.

‘**Silly old bitch,**’ he said when the door was closed behind her.

‘**Pompous old ass.**’ She hissed as she went down in the elevator. [Maugham. Theatre, p. 160].

‘Oh, fuck off, **you stupid cow** — don’t speak to me like I’m some fucking servant.’ [James. Dead Simple, p. 420].

‘**Stupid cow,** doesn’t have a clue!’ her lips burst into a massive grin, her whole face alight with joy. ‘Not a clue!’ [James. Dead Simple, p. 196].

Descriptions of human mental faculties also provide grounds for resorting to vivid ornithological metaphors and similes. To describe a narrow-minded, stupid, clueless, or incredibly superficial person, the descriptive expressions **birdbrain** or **birdbrained** can be used.

Stupidity is reflected in numerous ornithological zoomorphic metaphors based on the images of birds such as **hen, chicken, goose, coot, cuckoo, owl, and bird**. Such figurative comparisons as “**as silly/stupid as a goose; as stupid as a coot; as stupid as an owl**” are common. [15], [16]. Two contexts from A. Christie’s detective novels are illustrative:

“I’ll find her myself,” declared Tommy. “She’s somewhere. Whether it’s north, south, east, or west, I’ve no idea — and she was **a silly cuckoo** not to leave a word when she rang up where she was.” [Christie. *By the Pricking of my Thumbs*, p. 105]. Tommy is indignant that his wife, having gone out on some urgent matter, rashly neglected to tell him where she was when she called and turned out to be a silly cuckoo.

Poor old Dad, he’s got **less sense than a chicken!** [Christie. *Why didn’t they ask Evans?* p. 9]. The protagonist speaks critically of his father.

Perhaps because of the idea that geese look stupid, the goose has become a symbol of stupidity, laziness, and wildness in English-speaking culture. In English proverbs and sayings, the image is usually negative. In the example below, a man ironically addresses a woman, affectionately calling her a «silly little goose»:

“We’re right in the middle of the beach, what if someone comes along?”

“No one is going to come here at night, **little goose,**” he said. [Collins. *Love & Desire & Hate*, p. 215].

Analyzing instances of the «man — animal» metaphor in Gerald Durrell’s works, researchers note that at times Durrell’s approach to describing humans and comparing them to animals is literally striking. Through the writer’s comparisons, it becomes clear that he sometimes considers birds to be more intelligent and wiser than humans:

«The minute figure on the bed lifted thin, pale lids and looked at me with **great tawny eyes that were as bright and intelligent as a bird’s**» [Durrell. *My Family...*, p. 223]. The elderly mother of the eccentric Kralewski, who turned out to be a great bird lover and taught the young Durrell the basics of natural history, appears to the boy as a bird with lively and intelligent eyes. Her laughter also seems to the boy like the musical twitter of a bird:

The given context demonstrates such a quality of zoomorphic metaphor as its ambivalence, understood as the ability to express antagonistic concepts conditioned by the ambivalence of our feelings and emotions. It also provides an opportunity to dwell particularly on the property of ambivalence, when the same zoonym is endowed with opposite attributes. Thus, in English linguistic culture and in the West

in general, the **owl** is attributed with intelligence and wisdom. For example, the expressions «**(as) solemn (wise) as an owl**» are widely used to describe a person wise and important, possessing deep knowledge and extensive experience:

Hopkirk was a **wise owl** with many years of service behind him; he commanded a lot of respect in the force and was well liked. [James. Looking Good Dead, p. 463].

Everyone turned to look at Joe, who had **the air of a wise old owl** at the other end of the table. [Bennet. A Three Dog Problem, p. 165].

However, in India, the word **ullu** («**owl**» in Hindi) is used as an insult to a stupid person, and the address «**son of an owl**» denotes an idiot and is used to describe an idiot. This maybe due to the different ways these cultures perceive owl behavior and therefore associate them with different things? However, alongside the phraseological unit «**as solemn/wise as an owl**» there exists the expression with the opposite meaning «**as stupid as an owl**»:

‘Emily was always **as stupid as an owl**,’ said Miss Blenkinshop [Thackeray. Vanity Fair, ch. VI. Cited in: Kunin 1984, p. 735].

Conclusion. In this article, devoted to zoomorphic metaphors and similes that play on the stupidity and low intellectual level of people in English linguistic culture, based on the phraseological units and illustrative contexts from literary works by English-language authors, the emphasis was placed on zoomorphic metaphors exemplified by the image of a bird. The study confirms the assertion that while zoonyms lack evaluative connotations, the transfer of animal names to humans, animal traits, and the creation of zoomorphic metaphors are associated with evaluative connotations, mostly negative.

The «bird — man» metaphor is among the most widely exploited zoomorphic metaphors. In the English-language tradition, birds are generally perceived as symbols of stupidity, but some zoomorphic images are ambivalent and allow for opposing meanings and interpretations.

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DECODING THE SHIFT: HOW CULTURAL PERCEPTION AND ETHICS ARE RESHAPING THE LANGUAGE OF TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. *This paper analyzes the evolution of terminology in autonomous systems and artificial intelligence, arguing that lexical changes reflect deeper shifts in cultural perception, ethical norms, and social responsibility. It demonstrates that terminology is an active tool for shaping reality, not a passive descriptive medium. The study reveals a multifaceted process driven by the need for greater accuracy, neutrality, and inclusivity. This involves purging harmful connotations, replacing aggressive language, ensuring gender neutrality, and achieving legal precision. The analysis concludes that terminological evolution signifies the IT industry's maturation as it acknowledges its societal influence. Consequently, the conscious selection of terms is both a technical necessity and a sociocultural imperative, essential for fostering ethical communication and building trustworthy human-machine interactions.*

Keywords: *ethics, evolution of terminology, inclusivity, sociocultural perception, terminology.*

The evolution of terminology in the field of autonomous systems and artificial intelligence reflects not only technological progress, but also, as practice shows, the changing cultural perception of terminology. This process is far from accidental and serves as a clear indicator of how the technology community reacts to shifts in social norms, ethical requirements, and marketing realities. The programming language and system descriptions are gradually being purged of random and sometimes harmful connotations, striving for greater accuracy, neutrality and inclusivity. These changes initiated both within the community and under the influence of external socio-cultural factors, demonstrate that terminology is an active tool for shaping reality, and not just a passive means of describing it.

Let us emphasize that consideration of these diverse cases allows for a deeper analysis of the multifaceted nature of the evolution of the technical language. This process includes not only the transition from outdated concepts to modern ones

but also a fundamental revision of the metaphors that perpetuate discriminatory practices, shifting the focus from problems to solutions, and striving for legal and semantic accuracy. Such a comprehensive analysis makes it possible to identify systemic patterns and vectors of professional vocabulary development, which reflects the most important semantic and pragmatic changes not only in the field of artificial intelligence, but also in the IT industry as a whole.

The evolution of terminology in the field of autonomous systems and artificial intelligence reflects not only technological progress, but also, as practice shows, the changing cultural perception of terminology.

We start the analysis with the terms *daemon* and *agent*, since these concepts play a key role in the evolution of concepts of autonomous software systems in computer science. The term *daemon* traditionally refers to a background process in UNIX operating systems that is invisible to the user and ensures the operation of system services. In turn, *agent* reflects a later stage of system development and describes autonomous programs that are able to make decisions on behalf of the user or the operating system.

Let us emphasize that considering only these two terms allows for a deeper analysis of the transition from technically neutral but hidden processes to active ones, which undoubtedly reflects the most important semantic and pragmatic changes in the field of artificial intelligence.

Let us start with the term *daemon*. In ancient Greek culture, it meant ‘a deity or an intermediary spirit with the ability to influence people and events, but not necessarily evil’. In ancient philosophy, for example, *daemon* was interpreted as entities connecting people with the gods, having the functions of advisers and patrons. However, with the spread of Christianity, the term acquired a negative connotation, turning into a ‘demon’ as the embodiment of evil forces.

In computer science, since the 1960s, the term *daemon* has come to denote a background process that occurs invisibly to the user and performs system tasks such as processing print queues or network requests. Historically, the choice of this word was due to an analogy with the Maxwell’s demon — an imaginary intelligent being of microscopic size, the main character of the thought experiment invented by the British physicist James Clerk Maxwell. Maxwell himself never used the word ‘demon’ when describing the experiment, his agent opened the door between the cameras as a ‘finite being.’ This entity was first called a ‘demon’ by William Thomson to describe Maxwell’s agent in the journal *Nature* in 1874 [Leff, Rex, 2003]. Thus, the term *daemon* emphasized the invisibility and autonomy of the process, rather than its sinister nature.

The semantic evolution of the term *daemon* demonstrates the transition from a mystical and religious meaning to a technically neutral one. In antiquity and in the Middle Ages, a demon was a creature with supernatural abilities, in the

Christian tradition — an evil spirit. In computer science, the term has been reinterpreted — daemon has come to denote a hidden process that is necessary for the functioning of the system.

Pop culture has also influenced the perception of the terms. For example, the ‘Maxwell’s demon’, which we have mentioned above, in physics symbolizes an invisible operator controlling chaos at the micro level, and ‘Agent Smith’ in the movie *The Matrix* is the personification of an autonomous but controlled system. In modern information technologies, and in particular in the field of artificial intelligence, the term *daemon* has gradually been replaced due to negative associations and the risk of anthropomorphization, which can cause anxiety among users. Instead, in the 1980s and 1990s, due to the development of artificial intelligence and multi-agent systems, the term *agent* came into use [Online Etymology Dictionary]. In this context, *an agent* is an autonomous program or system capable of independently making decisions and acting in the interests of the user or the system itself. The transition to this term reflects the desire to move away from previous negative connotations and emphasize the purposefulness and usefulness of such systems.

Undoubtedly, the choice of terms has an impact on the perception of users, their trust and willingness to interact with autonomous systems, which is confirmed by a number of linguistic and psycholinguistic studies [Reeves, Nass, 1996]. Terminology, especially in technical and scientific fields, has not only a cognitive, but also an emotional and evaluative effect, which affects the formation of attitudes towards the object of designation. In particular, terms with negative or mystical connotations, such as *daemon*, can cause users to feel wary, distrustful, and even fearful, which reduces their willingness to use the appropriate technology. This is because emotionally colored words activate associations in the mind that go beyond the purely technical meaning and can increase anxiety, especially in a non-professional audience. In contrast, terms with more neutral or positive semantics, such as the word *agent*, contribute to the formation of an image of a predictable and controlled assistant among users, which increases the level of trust and motivation to interact with the system. However, changing *daemon* to agent is not the only example. Let us consider the other cases that illustrate different aspects of the same trend.

Another example of the terminological shift is the transition from the term *Black Box* to the *Opaque Model*, which was dictated by the growing demand for transparency. The original term, *Black Box*, was a classic engineering term for a system whose internal structure is unknown, but its inputs and outputs can be observed. However, in the context of responsible AI, the term *Black Box* has acquired a sharply negative connotation, becoming synonymous with unaccountability, inexplicability and potential danger. Regulators, the public, and the developers themselves began demanding transparency, and this term directly contradicted it, as if justifying an unwillingness to ‘look inside’. As a replacement, the new terms

opaque model and *explicable AI* have been established. These are more neutral and descriptive terms that shift the focus from stating a problem to finding a solution.

Similar motives — but already in the plane of social responsibility — were behind the transition from the *master/slave* bundle (sometimes *leader/slave*) to pairs of type primary/replica. The original term *master/slave* has been widely used in engineering and IT to describe an asymmetric relationship where one process or device controls another. The change was necessary because these terms carry a heavy historical burden of slavery and oppression. Their use came to be seen as racist and socially irresponsible, especially amid the rise of the social justice movement, as they created an unhealthy and offensive metaphor. New terms such as *primary/replica*, *leader/follower*, *main/secondary*, are technically accurate and devoid of offensive connotations, and their adoption by major projects demonstrates the maturity of the industry.

The evolution from *whitelist/blacklist* to *allowlist/blocklist* falls into the same category of changes aimed at eliminating racist microaggressions. The original terms, *whitelist* (allowed) and *blacklist* (blocked), have been used for decades, but they implicitly tied value judgments (white = good, black = bad) to skin colors, which has come to be seen as racist aggressions that do not meet ethical standards. The new terms *allowlist* and *blocklist* are not only politically correct, but also semantically more accurate, as they directly describe the action.

Another aspect — gender neutrality — manifested itself in the change of the term *man* — *in-the-middle on person-in-the-middle*. The original term, *man* — *in-the-middle attack*, is classic, but it is gender-specific, as it uses ‘man’ in the outdated meaning of ‘man’, which does not correspond to reality and excludes women from the context. New terms such as *person-in-the-middle* (if we are talking about a person) or even more precisely *machine-in-the-middle* are considered more inclusive and technically correct.

The desire to mitigate aggression in the language is evident in the transition from *kill switch* to *emergency stop*. The original term, *kill switch*, is used in security systems, but the verb ‘to kill’ carries an unnecessarily aggressive connotation, especially in the context of AI. New terms such as *emergency stop* and *safety switch* are devoid of negative connotations and focus on safety functions.

In other cases, the changes are dictated by the need for legal accuracy, as in the case of changing *spam* to *unsolicited commercial email*. The original term, *spam*, is a vivid cultural meme, but it is considered too colloquial and unprofessional for legal documents where precise wording is required. The new term, *unauthorized commercial email (UCE)*, is a legally precise definition that unambiguously describes the essence of the phenomenon.

Finally, an important change in the field of teamwork psychology was the transition from *bug/defect* to *issue/feature request*. The original terms, *bug* and

defect, are classic, but in an agile environment they can sound accusatory and create confrontation. New terms such as *issue (problem)* or *feature request* are more neutral and focus on the solution rather than on finding the culprits, which makes communication more constructive.

Undoubtedly, the choice of terms has a fundamental impact on the perception of users, their trust and willingness to interact with autonomous systems, which is confirmed by a number of linguistic and psycholinguistic studies [Reeves, Nass, 1996]. Terminology, especially in technical and scientific fields, has not only a cognitive, but also an emotional and evaluative load, which affects the formation of attitudes towards the object of designation. In particular, terms with negative or mystical connotations, such as *daemon*, or with socially offensive overtones, such as *master/slave*, can cause users to feel wary, distrust, and even rejection, which reduces their willingness to use appropriate technologies. This is due to the fact that emotionally colored words activate associations in the mind that go beyond the purely technical meaning and can increase anxiety, especially in a non-professional audience.

Research in the field of AI terminology shows that the successful implementation and standardization of terms requires taking into account not only their accuracy and unambiguity, but also pragmatic factors — how the term is perceived in a specific socio-cultural context. Thus, the adaptation of terminology in the field of artificial intelligence and autonomous systems should take into account the psychological reactions of users in order to minimize barriers to perception and increase the effectiveness of communication between humans and machines, as well as within the technological community itself.

In practical terms, this means that when developing new terms or selecting existing ones to describe technologies, it is important to conduct linguistic and socio-cultural analysis, as well as test the perception of terms by the target audience. This approach will contribute to the formation of terminology that will not only accurately reflect the technical characteristics of the systems, but will also promote a positive attitude towards them, reducing user anxiety and increasing their trust, as well as meeting modern ethical standards.

Thus, after analyzing the evolution of the meanings of the terms, we can conclude that in the field of information technology, terms for autonomous and complex systems evolve along several vectors.

The higher the level of autonomy of the system and the degree of its interaction with humans, the more conscious and responsible the choice of terminology should be. Understanding this process is important for an informed choice of terminology in the development and implementation of new systems, as well as for effective and ethical communication between specialists and a wide audience. The evolution of language in IT is not a fashion statement, but a sign of the maturity of the industry, which is beginning to fully realize its social and cultural responsibilities.

Thus, the process of changing terminology in IT is a constant dialogue between corporate policy, grassroots community initiatives and the inertia of established practice. This is not a smooth or linear process, but rather complex negotiations, during which the professional field redefines its ethical and cultural boundaries, literally rewriting them in code.

This complex, multi — level mechanism of the change clearly demonstrates that the evolution of language in IT that we are witnessing is a sign of the maturity of an industry that is beginning to fully realize its social and cultural responsibilities.

Therefore, understanding this process is important for an informed choice of terminology in the development and implementation of new systems, as well as for effective and ethical communication between specialists and a wide audience. Choosing a name for a new algorithm or architectural component today is not only a technical, but also a sociocultural decision. Realizing this turns linguistic refactoring from a routine into an act of professional reflection, and the quality of communication into an integral part of the quality of the technological solution itself. By rewriting its terminology, the IT community is not just updating its vocabulary, but actively building a linguistic ecosystem that will be adequate to its growing influence on the lives of each person and society as a whole.

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PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH THE ZOONYM COMPONENT IN TEXTS OF DIFFERENT GENRES

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Abstract: *the article explores the pragmatic features of the use of phraseological units with the zoonym component in the texts of different genres and the peculiarities of their usage.*

Key words: *pragmatics, phraseology, zoonym component.*

Contemporary linguistic studies are characterised by an in-depth examination of the national and cultural aspects of a language, as a language is a component of culture that reflects cultural and historical information about the character of a people and a multitude of facts about the current state of development of the linguistic community. Language acts as a mirror of a people's national culture and is its guardian. One of the most important sources of national and cultural information is considered to be phraseological units, the interpretation of which is a cognitive process of decoding, taking into account knowledge of national culture, traditions, rituals, and traditional models of structuring based on a worldview.

Phraseological units with certain national and cultural semantics are an integral part and one of the means of forming a linguistic worldview for a particular ethnic group that speaks the language. The linguistic worldview is formed with the help of a natural language as a specific type of semiotic system — it is a set of a people's ideas about reality at a certain stage of development of a given ethnic group, recorded in linguistic units. V. A. Maslova notes that phraseological units always indirectly reflect the beliefs of a people, the social structure, and the ideology of their era: 'like morning light reflected in a drop of water' [3: 43].

Currently, linguists are interested in issues related to the functioning of phraseological units in various communicative contexts. Particular attention is paid to the study of the use of phraseological units in human speech, which is considered a communicative-pragmatic aspect of phraseology. The pragmatic function of phraseological units is a 'targeted impact on the addressee' [2: 114].

Used in context, it is closely related to the stylistic function of phraseological units, which, in turn, are related to the concepts of locution, illocution and perlocution.

Based on communicative-pragmatic settings, the main pragmatic parameters of phraseological units can be considered expressiveness, conceptuality, and subtextual information [1: 41]. A study of the pragmatic component of phraseological units shows that, by conveying information about the speaker's emotional and evaluative perception of reality, they are designed to reinforce the communicants' intentionality, i.e. they can convey the speaker's various emotionally charged communicative intentions.

To study the communicative nature of phraseological units, we consider various classifications of phraseological units based on pragmatic criteria. Thus, A. M. Emirva distinguishes between substantive idioms with a personal meaning that characterise a person's social image, phraseological units in the sphere of human emotions, and phraseological units in the cognitive sphere of a person, 'denoting and characterising various cognitive processes: sensations, perception, thinking and speech' [2: 70]. It seems necessary to add to this classification a group of phraseological units that characterise a person's physical abilities. For further research, we will use the presented classification to analyse some examples from fiction and journals.

The first example we will analyse is from fiction.

'Silence, 3KM! I see nothing amusing about spending a week of my life teaching anyone quadratic equations when the result is this...dog's dinner. Everyone, page eighteen. Sit down, Taylor.' [6: 141]

After analysing the dictionary definition of the expression 'dog's dinner', which means 'something that is messy or bungled', we conclude that this phraseological unit belongs to a group of idioms that characterise the sphere of human emotions. The use of this phraseological unit in fiction is due to its emotional imagery. In this communicative situation, the author needs to have a pragmatic effect on the main character and the reader and create a negative image that expresses the character's attitude to the situation.

The following example is also from fiction.

'Who's he?' 'Official stepfather. That house is his house. Don't you know anything, Taylor? Mum and I live there now. They got married last year.' Actually now I remembered. 'What's he like?' 'Brains of a bull.' 'She peered at me round an invisible curtain.' [6: 58]

The example uses the zoonym 'bull'. The author creates a situational metaphor with the component 'brains'. This expression can be classified as an idiom with a meaning that characterises a person's social image. In this speech situation, the image of a bull in English culture and its connotative meaning (strong but stupid) are played upon. The result is an expression with high pragmatic potential that creates a vivid image in the reader's mind.

The use of phraseological units can also be used with a positive connotation:

*'Wow, 'me and Mum, hurried along Regent's Arcade so we'd get to the cinema before Chariots of Fire began, 'you handled those girls amazingly. 'Fancy. 'Mum's shoes smacked the shiny marble. Take that! Take That! Take that! 'An old dear like me being able to handle three spoilt Pollyannas "amazingly". ' (Mum was dead chuffed, really.) 'You spotted them in the first place, Jason. **Old Eagle-eyes.** If I was a sheriff, I'd pay you a reward.'* [6: 138]

In this example, we see a comparison of a character to an animal, expressed by the zoonym 'eagle,' which is often used together with 'eyes,' meaning 'unusually sharp visual powers; keen ability to watch or observe.' This expression can be classified as an idiom with a facial meaning, characterising a person's physical abilities. In this context, a positive attitude towards the character's physical abilities and praise for them is actualised.

Analysing the pragmatic features of the use of phraseological units with a zoonym component in journals, we can give the following example:

*However, his putting has also troubled him and his first objective is to make the cut, which Ballesteros failed to do the year after both his victories. Woosnam names Bernhard Langer as his '**dark horse**' and the German has succeeded in keeping an appropriately low profile even if he has had more practice rounds than anyone.* [Daily Telegraph, elect. edn. of 1992.04.09].

This example uses the expression 'a dark horse' to mean 'a racehorse, competitor, etc., about whom little is known or who unexpectedly wins.' This phrase can be classified as a group of phraseological units denoting cognitive processes. When describing a person with this phrase, the statement becomes more expressive, which will be correctly interpreted by readers in connection with the pragmatic features of this phraseological unit. This expression previously had a different usage, as it referred to the terminology of equestrian sports. Over time, the boundaries of the phrase's usage have expanded, and its pragmatic potential has increased.

Another example from a journalistic article:

*The one who turned up to preside over my fiscal destruction was particularly dismal, a desolately unattractive woman in a pink cardie who looked like **a sitting duck** for household cleanser advertisements.* [Punch. London: Punch Pub. Ltd, 1992, pp. 1367 s-units.]

In this article, the author uses the expression 'a sitting duck — a helpless or easy target or victim' when describing a woman. This phrase can also be classified as a phraseological unit that characterises a person's physical abilities. The phrase enhances the imagery and expressiveness of the statement, which helps readers to better understand and visualise the image of the person. As in the previous example with the phraseological unit "dark horse", the expression "a sitting duck"

can only be found in professional discourse, in particular, “*hunting*”, but later it acquired an additional pragmatic aspect and began to be used in a metaphorical sense when describing a person.

An analysis of the pragmatic potential of the phraseological units considered allows us to conclude that the ability to convey expressive and evaluative information through phraseological units predetermines the pragmatic orientation of these linguistic signs. In light of the above, we conclude that the functioning of phraseological units is carried out in accordance with specific rules governing their use in speech. Phraseology from the point of view of pragmatics has not yet been fully studied and requires further research to confirm the data, as well as to obtain new knowledge and patterns concerning the communicative-pragmatic aspect of phraseology.

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